

Comprehending the Extent and Impact of Digital Transformation:

The case of

The Wealth Management Services Sector in the UK

Submitted

by

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Abstract

As the digital transformation phenomenon continues to grow within the Wealth management services (WMS) sector, the pressure remains at a broader level of the management to explore technological applications to evolve the value creation and competitive advantage. The synthesis of demand and expectations leads the firms to enable strategic initiatives by exposing themselves to newer risks of business transformational shifts and turnaround revenues against investment swiftly.

The research uses the interpretive method with a phenomenological approach to explore the human perspectives from wider hierarchical layers within the WMS firms. The 8months of data collection phase produced extensive data showcasing the complex issues hindering the transformation of legacy approaches. However, despite research studies on the digital transformation phenomenon, there are limitations from a stakeholder's perspective on understanding the complexities of transformations. Instead, the literature focus is on the impact aspect over any specific process of various other industries. Thus, this research contributes to the knowledge body by exploring the granular view of digital transformation in the traditional WMS sector and obstructions in adapting to DT from the perspectives of involved stakeholders.

The research-based thesis is presented in three stages. The first part of the research establishes the foundational constructions linked to the chosen sector by evaluating the broader spectrum on the extent of digital transformation from existing literature leading to the formulation of main research questions. The second part justifies the chosen research methodology for the research study and identifies parameters for stakeholder selection. The last part of research contributes to a growing body of literature and the practical and methodological contribution. The proposed three-stage framework simplifies the evaluating process for practical usage to achieve the Circular Transformational Cycle.

Keywords: Digital transformation, Circular Transformation Cycle, legacy approach, complex transitioning.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

DT- Digital Transformation

WMS- Wealth Management Services

USP – Unique selling proposition

FSI- Financial Service Industry

ROI- Return on investment

Fintech- Financial technology

IDC- International Data Corporation

AI – Artificial Intelligence

IoT- Internet of things

HNI- High net worth individual

UHNI- Ultra-high net worth individual

CSF- Critical Success factor

DC framework – Dynamic capability framework

BFSI- Banking, Financial Services and Insurance

RPA- Robotic process automation

FCA – Financial Conduct Authority

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

This DBA thesis aimed to investigate the perceived understanding of Digital Transformation in the Wealth Management Services sector within the London region, using various stakeholders identified for this research study. It included exploring its extent and impact in the Wealth Management sector as digital change adoption is practised daily. The approach undertaken was an in-depth qualitative study by engaging with the main stakeholders (i.e. senior and middle management executives) and then followed this up with other stakeholders, namely external Digital Transformation consultants and the Wealth Management Services Sector customers.

Thus, this first chapter provides a brief introduction to the study in the context of the current scenario of the traditional Wealth Management Sector (WMS). It also examines the problem situation, leading to the formulation of the research questions that the study attempts to address. The intellectual starting point is reviewed through the literature on the Digital Transformation phenomena in chapter two.

The research design described in chapter three is based on interpretive methodology and describes in detail how the data were collected during semi-structured interviews conducted for eight months. Due to time constraints, I have not attempted comprehensively to review all Digital Transformation practices related to the Wealth Management sector. However, as shown in the findings (Chapter 4), I collected a wealth of information concerning the use of technology in traditional practices and the ways various stakeholders use and relate to it. The findings are organised in terms of stakeholder groups, such that Chapter four describes the views of stakeholder groups thematically analysed sub-themes and groupwise themes.

Therefore, the findings chapter explains how Digital Transformation is perceived by the main stakeholders and provides appropriate quotations.

The data presented in chapter four is then interpreted and analysed in Chapter 5 by referring to the stakeholders on what has been discussed in interviews. This chapter also addresses the original research questions posed and examines the findings using the conceptual framework. The chapter six, I draw some general conclusions, outline the theoretical and practical contributions of research and make recommendations for further research.

Intentions of the research

I intended to make two forms of contribution with my DBA thesis.

1. To offer research results to all concerned stakeholders, especially executives at top-management levels, wealth managers and external digital implementation consultants. The study reveals the significance of participant roles in the integration process of Digital transformation.
2. To contribute knowledge about the relevance and appropriateness of the internal capability funnel for the Digital Transformation adaption in the traditional Wealth Management sector and wider financial industry.

Chapter one structure is as follows: sections 1.1 and 1.2 provide the research background and overview of chosen case study industry scenario. The section 1.3 and 1.4, provides an overview of traditional perspectives of the sector and challenges encountered by WMS firm in their digital transitioning. The following section 1.5 develops the problematization approach of the existing industry scenario following the formulation of research questions, aim and objectives. Section 1.6 explains the significance of this research to the chosen case study sector and briefing the research rationale. Section 1.7 and 1.8 provide a brief explanation of the chosen research method, followed by an overview of the thesis structure, and section 1.9 summarises the chapter.

1.1: Research background

Digital Transformation (DT) enhances customer engagement, productivity and value proposition by adopting disruptive technologies (Ebert & Duarte,2018). For a decade and over now, every business sector shifting its focus towards digital transformation and increasing the budgets towards new technology adoption. Holistically embracing disruptive technologies is in pursuit of meeting the growing demands of customers, business sustainability and competitive advantage. According to Gale(2019), only 28% of the business organisations across industries are flourishing in their DT transitions despite the existing capabilities. At the same time, another 70% of organisations are unsure of their capabilities for DT navigation (Gale,2019). According to Simpson(2020), the estimated forecast over the total spending on DT by 2023 is to reach \$2.3 trillion worldwide across all industries. In line with ongoing developments, HBR (2019) study report reveals that around \$900 billion was wasted worldwide until 2018 from the total investment of \$1.3 trillion in DT(Behnam et al.2019). This scenario portrays the need to explore the reasons and impact of investment wastage in the space of the DT phenomenon, which is investigated inadequately in current literature.

The rapid technological developments considerably influence the organisation's digital plans and investment strategy. The changes disrupt existing internal and external legacy processes and the capability within the organisational ecosystem. The evolutionary impact of digital change entrenches the changes in business models and influences society and customer behaviour(Westerman et al.,2014; Schwab,2016). According to Brynjolfsson & McAfee (2014), the main characteristic of digital change in the 4.0 industry revolution is the rapid technology progression. As per practitioners and academic scholars from the change management space, states the central idea of reoccurring digital transformation change branches out into newer revenue-generating and agile business models (Westerman et al., 2011; Bharadwaj et al., 2013; Henriette et al.,2015; Coltman et al., 2015; Bounfour,2016).

The existing literature in context to the digital transformation primarily contributed to identifying the key influencing and driving factors and the impact of these factors in the derailment in embracing the digital change by the organisations. The leading practitioners and academic researchers have held few exogenous and endogenous elements like capability, culture, organisational approach, leadership, regulatory controls and integrational issues upheld as core issues derailment of DT adaption process. (Kotter, 2012; Westerman et al, 2015; Henriette et al., 2015; Morakanyane et al., 2017; Kane, 2017; Vial 2019). The increase of research interest in the DT phenomenon by researchers from various disciplines has created vast and diverse perceptions and broader knowledge. However, available theoretical literature and information are fragmented and not unified enough to be applied in a given business scenario. Thus, there is inadequate evidence about the validity and suitability of the discussed factors from earlier literature to the chosen case study scenario. Hence, researchers and practitioners' characteristics of the DT phenomenon presented in the literature cannot be generalised for the WMS sector, as it operates within specific regulatory framework market conditions and segments. Thus, available views over the identified factors cannot be generalised over the existing scenario of the WMS sector.

1.2: Overview of the Wealth Management Services Sector

The existence of the Wealth Management Services (WMS) sector dates back to 200 years old business sector within the Financial Services Industry (Zakrzewski et al., 2020). In simple words, it is comprehensive consultation and advisory services provided by financial advisors, who are experts in financial investment planning, regulation and risk compliance, providing their expert advice and associated services to affluent & potential wealthy customers. The essence of digital shift by traditional WMS organisations embracing the DT and shifting from the legacy business model is to provide agile and efficient services to their existing customers. To target and capture the broader customer segments by contributing towards value creation and business sustainability in a competitive market environment. The concept of industrial revolution 4.0 is about increasing value creation by reducing the actual time gap in meeting

customer expectations by leveraging innovative technologies is the aim of traditional WMS firms. However, with a tsunami of technological innovations, the traditional firms are struggling to catch up with the speed of technology and adapt to it. The constant surge in research by academicians and practitioners about "Digital Transformation" has created vast clarity about the myriad of digital innovations that changed the business and society perspectives over critical elements like customer engagement and services levels. The UK has an estimated potential of 2.2 million investors over the two decades, and personal financial Wealth globally had increased triple times from \$80 trillion in 1999 to \$226 trillion in 2019(UK fact sheet,2020). This growth scale encourages the traditional WMS firms to constantly upgrade their products and customer services by building the potential capabilities for growing market size.

There is no formal definition of the Wealth Management Services sector. However, the research attempts to define this traditional sector as a comprehensive advisory process with integrated and customized planning, analysis and risk management with various products and services to all customer segments. This consultative advisory service is provided to wealthy affluent customers and managing their investment portfolios on a certain percentage as fees agreed. The customers of the WMS firms are categorised based on their investment portfolio size, and the categories mainly are the UHNWI (Ultra High Net-Worth individuals) clients with investment portfolio sizes between £20-30 million. The clients above £5million in investment size are HNWI (High Net-Worth Individual), and retail customers are generally investors with investment sizes between £10,000-50,000. Holistically, the advisory function is significant is a prime, and revenue-generating unit in the traditional WMS sector, precisely it includes the consultation with evaluation, risk assessment and profiling of customers to secure their financial interest, appetite and expected gains. This comprehensive service model is a mature business with trust and transparency factors, fuelling the relationship between wealth managers and their clients.

Advisory consulting is a complex matrix of expert knowledge in the regulatory framework and financial products (stocks, bonds, cash investment & properties). These expert skills of advisors are significant in upkeeping the trust and loyalty factor along with agile and efficient services to the customers. The importance of using the term “legacy” because these processes, service model and the value proposition have continued since the inception of the WMS sector, expect adaption of digitization and digitalization of a few key processes within the administrative and onboarding documentation related processes. The infiltration of advanced technologies disrupted the dynamics of traditional processes and procedures in managing customer relationships. In the WMS sector, the impact of disruption is much higher than compared to other verticals like the banking and insurance sector.

While private banking, insurance and other financial sectors are steadily transforming their business and service models with the adoption of AI, big data and cloud infrastructure technology to digitalize the key front-ending processes to their customers. While in the traditional WMS sector, the front end process and onboarding are still following the legacy model as there are various challenges and constraints in automating the processes.

According to Oliver Wyman's report (The State of The Financial Services industry, 2020), most CFO's (Chief Financial Officer) have revealed that 50% of their digital investment spending is wasted and cannot identify the leading cause. Similarly, a report from HBR(2019) reveals that \$1.3 trillion was spent on DT initiatives till 2018 and around \$900 billion was wasted globally as the set goal of digital transformation were not achieved. However, issues highlighted by academic researchers and practitioners in perspective about DT failures are associated with critical hindrances in integrational challenging aspects with traditional service organisations. The major inferences are drawn from available literature highlight that traditional businesses fail in embracing DT successfully due to alignment issues in setting the culture with the right talent with the right capabilities(Kohnke et al., 2016; Hess et al., 2016; Kane,2017; Vial,2019; Matt et al.,2015).

As a consequence of digital adaption failures in the WMS firms, the repetitive change and lack of information impact the underlying trust factor with customers and provide space for resistance and panic situations among employees within the business ecosystem. In contrast, this situation greatly benefits dynamic Fintech firms to use pull strategy by attracting the customer base with their niche, specialised service with the agile delivery mechanism. Critically, it is vital to understand the reasons for DT investment wastage and factors impeding the embracing of DT vision. Hence, this research explores the relevant reasons for digital adaption failure by traditional firms in the WMS sector. Bilan et al.,(2019) mention that drivers for successful adaption of DT are vertical and horizontal integration within firms. The complex influx of digital technologies with the traditional business model requires complete accountability from stakeholders within a complete unified vision in value creation. Academic researchers Vial (2019) and Kane (2017) contribute by bringing their perspectives

about the following factors: transparency, comprehensive knowledge, and capability development, and these factors will impact the successful digital transformation rate. There is a lack of consensus on a unified understanding of the digital transformation phenomenon within business practices, derailing the process without complete visibility. Although the information is available on DT conceptually, it is fragmented or limited to the specific context of the case study industry. The characteristics of DT phenomena by Vial(2019) and Kane (2017) cannot be generalised for a given scenario in the WMS sector as internal and external variables in terms of influence and compelling factors will differ in each business segment.

However, the following research studies (Versteeg & Bouwman.,2006; Kotter,2012; Westerman et al., 2014; Schwab, 2016; Morakanyane et al., 2017; Kane, 2017; Henriette et al., 2015; Chanas, 2017; Nambian et al., 2019; Vial, 2019; Verhoef et al., 2021; Vaska et al., 2021) have investigated and attempted to organise the critical attributes of the digital transformation phenomenon in focus to various business case studies. However, as mentioned earlier, the various factors drawn from the above studies do not validate the existing problems in the WMS sector, as the business nature and controlled regulatory ecosystem is different compared to earlier discussed case studies in the literature. The WMS sector is under-researched in the academic literature perspective to understand the extent of the digital transformation phenomenon. Hence, this research takes the lead to explore the DT phenomenon and know the reasons for the DT adaption failures and impact.

1.3: The Wealth Management Services Sector perspectives: Digital Transformation

There is no specific yardstick to measure the digital readiness of the traditional WMS organisations. Still, there is no universally accepted single framework on digital readiness & maturity of the business model, but there are contributions from academic scholars and practitioners in designing the maturity frameworks for successful DT adaption(Schumacher et al., 2015; Matt et al., 2015; De carolis et al.,2017; KPMG Global business services - maturity assessment, 2016; Sanchez et al.,2018). Moran & Brightma (2001) comment on the digital

transformation era as a "Whirlpool change process". Chanies & Hess (2016) agree on integrating resources and competencies towards creating the unified vision for impactful change. Similarly, in agreement with Chanies & Hess(2016) outcomes, the traditional WMS firms are breaking the status quo by introducing change management by adapting the technology but failing in building and integrating the efforts in the right direction to create a unified vision across all involved stakeholders.

Additionally, the literature indicates the significant role of leaders within WMS firms in developing the unified approach and setting the right culture. Kane et al.(2017) and Matt et al.(2015) have stated in their respective research that the lack of propagating the integration of values with vision within all organisational layers leads to a lack of comprehensive understanding, knowledge and strategy decision on the phenomenon, leads to a mismatch of vision alignment.

Drawing upon the outcomes from Matt et al.(2015) & Kane et al. (2017), considering the nature of business and work processes within the traditional WMS firms. The amount of integration between inter-departments like the front, back and the middle office is disintegrated due to the silo's nature of working among these inter-departments in various processes, triggering administrative delays and inefficiencies in the onboarding process for prospective customers. The high penetration of technology has disrupted our personal and social life and is a major factor in influencing service-level expectations and change behaviours. Hence, due to these disruptive factors, the traditional firms constantly recalibrate their capabilities and service model to meet the speed of technologically disruptions without vertically diving in to explore their internal perspectives and readiness quotient.

A report from a joint study by MIT Sloan and Deloitte consulting (2015) clarifies that most organisations across the WMS sector don't have complete clarity over DT's impact holistically. The organisational maturity levels contribute to the excellent integration factor to leverage the value creation, while other firms struggle to calibrate their resources for transformation(Morakanyane et al., 2020).

In the current scenario of rapid technological growth, the nature and investment planning processes radically influenced more towards technological applications in reducing gaps in services. Customers' behaviour and expectations keep shifting due to the speedy availability of information over investments plannings and product offerings from competitors in the WMS industry. This behaviour compels the WMS firms to disrupt the legacy model to avoid further loyalty shifting of their customers. This change induction creates a ripple effect within the WMS sector, following path dependency models to evolve their processes by exploiting technology to simplify their legacy process for value creation.

The Cisco (2017) report about the DT in the Wealth management services sector reveals the growing focus on new talent demands, especially in the front office division of the Wealth services firms. The roles like advisors, relationship managers and wealth managers are undergoing the major digital shift to pull back the customer loyalty and interest towards traditional WMS firms. According to Cisco's report, the traditional wealth service sector will be entirely disrupted by 2021, 46% of companies will suffer from a lack of long-term vision over the critical areas, and 52% of investors are sensing the major competition by fintech companies over the traditional WMS sector. The practitioner Webb (2019) has highlighted that the major reason for fintech being considered by customers is lower transaction cost compared to traditional WMS firms. However, fintech firms are a new entrant into the financial sector but swiftly capturing the market share due to their specialization in providing niche services. The distinct factors like an agile process in providing niche and expert advice, in lower fees in comparison to traditional wealth service firms leveraging the AI-led, Robo technologies. These elements are successful in influencing the shifting behaviour and on customers' loyalties towards traditional WMS firms.

Thus, the following picture illustrates the current scenarios of compelling factors over the traditional WMS sector towards adopting digital transformation.

Figure 1: Author's illustration of compelling factors over the WMS firms.

Fintech firms follow the customer-centric approach model (Nicoletti et al.,2017; Gomber et al.,2018) by providing customers with an effective and efficient bundle of frictionless investment experiences. The AI-led Robo advisor, big data and machine learning technologies with open access to their clients to see and analyse their investment patterns and visibility over possible investment options, this customers' experience help in creating the value proposition. The fintechs firms have developed their digital capabilities by steadily investing in their people skills and technology, enhancing their service output ability by using disruptive technologies in routine service processes.

On the contrary, traditional WMS firms struggle to identify their capabilities and the right technology for their digital transformation. Due to various factors, these established firms juggle with the alignment and transparency issues within interdepartmental processes as departments have a silo culture of working. The lack of collaboration among back, middle and front offices results in delays in the onboarding process of customers.

Thus, with growing intense competition, the traditional firms exploring to identify their internal challenges and underlying complex issues impede the DT adaption process of transitioning, which remains unclear.

Innovations within customer services and work processes remain a vital focus in change practices of the WMS organisations, and these traditional firms are racing to adapt to the DT change to provide innovative services through the technologies. However, the challenge remains in aligning the processes and people involved to adopt the digital change. According to the researchers, IT (Information Technology) alignment is a significant part of the DT process due to its role in creating positive impacts on business performance (Gerow et al., 2014; Renaud et al., 2016). But there is not enough evidence about this claim specifically in context to the WMS sector, although the first impression from available literature highlights the imperative role of IT in a digital shift of businesses in the financial sector.

As per Coltman et al., (2015) and Fonstand & Subramani (2009) share similar outcomes, claiming that capability alignment is more challenging for the older organisations, as new firms can quickly respond to dynamic environmental changes undergoing strategic and operational change. In these scenarios, the traditional organisations adapt for the digitisation of their legacy processes and operational functions rather than adopting the complete digital transformation of the service model due to a lack of holistic clarity from the top-level management regarding DT is not just aligning IT strategy.

Instead, this research agrees with Galliers (2011) outcomes, as there is blurring the distinction between business and IT strategies, leading to a fusion between digital strategy & IT strategy. Hence these theories are directive gaps relevantly with the management approach towards the DT adaptation.

1.4: Overview of challenges for the Wealth Management Service firms

Since the inception of the industrial revolution in the eighteenth century, the Financial industry has been evolving in terms of services and process development, keeping their legacy advisory process entrenched along with digital evolution.

However, in the fourth industrial revolution, is the maturation of digital technologies has abundantly penetrated with high speed and radically changed the perspectives of society. Thus, the traditional WMS sector faces intense expectations from younger customers (Millennials to gen Z) over the agility of service delivery levels and high expectations of a flexible and transparent service model (Cisco, 2017). The current market size of potential customers (Prospective investors/ clients in WMS firms) is 2.2 million(UK Fact sheet: Wealth Management Association, 2020), which is the potential feature for WMS firms for constant attempts of digitalising their products and service offerings.

So far, there is potential fear among traditional WMS firms related to the complete digital transformation might not allow them to return to their legacy business model due to radical change involved in the process of the DT (Weilk & Lang, 2003). It is followed by cannibalization anxiety over the traditional business processes, a revenue-generating unit of these wealth service firms. Hence top management is unable to tackle the uncertainty involved in embracing the transformational approach.

The study conducted by McKinsey (2016) about *“How of transformation in an industry”* claims that seventy per cent of firms primarily fail in their DT initiatives due to management approach and lack of clarity at employee's end, leading to resistance and inertia towards change practices. The change transformation is a whirlpool change process(Moran & Brightman,2001) as there is no specific yardstick to measure the digital readiness of an organisation. However, researchers have contributed by developing various frameworks but critically, digital maturity or readiness built upon the approaches and perceptions of digital transformation within organisations. But this research argues that there cannot be a rigid framework for introducing the change framework for transformations as drivers and factors differ in every organisation. However, the key critical input towards DT is a unified understanding of this phenomenon for impactful change (Chanies & Hess,2016). Their research outcomes focus on collating the top-down and bottom-up strategising in forming a digital ecosystem within companies.

However, collation of bottom-up approach linked with the inside-culture of the organisation, in the overview of the WMS sector are family-managed or patriarchal culture hence there is less scope for bottom-up approach and employee inputs.

The human-technology link has emerged significantly critical in developing the strategic roadmap for successful DT navigation. Versteeg & Bouwman (2006) explain that it is a critical influencing factor the integration of the human element is significantly essential for the success of the digital transformational shift. As per the survey report on leaders from the financial industry(HBR, 2019), around 50% of top leaders agree that the money put forward for the digital transformation initiatives is draining out without any results, but it is not due to technology. However, lack of synergy between humans and technology is also the most significant element in the transformation process, which needs to integrate with DT vision by organisational leaders.

1.5: Problematizing the research issue and gap

Holistically, the existing literature from academic researchers and practitioners presents different perspectives on DT phenomena. The first impression of the literature review shows that available literature focused on either pre-digital preparedness of organisations or post-digital implementations strategy. According to practitioners and researchers(Casu et al., 2004; Henfridson & Lind, 2014; Kohnke et al., 2016; Chanias, 2017), the imperative factor within traditional organisations is technology, for their transitioning focuses on revenue generation and the value proposition. At the same time, the practitioners from the WMS industry contends that constant change innovations and speedy developments in technology space are compelling reasons for traditional wealth service organisations to adopt the digital ways to sustain and meet customer expectations (Mckinsey, 2016; Cocca, 2016; Oliver Wyman, 2020). Hence to summarize the technology advancement is an imperative factor and trigger point for change initiation in the WMS sector.

Despite constant research on the WMS sector by business consulting companies and fewer studies from academic scholars, there is still a gap in agreement on the unified view about the DT phenomenon. As found by this research, that every available literature is a contributing factor in the process of unpacking the digital phenomenon layers(Chanas, 2017; Nambian et al., 2019; Vial, 2019; Vaska et al., 2021; Kohnke et al., 2016; Henfridson & Lind, 2014), but due to its dynamic attributes of DT change, the adaptation strategy must be tailor-fit to the organisation for a successful embracing of digital transformation.

The concept of DT is not very new in industry 4.0, introduced in the early year 2000(Patel & McCarthy, 2000), wherein it got antecedents in the era of digitisation, digitalisation in the era of 1950s, the conversion of analogue format to digital variant(Verhof, 2021; Kohnke et al., 2016; Brennen & Kreiss, 2016). The Digital Transformation in the 4th industrial revolution is distinct from the 3rd Industrial revolution, making it distinct in its speed, scalability and social impact levels over business models. According to SAP's Business insight report, 84% of global companies have DT in their top agenda for the next five years for business sustainability (SAP Study Reveals Four Key Traits of a Digital Transformation Leader, 2017).

The available literature highlights that the driving elements and influencing variables for the DT change have to be specific and distinctive to every firm, sector and industry. However, there is largely agreement within the research and practitioner community over a few variables like organisational maturity, culture and leadership management (Kotter, 2012; Matt, Hess & Benlian,2015; Fitzgerald et al.,2017; Kane, 2017; Osmundsen,2018). Noticeably, the impact level of these factors might vary depending on the nature of the business. Hence, due to the lack of relevant evidence pertaining to the research case study sector, these factors cannot be generalized to the WMS firms, as it is linked with what level of digital transformation goal that firms intend to transform. Thus, this research study is significant in elevating the knowledge about the underlying complexities of the traditional WMS sector in the digital change phenomenon.

The WMS sector remains under-researched in light of the digital transformation and exploring its driving factors in the context, considering the dynamic and regulatory controlled markets that this sector operates within. Thus, this research explores the relationship extent by unpacking the mystery puzzle of capability and technology factors in digital navigation by traditional WMS firms.

From practitioners' viewpoint, the literature provides the flip-side view of scenarios within the WMS sector struggling in embracing the DT into the legacy culture. According to a Forbes magazine report by Gale(2019), only 28 % of organisations are flourishing by embracing Digital Transformation in the financial industry. According to Brown & Eisenhardt (1997, p.3), "the ability to change continuously is a core capability of successful firms". However, reports from the Forbes editorial(2019) on the WMS sector reveal that around 70% of WMS firms are unsure about their capabilities to embrace the DT(Morgan,2019). Holistically, the knowledge body over DT has been building up, but it is still fragmented in breaking the puzzle for the successful embrace of DT change.

Another perspective from a set of researchers recommends the various frameworks with the possibility of successful digital jump resulting in business sustainability and competitive advantage(Chaniyas et al.,2019; Verhoef et al., 2021; Kossowski et al., 2020; Kohli & Melville, 2018). However, due to the traditional mindset of the WMS firms within this business sector, possibilities are fragile as anxiety of losing the revenues from legacy business models and inability to return holds to adapt these frameworks successfully. While there is another perception specific to European financial services firms stated in research by Casu et al. (2004), the productivity factor impacted by the unprecedented velocity of technology developments in traditional companies, the frequent operational changes entailing due to organisational culture of inducting the agile technologies affects the organisational culture, processes and structures.

1.5.1: Research Gap

The review of literature primarily highlights diverse perspectives about exploring the DT phenomena in the research context. The point of view from the academic literature is compartmentalized either pre or post-digital effects and implementation strategy. Thus, including academia and practitioners' perspectives, two major approaches are sighted in review from an interpretation of relevant literature on DT strategy.

- Firstly, the technology as the primary change element and then focussing on integrating the existing processes, capabilities and resources towards chosen technology.
- Secondly, the few organisations emphasise building their digital maturity internally and adopting relevant and efficient technology to improve existing processes and revenue models.

Thus, to some extent, the existing literature successfully creates foundational insight about digital transformation and narrows it from general to specific. There is inadequate literature over the factorial relevance to the traditional WMS sector, as this financial sector is under-researched in academia. Hence, it indicates an opportunity to contribute to the growing literature about inside-out perspectives of the DT complexities in the WMS sector. Due to the abundance of literature available in the context of DT, it is necessary to restrict the exploration in the direction of research objectives; hence the "*GINC perspective*" framework was developed to keep up in the direction in research exploration based on identified research gap. It is essential to set a framework to accurately set the research questions, aim, and objectives for further research.

The significance of the "*GINC Perspective*" framework is components that explore the perspective based exploration of research. The *GINC* perspective is an abbreviation of **Gap, Issues, Needs** and **Capabilities**, and these components are significant in meeting the aims of the research. The following diagram illustrates the research gap identified and the research.

Figure 2: Research gap

1.5.2: Research Questions

Following are the main research questions designed based on identified gaps in the literature.

- Q 1: What is the extent and impact of the Digital transformation in the Wealth Management Services sector?
- Q 2: What are the constraints and challenges in embracing the DT in a traditional WMS environment?
- Q 3: What are the critical success factors (CSFs) for digital change transitions?
- Q 4: What are the strategic capabilities essential for the successful DT change?

1.5.3: Research Aims & Objectives

This research explores the extent and impact of Digital Transformation in the Wealth Management services sector in the London region.

Following are the objectives of the research set in order to achieve the aim of the research.

- A. *Examining the current and relevant literature in relation to explore the Digital Transformational phenomenon and its impact on the chosen the WMS sector*
- B. *Investigating the relationship and significance of critical success factors for the successful embracing of Digital Transformation.*
- C. *Defining the perspectives on challenges and constraints in relation to chosen WMS sector's digital transitioning.*
- D. *Discussing and sharing the key findings outlining the theoretical and practical implications of the research and offering directives for future research.*

1.6: Significance of the research

The significance of this research is two-fold. Firstly, the research contributes to the body of Knowledge as the WMS sector is under-researched in academic literature. With an aim to explore the DT phenomenon, the research will be the first of its kind to provide a comprehensive inside-out picture of the WMS industry and the underlying complexities of DT transitioning from legacy to digitally transformed state. This research clarifies fundamental constraints and challenges in transitioning traditional business irrespective of these organisations' capability and resource availability.

According to the current scenario of the WMS sector, there is obscure information over the disorientation of traditional firms from their objectives to transform their business model by realigning & reinventing their capabilities and processes. According to the literature, there is a lack of unified understanding of DT phenomena, and precisely unclarity over the differences between digitisation, digitalisation and digital transformation phases as it is frequently

interchanged in business practices. The available literature leaves a fine line of differentiation between these phases, leaving the gap to explore the impact of each phase in the transformation journey within the organisations. This research will provide conceptual clarity to the reader, highlighting the DT phenomenon's underlying understanding among critical stakeholders and policymakers and the significance of unified knowledge about each DT phase for the formation of DT strategy.

The research aims to exhume the reasons for failures by traditional WMS firms in embracing and adapting the DT, will evaluate the factors for creating the fluidic environment easy to accept and embrace the digital change by exploring the subsequent perceptions of key stakeholders. The research study intends to recommend a framework by captivating the outcomes of research data analysis and providing stage-wise conduct of DT adaption by traditional WMS firms.

1.6.1: Research rationale

Table 1: Research rationale

Research questions	The rationale to research questions
<p>Q 1. What is the extent and impact of DT in the Wealth Management Services sector?</p>	<p>To evaluate the extent of the DT phenomenon, and the following significant factors need to examine.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Understanding the definitions of the DT phenomenon from academic researchers and practitioners' lenses. b. Evaluating the extent of literature on Digital transitioning on Wealth management services. c. Reviewing the relevance and impact of technology over legacy roles and processes. d. Seeking to understand the attributes through the lenses of the TAM framework. e. Evaluating through TAM components to comprehend the gaps existing in understanding at various strategic levels within organisations. f. This research question focussed on identifying the <i>GAP</i> component of the <i>GINC</i> framework.
<p>Q 2. What are the constraints and challenges in embracing the DT in a traditional WMS business environment?</p>	<p>Reviewing the core elements obstructing the adaption of the DT.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Identifying the nature of constraining factors and reasons and challenges in focus to the WMS firms. b. How and why the identified factors are impactful in the process of digital change, evaluation of the relationship with external and internal elements. c. What are the sustainability aspects for the WMS firms. d. This section caters to the <i>ISSUE</i> component of the <i>GINC</i> framework.

<p>Q 3. What are the critical success factors (CSFs) for digital change transitions?</p>	<p>Review the extent of literature on CSFs factors in transitioning the legacy to a digital mindset.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Essential to evaluate the holistic the approach of traditional mindset towards digital adaption process. b. Defining the capability aspect in understanding CSFs for digital transitioning. c. To evaluate the supporting factors for causation of success and failures in DT adaption. d. This question caters to the NEED aspect of the <i>GINC</i> framework.
<p>Q.4. What are the strategic capabilities essential for the successful DT change?</p>	<p>Evaluating the capability aspect in strategic planning of DT change.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Based on identifying foundational elements by adopting interpretivism paradigm adopted for gathering the empirical data with participants from WMS firms to understand their perspectives over the extent of DT. b. Identifying the linkage and relationship between the strategic capability. c. Exploring and bringing clarity on the strategic capabilities at a critical hierarchy involved in executing DT strategy. d. Recommendation of the framework for practical implementation based on the research findings.

1.7: Research Methodology

The research is exploratory and qualitative in nature. A qualitative research methodology is adopted. The research study aims to investigate the extent and impact of the DT in the WMS sector. The research adopted the interpretivism paradigm and a phenomenological approach in conducting the semi-structured interviews for empirical data collection.

The research emphasised sampling from the WMS industry; the sample size selected for empirical data collection are various executives associated with the WMS industry with relevant experience, background, roles, responsibilities and involvement in DT strategy and planning. Hence stakeholder analysis was conducted to potentialize the stakeholders' participation. The four stakeholders groups identified for research interviews hold various roles and responsibilities in the WMS sector and are engaged in the DT process. The stakeholders are senior management in roles of CEO, CDO and managing partners. The middle management participants are the wealth manager, advisor and relationship manager, external DT consultants from consulting firms associated with WMS firms in implementing and strategizing the DT shift and lastly, the customer/ clients using wealth services companies for their financial investment planning. The focus of the research is to explore answers through lived experiences of the stakeholders on set questions based on the underlined *G/INC* perspective framework.

The Interpretivism paradigm is adopted as a research philosophy to understand the individual's perceptions on the concept of digital transformation phenomena and viewpoints associated with digital embracing and implementation aspects. As identified participants are part of these ongoing transformational changes practices within organisations, qualitative methods of semi-structured interviews are adopted to maximise their outlook and observations and are critical to understanding the existing reality within the industry. The adopted research methodology is commonly practised for interpretive and exploratory research by researchers from diverse IS management fields (Kane, 2017; Chanas et al., 2019;

Mergel et al., 2019; Kossowski et al., 2020). This qualitative research employed the thematic analysis technique for the analysis of empirical data collection.

1.8 Structure of the thesis

The structure of the research is divided into three main stages. **Stage one** provides the introduction and background of the research theme and reasons for choosing the Wealth Management service sector as a case study. This research stage explores and evaluates the literature and its relevance to this research study, considering the relevant literature from academia and practitioners perspectives to identify the gaps and develop into research questions, aims, and objectives. The research will review the literature in the context of DT, from general to specific, to construct the conceptual framework for further research based on the identified research gap. **Stage two** is a significant phase of the research study; further to the developed conceptual framework, chapter 3 provides a brief outlook on research methodology to explore the research aims and objectives. The detailed explanation and justifications are provided in stage two, clarifying research participants participating in semi-structured interviews for the empirical data collection process. **Stage three** is the novel contribution in synthesizing the outcomes of the findings and channelising the themes into recommended contributions and limitations of the research study. The below sections provides a brief outline of six chapters of this research.

Chapter 1: This chapter sets the stage for the research by introducing the conceptual understanding of the digital transformation phenomena and provides a background and relevance of this study to case study the WMS sector. The chapter reviews the literature to explore the perceptions of the DT in traditional industry and challenges encountered in the process. The lack of clarity and unavailability of accurate information on research context in the WMS sector led to adopt the problematization approach to set the precise area of issues for research to investigate. The research formulates the research questions, aims and objectives and rationale for research questions.

Chapter 2: This research section evaluates the understanding through provided definitions of the DT from transdisciplinary researchers. The variances in the perceptions and approach presented towards DT phenomena identifies the literature gap. This chapter conducts a brief literature review in context to the DT theme. It concludes with developing the conceptual framework by integrating the foundation elements from the TAM model & Dynamic capability framework, the right components to find the answers for formulated research questions.

Chapter 3: This chapter presents the research methodology and design adopted for the further research study. It explains and justifies the philosophical stance of the research, briefing the research epistemologies, ontology and axiology of research. The chapter is linked with a conceptual framework to adopt the interpretivism and inductive methods for conducting interviews. The research explained the significance of stakeholder analysis in selecting the stakeholders for this research study. The last part of the chapter provides a brief understanding of data collection tools, and ethical considerations followed for this research.

Chapter 4: This research section provides a brief narration of sub-themes and themes from each participated group in the research. The thematic analysis of data gathered all four groups presented in diagrammatic format with yielded sub-themes and themes. The chapter explains the process, how the data is thematically analysed and extracted from transcripts to themes. It outlines essential and relevant quotes from research participants and explains quotes to the research outcome. In total, the research conducted semi-structured interviews with twenty-three participants, including executives associated with the WMS industry internally and externally.

Chapter 5: This research section is most significant to research as it discusses the outcomes of research findings and its relevance to research questions to verify if research questions are answered. It discusses the group-wise results from data analysis briefly and contributes to gaps identified based on research outcomes. The chapter provided relevance to identifying dynamic capabilities at participated executives roles and recommended the framework for practical contribution.

Chapter 6: Chapter six is the concluding part of the research; this section revisits the research aim and objectives, connecting back with the literature review chapter. It provides an outline of outcomes, literature's contribution, and discussion briefly the limitations and implications of research findings towards the practical implementations. This section of the research reflects on limitations and learnings during the research journey.

1.9: Summary

The Introduction chapter provided an overview of the research background, rationale and motivation for commencing the research in the Wealth Management services sector as a case study sector for the research study. This chapter presented the overview of the chosen financial sector and the existing scenario on digital transformation initiatives. The overview of the literature indicated the lack of unified understanding of DT phenomena. Due to inadequate information and vision integration from expected DT change, stakeholders perceive a general understanding of digital change linked with their role, function and responsibilities in organisations. Hence there are variations in perception about the DT phenomenon.

The research adopted the problematization approach to identify the precise issues and complexities for research to investigate. Based on an initial review of relevant literature in the context of the DT phenomena in the WMS sector scenario, there are inadequate research outcomes, and directives specific to chosen case study sector, hence the brief review of literature from academics and practitioners in the field of the digital transformation is conducted in next chapter.

Based on identified gaps in the initial review, the research questions, aims and objectives are formulated for further research. Thus, this research explores the extent and impact of Digital Transformation in the WMS sector and ventures to understand the underlying perspectives from various stakeholders about this phenomenon. The research outcomes will yield the IS literature in a specific context by synthesising lived experiences and perceptions of executives from various levels associated with the WMS sector. The practical and theoretical contributions illustrated will be expanded further in the remaining chapters.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2. Introduction

Chapter one provided the background of the research theme and outlined the literature gap, providing the rationale for formulated research questions, aims and objectives for the research study. Chapter two, the literature review, presents an overview of DT phenomena in the traditional WMS sector, which operates within a dynamic ecosystem of the financial services industry. Despite substantial investments and digital expertise in support, traditional firms fail to adapt to the digital transformation. The literature focuses primarily on pre or post-digital strategy, leaving no clue about the reasons for failures in the given context of the sector, as there are fewer studies conducted on the WMS sector from a theoretical point of view. Thus, it leaves a gap to determine the scope of understanding the perspectives about the DT phenomenon. This chapter will critically view the relevant literature in the context of DT to comprehend the factors that derail traditional WMS firms' attempts to embrace digital transformation. The critical construct factors discussed will support in developing the conceptual framework for the further conduct of research.

Chapter two structure is as follows: Section 2.1 and 2.2 provides a brief overview of the DT phenomenon, understanding the various perspectives from diverse researchers and evaluating the available literature reflections in context to the case study. Section 2.4 and 2.5 provide the overview of DT's phases, theoretical aspects in relation to the DT adaption and implementation, and evaluating the literature highlighted factors in context with the WMS environment. The literature review in section 2.6 reviews the fintech invasion and challenges raising the competitive pressure over traditional WMS firms and discusses the relationship of identified factors. Section 2.7 and 2.8 discusses the theoretical research gap and extractions from theories for the conceptual framework of research.

The conceptual framework is developed for further research by combining the perception-based frameworks TAM model and Dynamic Capability framework. Lastly, sections 2.9 and 2.10 discuss the conceptual framework of research and its significance in meeting the research aim, and section 2.10 summarises the chapter.

2.1: Definition of the Digital Transformation (DT)

The surge of technological advancements is highly influencing and mounting the pressure over the traditional organisations, predominantly on the leaders in top management and key executive positions holders involved in strategizing the change movement and adaption of the DT. The new business processes led by disruptive technology shorten the gap between business value creation and scalability by meeting rising expectations with efficient services. This is possible to achieve the desired state if the WMS firms elevate the DT perspectives across the organisation by inventing ways to create a new value proposition by configuring the capabilities reinforced by disruptive technology.

The flipside of the DT phenomenon in the traditional WMS sector requires a new set of capabilities to composite evolved processes, practices, and talent to create a novel business model. Moran & Brightman (2001) have defined any change movement as a process of constant renewal of an organisation's structure and capabilities to meet changing needs of internal and external customers. The WMS business firms quandary on parting the legacy processes by adapting the agile methodology and innovative practices. The issues creeping between departing the old methods and embracing agile practices are critical sets of challenges. According to an HBR report (Digital Transformation Is Not About Technology, 2019), in the FSI sector, 70% of organisations fail to achieve their set DT objectives and goals due to failure in integrating the required capabilities with a purpose (Tabrizi et al.,2019).

The interruptions in legacy processes caused by disruptive technologies induce changes impacting all organisational hierarchies, breaking the status-quo within the WMS sector. The significant reasons for delaying the DT in traditional firms are inadequate knowledge, skills,

and capabilities at the top management level, impacting DT adaption. According to Alvesson et al.,(2008), as technology changes the world progressively, organisations must change quickly for development and survival reasons. The transdisciplinary view on DT enables a holistic approach to the DT phenomenon from various angles. This leads to the search for relevant literature on DT from leading databases with the theme of "Digital Transformation" directed scholarly contributions beyond any specific discipline approaches. Hence, the transdisciplinary review by scholars from various fields of medicines, manufacturing, engineering and media provides an understanding of how scholars and practitioners from varied disciplines perceive the DT phenomenon.

Table 2: Transdisciplinary view on Digital Transformation

Author	Sector	Different approaches
Herrmann et al. (2018)	Medical sector	Comprehensive reorientation of the business models disrupted by technological advancements.
Agarwal et al. (2010)	Medical sector	Digital transformation defines the outline of making the health care system holistically accessible, safe, and affordable.
Kossowski et al. (2020)	Engineering sector	Digital transformation is an organisational transformation in the era of digitalisation.
Valdez-de-Leon (2016)	Telecom sector	Digital transformations go deep into every aspect of the businesses and operating models of communications service providers
Colli et al. (2018)	Manufacturing	Increased number of new possibilities in the enhancement of product, process, and services model.
Canetta et al. (2018)	Manufacturing	The consequences of digitalisation in shaping a new working environment are analysed, focusing on workforce impact.
Hess (2016)	Media Industry	Frequent transformations of critical business operations affect the products, processes, structures, and concepts.

The evaluation of definitions by transdisciplinary scholars' in the above table illustrates the varied perspectives about DT phenomena. These insights by transdisciplinary scholars highlight the role of other elements in the adaption of DT at an organisational level. Holistically, by adaption of DT in any business will change the vision and goals to potentialize through technology for achieving the set goals. Hence, the research aims to supplement with deep insights on the extent of DT for business practitioners and policymakers to facilitate the understand DT phenomenon in a granular and inside-out view, as technology-led disruptions are impacting society significantly in every approach. Every organisation strategizes the change models by evolving the various processes, people, and products, but not necessarily every traditional firm is proactive rather than reactive to massive complex change phenomena. The present literature focused on the technology element, its imperative role in digital navigation. The elements like stakeholder perceptions towards change adaption and how product and processes change impact customer loyalty are in the perimeter of available literature but not in focus.

Although there has been a steep increase in research interest on the DT phenomenon from a couple of decades from academic and non-academic researchers, a review of existing literature leaves the reader in the state within a jigsaw puzzle. As every puzzle piece is important but unclear about puzzle piece integrations. This is a metaphor for the present status of available literature in the present context of the digital transformation.

2.2: Reflections on literature: Digital Transformation

The change management process is an ever-present feature of a business organisation to identify and develop the ability required for the future course of action at operational and strategic levels (Burnes,2004). The DT change transition aims to improve an entity by triggering, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies (Vial,2019). The adaptation of DT cannot be isolated only to certain levels within the organisation, as it is an interlinked effort to achieve the set objective together from digital change. However, despite the rise in research interest from diverse management scholars, there is still scope

to contribute to the business practices and knowledge body by exploring the underlying perceptions of digital transformation change and associated capability factors.

As per the Deloitte survey report(2019), the Financial Services industry(FSI) in the UK confirms that nearly 90% of firms are attempting to be digital champions. However, only 28% of financial organisations are flourishing pragmatically by embracing the right approach. At the same time, many other financial firms are unsure of having the right set of capabilities for massive transformational navigation (Forbes,2019). According to the leading author in change management, Kotter (2012) has stated in the book "XLR8 (Accelerate)" that most of the digital projects have failed not because of challenges but due to human element issues. Thus, there are significant indications towards variables associated with the human element involved in the DT adaption process. The growing evidence of literature from academics and practitioners indicates that organisations are attempting to adapt the DT but lacking in integrating the vision with the right set of capability puzzles. According to Oliver Wyman report (2020), most CFO's of Financial firms have a similar opinion that 50% of their digital spending are getting wasted, and they cannot identify the key factors contributing to ongoing investment wastage.

In the current scenario, there is a critical need to explore the deeper reasons that delay traditional companies' adoption process of digital change despite available resources and capabilities. Thus, it calls for a critical review of literature in assessing theories and views associated with the context of digital transformation. Academic researchers and practitioners (Gray & Rampe 2017; Matt, 2015, Verhoef et al., 2021; Vial, 2019; Warner & Wager, 2018; Sebastian et al. 2017; Kane et al. 2016; Majchrzak et al. 2016; Parviainen et al., 2017), has contributed to the literature by creating some visibility and understanding on aspects in the periphery of digital transformation phenomenon. So fundamentally, two approaches are being formed from the analysis of recent literature: *Firstly*, "Technology being the centre argument of strategy and organisations align themselves towards it" (Fichman et al., 2014; Hess et al.,2016; Vial,2019; Collin et al., 2015). *Secondly*, organisations focus on specific dynamic capabilities and then adapt to the right technology to meet the digital aim(Morakanyane et al., 2017; Aldrich & Ruef, 2006; Vial, 2019; Liu et al., 2011).

Thus, however, it is evident that technology and capabilities are the most critical variables of the DT shift. Hence mind mapping is developed further with these identified variables (Appx p. 252)

According to Finchman et al.,(2014) & Hess et al.,(2016), claims that DT as IT (information technology) enables change by digitalising products, services, and customer touchpoints. Singh & Hess (2017) argue that DT is a comprehensive process of organisations' actions to build strategy beyond functional thinking and risk assessment from digital technology. At the same time, Warner & Wager (2018) supports by stating the DT as an ongoing strategic renewal process that uses advanced digital technologies to build capabilities that replace an organisation's business model, collaborative approach, and culture. Holistically, the DT constantly shifts the organisational focus from the existing state to the expected state (Kossowski et al.,2020). However, the existing definitions of digital transformation focused on the imperativeness of technology in the movement to achieve the expected state of transformation.

These definitions of DT emphasise that technology is imperative in rebuilding or configuring newer capabilities, focusing on technology as an important factor but according to practitioners within the industry has a different outlook on this phenomenon. According to secondary statistics, HBR (2019) reports reveal that \$1.3 trillion was spent on disruptive technology for digital transformation, around \$900 billion wasted without meeting the set objectives. A significant amount of research is being conducted on digital transformation by varied scholars from every industry, like academicians, practitioners, consulting leaders, and government authorities.

The table presents the summary of definitions by academicians and practitioners and the focus highlighted from their definitions.

Table 3: Attributes defined within the Digital Transformation Phenomenon

Author	Definition	Reflection of DT definitions
Fitzgerald et al. (2004)	Use of technology to bring improvements in business	The central focus on technology
Liu et al. (2011)	The organisational transformation that integrates with technology with process	The central focus on technology
Singh & Hess (2017)	Company-wide transformation of existing state due technology	The central focus on technology
Westerman et al. (2014b)	The use of technology to radically improve the performance of enterprises	Radical change inclusive of technology
Warner & Wager, (2018)	The ongoing process of renewal to build capabilities for newer business model	Development of capability
Bharadwaj et.al, (2013)	Digital strategy formation by leveraging digital resources for value creation	importance of strategy in the process of value creation
Morakanyane et al. (2017)	Evolutionary process by leveraging capabilities and technologies to create value	Transformation as an evolutionary process
Chanas & Hess (2016)	The scale of changes induced by technology throughout an organisation	The central focus on technology
OECD (2018g)	Digital Transformation refers to digitisation and digitalisation and their effects on the economy and society	Significance of Transformation over economy & society
Accenture (2019)	The transformation of activities , processes, and competencies to fully leverage the benefits of digital technologies and their accelerating impact across present and future business	Significance of Transformation over existing and future business stages
Deloitte (2018)	The use of technology to radically transforms the processes, more engaged talent , and business model	Transformation as an evolutionary process

Summary of above-stated definitions from key contributors in the field of digital transformation phenomenon comprehends the scale of transformations within a radius of disruptive technology adaption. Holistically the understanding of DT extracted from these definitions explicitly shows inadequate focus over the human link and correct perceptions in the entire DT process. According to approaches from the above-stated definitions, a significant focus integrated with three processes attempted to present in a diagrammatic format below. There is a lack of a focussed approach about human perspective and involvement in the digital transformation process. As per leading industry advisor, Nucoro's report (Further challenges of Wealth Management, 2020) estimated that 84% per cent of organisations fail to set their vision clear across all levels, mismatch of strategic leadership in aligning the vision's capabilities and resource integration.

Figure 3: Central focus of current Digital Transformation (Author's development).

The human-technology link emerges as the most sought integration required for successful digital transformation adaption. Versteeg & Bouwman (2006) emphasised this integration as a critical influencing factor for transformational impact from the change process in agreement with the above revelations.

Additionally, Deloitte (2018) defines DT as evolutionary necessary for human talent and engagement; hence the human perspective is vastly underestimated. However, some scholars and industry bodies have emphasised the importance of the human element and their perspectives in DT changes, which is crucial for the successful adaptation of transformational changes (Schwertner, 2017; Kohnke, 2017; OECD; Deloitte, 2018).

Researchers have a highly unsettled opinion about perennial issues on prioritising technology adoption and capabilities configuration or vice versa in line with the DT scenario. Based on a literature review, apart from the technology point of view, there is an underlying lack of clarity on factors critically evaluated for forming the digital strategy by top management within firms to view the extent of DT. The variables like culture, leadership, organisational mindset and size and organisational habits are the most critical contributing factors in developing the foreground for adapting the digital transformation (Fitzgerald 2014; Earley, 2014; Kahneman, 2011; Kane et al., 2015; Kohnke, 2016). Hence, it is pivotal to explore the literature in context to these underlying attributes for digital transformation readiness, but due to insufficient research literature specific to the WMS sector, the practitioners' outlook on the research context is needed.

This research will explore the industry perspectives towards adapting the DT and characteristics that drive the digital change phenomenon.

2.3: Research Context: The Wealth Management Services Sector

According to the research outcomes by leading industry consultants, Oliver Wyman (2020), focused on traditional WMS firms, symbolises the current most significant challenge of shaping the digital business for tomorrow from yesterday legacy. Most big traditional firms still depend on the old business model to generate revenue for digital transformational change. The DT is a company-wide transformation in length and breadth, not just technology transformation (Matt et al., 2015). Thus, as discussed above, organisational culture, structure, process, and capability are crucial elements in DT change and specific to the business

and industry in digital change. Hence, it is necessary to understand the WMS sector, why they want to transform, and how they adapt to disruptive technology caused changes.

2.3.1: What is Wealth Management Services (WMS)?

The earliest information tracked about the "Wealth Management" connects as early as 1933 (Fowler, 1933), this term earlier was interchangeably used with money management or asset management, the range of services in the form of investment, tax and financial advice extended as concierge banking and investment services to only wealthy customers supervised by asset managers (Traff, 2016).

This advisory services industry was popularized in the 1970s when top companies like Goldman Sachs and Morgan Stanley started providing enhanced and exclusive services to wealthier customers to distinguish the wealthier clients from mass-market customers (Traff, 2016).

The exclusive advisory services within the WMS industry are major revenue generation unit in this business that combines other allied investment services to address the wealthy customers' investment requirements accordingly. It is a consultative process whereby the advisor/ relationship/ wealth managers create a portfolio by understanding the customers' background, preferences, risky capacity and investment scalability for documenting a personalised investment strategy about investment and returns utilising appropriate financial tools and products (Investopedia, 2019).

The closest and most apparent reason to adopt the massive digital change is to satisfy the customer demands, wherein every business vertical within the Financial industry is attempting to establish its competitive advantage by providing the expected customer experience. However, specific to the WMS sector, one of the significant challenges is tighter regulatory restrictions that clamp the accelerating pace of digital change adoption.

Compared with other FS industry segments, banks and insurance verticals have greater flexibility to embrace advanced technologies like AI (Artificial intelligence), cloud computing, blockchain in customer services and product innovation development.

Understanding the FS industry structure and segments is critically necessary to know the modularity impact in technological shift (Henfridsson, 2014). The FS industry is driven by a flood of disruptive technologies, enforcing the organisations to adopt the DT by transforming their business, changing the product and service scale for creating the value proposition and more customer engagement but currently abided within the framework of regulation, data security, margin revenue, customer engagement & trust and customer wellbeing.

Figure 4: Overview of the Financial Service Industry

Relationship management is one of the critical elements of the Wealth Management industry (Hallmann & Rosenbloom, 2009; Cocca,2016). In the constant attempts by traditional organisations to fuel the trust factor, various elements influence customer expectations that influence the adoption of disruptive technology to meet their service expectations. A synthesis of available literature indicates an understanding of DT, linked with varied drivers and attributes specific to an industry where business firms are operating within.

As per the industry reports, the involvement of leadership in devising the digital strategy beforehand of adopting the technology is a crucial factor in business (Bharadwaj et al., 2013) for integration of value optimisation from DT. Approximately 70% of the Financial companies have not achieved their set digital goals (Harvard Business Review, 2019), which enforces to re-evaluate the current understanding of the Digital transformation phenomenon among the stakeholder involved in the process of devising the DT strategy, to explore the reasons of the gap in achieving the organisation digital goals.

2.4: The phases of the Digital Transformation

The phases like digitisation and digitalization are inter-exchanged within business practices under the DT umbrella. However, the significance of each DT phase is linked with the organisations' strategy for DT shift. Hess et al.,(2016. p.7) claim that "strategies that embrace the implications of digital transformation and drive better operational performance." In agreement with Hess et al.,(2016) research outcomes, the lack of understanding about each phase's significance hinders the overall embracing of the digital shift. Valdez-de-leon et al., (2016) emphasise that DT vision is communicated across the organisation, it helps to propellant in designing the customized approach towards the desired service model.

Earley (2014) focuses on bringing the change in deeply entrenched organisational habits. At the same time, the researchers Parviainen et al.,(2017)and Hughes,(2016) emphasised that the digitalisation of legacy processes can enhance internal efficiency and a significant reason for the change in customer expectations. The organisation transition from its status quo is possible by leveraging disruptive technology (Sebastian et al., 2017). The researchers Stolterman & Fors (2004) refers DT, also known as digitalisation or digital disruptions, to a business model driven by "the changes associated with the application of digital technology in all aspects of human society" (p. 689).

The "digitisation", "digitalisation", and "digital transformation" these phrases are overused in practices for any transformation-related change. KPMG (2019) quoted that getting the digital right states that confusion lies in lack of clarity, communication, and leadership management skills (Weir & Smith, 2019). Unless there is absolute clarity on DT strategy at all required levels in the organisation internally and externally will lead to wastage of investment and failure to achieve digital goals.

Continuing with arguments and views presented over significance on clarity of phases of DT, it is unclear whether organisations consider these concepts of digitisation and digitalization as part of large scale DT change or it is assumed if these phases are the DT. Holistically, the DT encompasses various phases, "Digitisation, Digitalization and Digital Transformation", but these three stages have different significance in DT implementation within complex change mechanisms. There is inadequate clarity over the significance of these phases in the DT implementation. Following is the conceptual understanding of these phases of the DT.

Digitisation: Converting information from analogue format into digital format (Yoo et al.,2010; Li et al.,2016; Sebastian, 2017; Parviainen et al., 2017). Back-end administrative and paperwork conversion into the digitalised format in the chosen service sector includes applications, financial declarations, administration purpose data collection, surveys(Verhoef et al., 2021).

Digitalisation: This stage of digitalisation is value creation stage wherein, organisations pensively strategises the adoption of disruptive technologies to bring changes in existing process and services, it is an enabler to seize new services possible in a shift in existing business processes (Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2016). Often, the digital transformation efforts require internal and external integration in dealing better with core changes at an organisational level, which requires end-to-end efficiency and agile changes. Such agility is an ongoing digitalisation initiative often confused in Digital transformation(Bloomberg, 2018).

The following diagram below illustrates the significance of three separate phases towards embracing the DT, but often these processes are not clearly understood within the organisational ecosystem.

Figure 5: Impression of phases under Digital Transformation Phenomenon in literature (Author's development).

To summarize, the impression of DT phases through available literature indicates the relationship is interlinked. However, due to inadequate knowledge of digital transformation scope the scalability within business practices, the processes change for digitisation and digitalization is understood as DT shift which is just part of large-scale DT change.

In connection to the above discussion over phases of the DT, the researcher Arner et al., (2016) exhibited the phases of technological disruptions that evolved specifically to the Financial industry globally. Due to constant technology disruptions, there is still an underlying gap in understanding the difference between digitisation and digitalization implementation and its significance to the work process. Hence connecting back to literature, as discussed

earlier, there were two major approaches expanded in literature is about pre and post-digital settings with little clarity on the significance of phases of the DT.

Figure 6: Evolution of change transformation in the service industry (Source: Arner et al.,2016).

The large scale of DT & transitions of processes in the traditional WMS sector is challenging and overwhelming. Specifically, the advisory process with human elements involved wherein it connects with trust and relationship factors while dealing with all segments of customers. Currently, the core challenge in front of WMS firms is the influence of disruptive technologies as major propellers in rapid changes in customers behaviour and expectation in services demand. With more younger generations (gen Y, Z & Alpha) approaching investment planning and building up their investment portfolio, demand for transparency, flexibility, and agile services is rising pressure on traditional WMS firms. Another critical challenge of resistance from internal employees in adapting to newer digital ways is the lack of clear communication and transparency in sharing the DT strategy, which leads to inertia. Hence traditional firms often have conflicts and barriers in implementing Digital Transformations (Christensen et al., 2016).

2.5: The critical aspects of Digital Transformation

The reflection of available literature in transformational change presents the idiosyncratic factors for adapting the DT, which connects with organisational attributes like leadership and culture elements. (Haffke et al.,2016; Ebert and Duarte., 2016; Kane,2017; Kossowski et al., 2020). Hence, it is necessary to explore the related aspects of DT adaption with the aforementioned attributes to develop the successful foundational foreground in the digital culture shift within organisations. Hamel and Prahalad(1994) also described that organisations need to transform themselves before transforming others, emphasising internal elements before adapting the complete DT transitions

2.5.1: Leadership and Culture

According to Oberer & Erkollar (2018), Digital leadership is cross hierarchical, team-focused, agile and innovation-oriented. In connection to the research context, a vital aspect of a leadership element in creating a vision clarity on the currently existing state to the expected state of DT. Firstly, the crucial element is to have a unified understanding of the digital transformation phenomenon and secondly, the topmost priority of the traditional organisation is to have an exemplary leadership steering the DT planning. However, according to Nucoro's report (Further challenges of Wealth Management, 2020), leading industry advisors revealed that 84% per cent of firms fail in achieving the DT goals due to a lack of strategic leadership skills, vision and value integration and capability rearrangement.

The strategic directives towards DT require the top-management involvement with the consensus of all stakeholders in adapting and implementing DT processes (Yokoi et al., 2009; Porfirio et al.,2021). The leaders characterise the scope of structuring the process in strategising the company mission, vision and efficacy of the implementation process. Kagerman et al.,(2013) suggested the following features of leadership style in a dynamic change environment.

1. Standardisation 2. Managing the complex systems 3. Comprehensive communication structure 4. Safety and security 5. Resource calibration 6. Regulatory framework understanding 7. Organisational design 8. Training and knowledge management.

Holistically, these features align with reports by few consulting companies (E&Y,2019; Deloitte; 2018) in context to the scenario in the WMS sector. However, the challenges for leaders is changing behaviour expectations, especially from younger clients and mapping the capabilities, resources under the regulatory framework. According to Fitzgerald et al.,(2013), understanding DT's goal is imperative for dynamic leadership within a traditional firm. It is crucial to share a vision about the state of change from present to expected state, what phase of the DT will be required to be adopted to bring changes in work processes to steer the change swiftly.

According to Wade et al.,(2017), the digital transformation is viewed as the conduct of a digital orchestra, wherein the leader in charge of this DT is a maestro. Thus, culture is directly linked with leadership as leaders bring new approaches, knowledge, awareness and strategic capabilities to adopt the DT phenomenon. On the contrary, there is inadequate literature specific to the WMS sector ecosystem. Hence, not many directives were found, discussed, and explored from a leadership role, perspectives, and constraints in digital change transformation.

The significance of the DT in Industry revolution 4.0 is not only about technology (Westernman et al.,2011; Kane et al.,2015) but the right culture with the right set of capabilities under the direction of the right leadership. However, changing the existing culture towards adapting digital culture is the most critical challenge in traditional WMS organisations as the internal ecosystem is engrained with traditional values, approaches set earlier by management, leadership and buy-in approach by top management regarding DT adaption. According to Warner & Wager (2018), the DT is an ongoing renewal process that either refresh or replace organisational approach and culture. Kane(2017) has stated in his article "Technology Fallacy", have stated his research findings indicated the culture is a key driver

in the adoption of digital transformation and how questioning senior executives about the process getting this right culture reveals the linkage with the digital maturity of organisations.

Thus, dynamic leadership is critical in initiating the digital culture, while literature pictures the culture is developed based on the digital maturity levels of organisations. Due to the lack of literature in focus on the WMS case study, it cannot be confirmed if the above-stated elements are key critical success factors for adapting the DT switchover. Hence it is necessary to involve the senior leadership team in data collection to have precise ground reality within WMS firms and their perspectives about the digital maturity factor.

2.5.2: Digital maturity for adopting an agile approach

Commenting on the current scenario of the FSI industry, according to Vanguard's CIO, John Marcante, the customers are not judging their wealth management service provider against their competitors but comparing with technology leaders like Google, Apple, and Facebook. This indicates the service level expectations growing among young customers age groups (gen Y, Z and Alpha). This takes back to three phases of digital transformation discussed in earlier chapter indicates the digital readiness levels of firms. According to a survey report by Alphafmc consulting firm on the digital maturity of WMS firms(2020), 92% of the Wealth management firms are mobilising their efforts to embrace the digital change, but firms have fragmented implementation to only by specific processes. Hence, most legacy processes are still operating and part of revenue generation (Taylor,2020). According to the Cisco(2017) report on leadership and maturity in the Financial service sector, the major chunk of revenue comes from the customer segment of baby boomers and millennials looking for a seamless and personal approach in managing their investments. Thus human element seems to be a critical part of the digital shift (report associated with Roubini Thoughtlab, 2017). These traditional firms adapt the digitalization phase to re-innovate their back end and documentation-oriented work process to match the customers' agile expectations instead of providing a holistic view of the DT process. This strategy provides the tandem between relationships with a seamless experience and value creation.

Thus, in continuation of the discussion, there is a gap in elevating the digital maturity among all organisational stakeholders. Many researchers have proposed the digital readiness framework relevant for organisations with the objective of transformation by comprehending the opportunities for innovating the existing processes by assembling the requisite assets, knowledge and relationships (Lichtblau et al.,2015; Remane et al.,2017; Teece,2007; Sambamurthy et al.,2003; Bain and Company,2016; Cisco,2017. Sambamurthy et al., 2003 p. 245) but there is fragmented clarity about undermining factors in the development of digital readiness. However, the following researchers argue about the mandate to comprehend the current state of an organisation by identifying the potential problems, vulnerabilities, opportunities and risk assessments before adapting to the digital readiness framework (Lawton, 2015; Kaufman & Horton, 2015; Vial, 2019).

To summarize from the above sections, due to speedy developments in technology and its influence over the traditional services sector, the organisations are in a dilemma about their orientation on internal digital maturity or leveraging newer technologies for quicker revenue generation. The literature review in this context emphasises building the internal capabilities to assess and reconfigure the resources accordingly (Sambamurthy et al., 2003; Horton & Kaufman, 2015; Lichtblau et al.,2015). Connecting this approach with the WMS sector scenario, due to the rigid nature of various interconnected elements like traditional processes, culture, approach and resistance within the framework, obstructs the digital mindset and readiness within the WMS sector.

The digital maturity models by researchers are a significant contribution in integrating the organisation focus with its DT objective, as each of these models discusses the specific aspects in developing digital maturity. Horton & Kaufman(2015) focusses on operational agility by emphasizing core operational processes within internal departmental and supply chain flow. Horton & Kaufman's model aims to increase the agility in the entire process by determining the points of vulnerabilities. While Kohnke (2017) emphasizes the alignment of four aspects to improve the organisation's digital maturity: Leadership, Communication, Capabilities and Sustainability factors, these are critical factors for the digital readiness environment.

Berman(2012) favours adopting technologies in equipping the organisation with digital maturity. Specific technologies like predictive capability and data analytics can enhance the insights and optimise the performance.

2.6: Literature overview on Digital Transformation challenges

According to Oliver Wyman's report (2020) on Wealth management companies, the most significant challenges to traditional industry are shaping the digital business for tomorrow from yesterday's legacy (Allchin, 2020). There is significant pressure on external and internal cultural transitions, impacting critical features like the product, operational processes and culture. Hence, the DT phenomenon across all industries is large-scale and company-wide transformations, not just technology transformations (Matt et al.,2015). So far, the perspectives in the literature indicate the lack of unified understanding of the Digital Transformation phenomenon holistically, and It majorly impacts the human element involved in the ongoing DT change process. The lack of long-term vision from the digital change process will lead to inertia and resistance unless the top management does not collaborate in steering the change process. There is no specific literature indicating the type of leadership and culture requirement for successful digital adaption. As per Kane (2017), leadership is the most critical factor in turning digital disruption into an opportunity for organisations to branch out new revenue-generating models. As per the view of Oberer & Erkollar (2018), according to behavioural leadership theories, there should be more focus on a human-side element to bring efficiency and productivity in the process of the value change process.

Due to inadequate research in the WMS sector, there is a lack of visibility on inertia and resistance specific to chosen case study sectors surrounding the DT phenomenon (Chanias et al., 2018; Hess et al., 2016; Nadeem et al.,2018). As per the HBR article on the financial sector, there is \$1.3trillion investment being done till 2019 into digital transformation, but 70% of traditional firms have not achieved their digital goals(Tabrizi et al.,2019).

2.6.1: Fintech (Financial Technology Firms)

The Financial industry is constantly adapting to significant transformations over the many decades within the regulatory frameworks. Endogenous factors usually impact the WMS industry by slightest changes in political, geographical regimes and legislative changes. However, in present times, the major challenge unfolding its impact is "Fintechs", the firms providing services loaded with advanced technology to provide tailored end-to-end seamless service to customers. The Fintech is an acronym which stands for financial technology, combining bank expertise with modern management science techniques and the computer" (Bettinger,1972, p.62)

The expert ability of Fintech and its growing market presence in service offerings directly pressurise the traditional firm's sustainability factor. The niche expertise of fintech firms is the compelling factor over the traditional wealth service firms and pull approach for younger customers (gen Y, Z & Alpha). This customer segment wants independence, decision-making flexibility, and digital-based interactions on investment advisory with minimum human intervention in cost-effective ways. Thus, digitally-born companies like Facebook, Amazon, Aliexpress and many others are slowly invading the markets spaces in most traditional industries. Holistically, the form of "fintech" amalgamation of financial innovation services with technology-laden services (*Finance + technology=Fintech*).

The fintech firms leverage the latest technologies like AI Robo advisor, data analytics technologies and many other dynamic technologies in providing niche seamless experiences to their customers. This unique selling proposition concept of Fintech provides the customised niche services at a lower cost, resulting in customers' shifting behaviour. Fintech firms are primarily active in BFSI sectors in the UK. At the same time, "Big-tech" companies provide financial investment options as part of a much broader set of activities, prominently active and operationally in Southeast Asia, East Africa and Latin America (BIS Annual Economic Report,2018). According to Gomber et al.,(2017), there are three main reasons to make fintech companies distinctive from traditional wealth services companies: new customised products and tailored solutions to suit customer requirements.

Secondly, the customized product packaging and advisory services in less transaction cost than traditional service firms digitally and innovative practices. Fintechs builds a frictionless experience for customers with the right resources and cybersecurity features. Thirdly, the agile, efficient and innovative practices make its Fintech firms' culture distinctive from traditional WMS firms.

The innovative digital technology is the major essence of the fintech value proposition. Deloitte(2020) stated in their report on "*Tech trends*" that disruptive technologies like AI, Machine learning and data analytics are the currently dominant technologies in the WMS industry. Organisations have constantly been increasing their investments into these technologies to keep up with customers' rising expectations, and these advanced technologies strengthen the new processes, efficiency, and agility in developing the systems to meet the set goals.

AI (Artificial Intelligence): According to Accenture's report on AI strategy by C-Suite executives in the WMS industry(2020) reveals that 76% per cent of top executives are still struggling with the adoption of AI and scaling its overall business processes (Awalegaonkar et al., 2020). In the WMS sector, the AI is specially deployed in the front office section of the operational process, keeping the client interaction personalisation as wealth managers or relationship managers can anticipate the customers' needs, and customisation can adopt in providing services. Robo-advisor is already functional as front-end advisors in the WMS sector at various deployment levels to cater generally retail sect of customers. It can calculate the best investment opportunities, the best interest rates, pretty much everything someone needs to stay on top of their investment prospects.

Big Data: Big data generated from various sources like internet searches, online transactions, social media, and purposefully content through sensor networks leads to big data perceptiveness (George et al., 2014). Currently, big data is in use everywhere, and the systematic analysis process identifies the patterns by leveraging complex data sets to build other strategic decisions. Traditional institutions require machine learning tools to process it quickly and accurately in ways that allow them to serve customers better, save money, save

time and efficiently. The traditional Wealth management companies are currently under severe pressure due to changing the behaviour of customers, cybersecurity threats and scalability through using disruptive technology.

Blockchain: Blockchain or distributed ledger technology, its underlying fundamental technology over which other applications are built, like cryptocurrency, has been developed. In the context of the WMS industry, wherein back-office processing has challenging tasks of risk management like KYC (know your customers), and ML(Money laundering issues) are time-consuming and possibilities of causing the errors. Blockchain technology is secure, data protected, and tamper-free, minimizing the transaction cost and crafting agile onboarding processes.

Fintech firms are already adopting the blockchain technology compared to the traditional WMS firms in services like digital payments, escrow services (Loans, mortgage services), keeping the minimum transactions cost and maximum data security. According to FCA(2020), regulatory requirements for financial firms approves the use of distributed ledger technology in “Reg Tech (Regulatory technologies)” in automating the specific processes before being executed.

Cloud Computing Technology: This is the next wave of disruptive technology, which certainly requires the digital maturity of firms to differentiate from IT strategy to cloud usage. Firms need to gain expertise in utilising the IT infrastructure aspects or associating with expertise hand to provide on-demand availability of information in the form of services through the cloud-based. This technology provides data centralization accessibility, and it is cost-effective, providing a frictionless experience to customers. The traditional WMS firms handle massive customer-related data with complex IT systems and processes, indirectly impacting transactions cost to customers, while the adaption of cloud-based technology will enhance data management and scalability.

Thus, summarizing on influence and scope of disruptive technologies in the case study sector, these technologies are much in use by Fintechs firms in their platter of niche services. Sebastian et al.,(2017) indicate that companies need to devise an approach with

game-changing opportunities and existential threats. In agreement, Sebastian et al.,(2017) the traditional WMS firms adopt the mindset approach towards adopting these disruptive technology innovations for business scalability and sustainability in competitive markets.

The majority of industry practitioners claims that the failure rate in adapting the technology and deployment of digital strategy is between 70-80% in traditional WMS sectors (Chantias et al., 2018; Nadeem et al.,2018; HBR,2019; Nucoro, 2020) and the gap in devising and recalibrating the dynamic capabilities for digital transformational change (Bharadwaj et al., 2013, Matt et al., 2015).

2.6.2: Outline on fintech challenges

According to Lee and Shin(2018), the tech-savvy gen X &Y have the primary choice of Fintechs for their investment planning due to their services, flexibility and lesser transactions cost. The asset feature of the Fintech model in the WMS sector is Robo-advisor, a 24/7 automated wealth manager led by AI technology and deployment of cloud usage with secured data management features. These advisory options are based on algorithms mix suggested from the ML (Machine learning) collated from customers' preferences and risk patterns, providing much more scalability in their investment mix and options. The penetrations of digital services by Fintech have been disrupting the traditional model of human-led advisory in the WMS sector and have been the driving force behind the changes in expectations of the customers.

Currently, the agile ways deployed by fintech firms leveraging the technology have reduced the fees per transaction compared to fees charged by traditional financial advisors' (Wealth managers, relationship managers and financial advisors). However, there is apprehension regarding the role of the human advisor will exist in a comprehensive advisory function in the wealth services.

Chanas(2017), highlights that fintech's sector is strategically focusing on customer-centric planning rather than product-centric. While the traditional WMS sector focus is product-centric, there is a considerable emphasis on the push strategy(sales) of products without scrutinising the customer requirement & preferences. The research by Matt, Hess & Benlian(2015), brings a new business-centric approach, wherein business firms align their focus, transforming the elements of an organisation like functions, products and processes. To summarise, management's approach is crucial to strategising the transformation path as the vision needs to integrate with value creation by meeting customers' requirements in more agile and efficient ways. Yeow et al.,(2017) stated that the technological factor's implications for behaviour & expectations factors introduce the risk of goal derailment.

In the transition of the Industrial Revolution, the current era of 4.0 is the digital transformation era, defined as "the use of technology to improve enterprise performance or reach of enterprise radically" (Westerman, Bonnet & McAfee, 2014). The practitioner Westerman(2014) explains that digital transformation is associated with a few key specific areas in the organisation required to undergo complete transitions: Customer experience, process and business models, as a significant attribute of digital transformation, is the "customer-centric" financial services industry. However, the comparisons of service levels approaches between traditional WMS and Fintech firms indicate the gap in identifying the sequence of the key steps towards embracing and deploying core resources for adapting the DT into existing ecosystems. Further to the investigation of literature from academic and industry practitioners, the following sequence is designed to summarize the approach of transitions journey undertaken by the traditional WMS sector towards achieving the digital transformation state. This sequence of transitioning is termed the "Circular Transformation Cycle.

Figure 7: Circular Transformation Model (Author's development).

The above diagram depicts the present scenario in the traditional WMS sector to achieve the desired state of digital transformation. Given view from industrial revolution transitions, the various factors trailed from the 3rd industrial revolution era accelerating the effort in the invention. The shift of analogue to digital services led to the birth of "Fintech" in the same period of 2005 as traditional financial industries were impacted heavily due to financial crisis in 2008 and compelled to follow restricted regulatory framework less scope of scalability innovation. This movement has boosted the growth of fintechs in the financial investment space. The 4th Industry revolution is purely the insertion of the innovation phase, deployment of agile process and highly integrated services model with a customer-centric focus. The diffusion component is part of the DOI theory (Rogers, 1962), briefly explaining how and why the diffusion of innovative practices can be relevant. In the WMS sector, diffusion is linked with the customer segments acquired by firms based on customer expectations, investment portfolio, and digital adaptability, which will be the critical element in the cycle of circular transformational. Thus, traditional firms objectively need to link their digital strategy with the target customer market, planning to acquire and provide agile and innovative services.

Similarly, in the WMS sector, its organisation approach to the target market decides the diffusion element of this model. According to earlier researchers, the inadequate clarity about specific elements in the literature indicates that factors like organisational willingness, structure, leadership, and culture contribute to a successful adaption of DT shift.

Finally, creation is a significant phase closely linked with the internal ecosystem of the organisation, identifying the gaps and forming a framework with scaffolding parameters for creating the cycle of DT adaption.

2.6.3: Evolutionary digital impact: The Wealth Management Services sector

Digital transformation is a vital part of the change evolution of all businesses in every industry, the present era of a widely expected rise in innovative practices in customer services and associated processes. All financial service sectors are striving to achieve dynamic capabilities in providing innovative services through technologies. Information Technology (IT) alignment is a significant part of the digital transformation process because it has positively impacted performance (Gerow et al., 2014; Renaud et al., 2016). The contemporary fintech sector responds swiftly with a tremendous ability to adapt to the environment and digitally-led innovations inducing the operational and strategic models (Coltman et al., 2015; Fonstad & Subramani, 2009). Business practices are increasingly digitalising their operations and processes (Bharadwaj et al., 2013; El Sawy, 2003). Thus, it makes it more critical in present circumstances to know the implications and scope of the DT. Due to the diminishing line of differentiation between IT strategy and DT strategy (Bharadwaj et al., 2013; Coltman et al., 2015), leading to a fusion between them in the form of digital strategy (Galliers, 2011). In a nutshell, there is evidence that traditional IT strategy merging with DT strategy but this research emphasis crucial aspects on developing panoramic capabilities to manage the dynamic digital transformation in a discussed scenario.

Top-management and leaders' role is significant in developing the fluidity in the organisational ecosystem to develop the right set of panoramic capabilities. Undoubtedly, the fluid culture is crucial for the constant calibration of the resources and capabilities. In the current scenario, the WMS sector depends on the leader's ability to transition into digital transitioning by transforming the business revenue models and adding value to existing services through digital technologies (Kohli and Melville 2018; Lucas et al., 2013).

The transitioning of traditional WMS firms into digital space encompassing change in mindset, people, culture and process, as mentioned in earlier paragraphs, after the financial crisis of 2008, the WMS sector is witnessing a great extent of cultural change but limited scalability due to regulatory framework. The authors Matt et al. (2015) explains that DT is more than just a switch to new technology. It is all about integrating people, process and product (bringing in people, process and product transformations). Thus, literature directs towards devising a strategy for embracing DT(Bharadwaj et al.,2013; Matt et al.,2015) designed the term "DTS" (Digital transformation strategy) to manage the transformations by sustainably integrating digital technologies.

Figure 8: The attributes of the Digital Transformation phenomenon (Author's contribution).

The diagram illustrates the central focus on attributes of adapting the DT strategy in connection to the scenario of the case study sector. The significant attributes discussed in available literature in relationship with a set vision for DT transitioning are people, process and product transformation.

In connection with people, the resources connect the human link with disruptive technology, harnessing the technology's capabilities to achieve value creation through services. Processes count each administrative and operational process involved in the path of value creation, requires deep analysis of each process-flow to provide a seamless and frictionless experience to customers. Lastly, the product, a core attribute of digital transformation, requires talent harness and resource integration to shift towards a customer-centric approach instead of a product-centric approach.

2.6.4: Is culture change necessary for embracing the Digital Transformation ?

From the study undertaken, organisations are required to undergo complete culture transformation in the context of WMS sector sensitivity towards external factors, like disruptions due to technology, competition, and changing customer expectations. The matured organisations tend to adapt to technology for faster ROI (return on investment) and customer base. However, these decisions on change of business model inclined towards quick returns and customer loyalty, but in the longer run, these organisations tend to overlook their internal digital readiness and maturity to manoeuvring the change transitioning. Aldrich & Ruef,(2006) explain that significant change involves breaking the existing routines and shifting to new competencies that challenge organisational knowledge. This calls for alignment of the pre-digital strategy with involved stakeholders in transitioning, focussing on vertical and horizontal integration of involved departments and processes.

Thus, it directs towards organisations' maturity levels regarding knowledge, resources, and cultural appropriateness. In recent years, it is evident that digital transformations implications have underpinned the strategic role in information technology in firms (Bharadwaj et al., 2013a, Fitzgerald et al.,2014), as technology has become an imperative entrant in the traditional financial services market, causing the seismic waves in traditional business (Christensen & Overdorf 2000). Constructively to accomplish any fundamental business transformation, organisations embrace intentional strategies, establish the digitalisation implement IT strategy, sustain the disruption, and leverage the opportunities opened by advanced technologies (Bharadwaj et al.,2013; Downes & Nunes 2013; Hess et al.,2016).

Scholars from various disciplines and research fields agree that culture essentially impacts the success of business transformations. Philip & McKeown (2004, p.625) put it: "business transformation is about bringing radical changes in organisational culture in terms of structure, processes and above all, people's attitudes, beliefs and behaviours". Following Venkatraman's (1994) proposition, cultural transformation is crucial to fully exploit new IT deployment benefits. Therefore, establishing a digital mindset and culture change is indispensable for successful DT (Fitzgerald et al.,2014). Customer-centricity is essential for meeting customers' changing needs and facilitates digital transformation because it shows companies' readiness to change (Hartl & Hess,2017). According to leading researchers, culture is a prominent factor in the digital transformation journey scale. However, there is a lack of clarity on why organisations struggle to build the right culture, which are core reasons that make it challenging to extract the suitable risk and measure for successful implementation of digital transformation conceptualisations (Straub et al.,2002). There are limited perspectives towards understanding the critical factors necessary for setting the culture in adaptation. Significant challenges exist from times of pre-digital transformation, prospering on its tangible and intangible resources. Firms cannot ignore goodwill and relationship management. In traditional firms' settings, customers' loyalty developed with mutual understanding and trust developed over the years. The advent of new disruptions through technology is changing the organisations from inside out rather than outside-in approaches. Currently, the financial services firms pose an existential risk from fintech services (Ross et al., 2016; Bharadwaj et al.,2013; Sebastian et al.,2017; Tumbas et al.,2017a).

2.7: Theoretical research gap

The DT strategy provides the roadmap to traditional organisations to prepare themselves for the growing digital tsunami around them. Based on the review of the earliest theories on digital business strategy (DBS), researchers Bharadwaj et al.,2013; Kahre et al.,2017 proposed combining organisational IT strategy and information strategy (IS strategy) instead of the traditional method of aligning these strategies individually.

This proposition attracted attention from researchers and academicians (Sia et al.,2016; Yeow et al.,2017; Chanas, 2017; Leischnig et al.,2017) within the field of organisational management, but the proposition lacked integrated strategic actions in deploying the DT.

At the same time, Matt et al.,(2015) highlighted the integration of technology with the operational process to achieve the set digital shift goals. The success of DT is linked with an impactful strategy by realigning the resources in creating value creation. In this ongoing process of repetitive integration, various factors are required to support developing the right ecosystem for the deployment of DT strategy. According to the existing literature, the calibration of the tangible and intangible capabilities plays a crucial role in the path of value creation(Lucas et al., 2013; Melville., 2018). At the same time, Parasuraman & Colby (2001) highlight the critical role of technology in meeting customer expectations. Similarly, Osmundsen et al.,(2018a)claim the organisational maturity is an impactful factor in elevating the focus on the customer rather than the product-centric approach.

Along with the maturity factor, other aspects like mindset, trust, communication and risk affinity are critical factors in building maturity in business organisations(Hartl & Hess., 2017) as DT change is a large scale transformation process including complex stages of change inclusive of all critical assets and processes holistically. Considering in context of the WMS firms, cost critical concern highlighted by industry practitioners in at middle management level where financial and wealth managers are concerned with the rapid shift in their functional role existence due to deployment of AI-led Robo advisory by many firms (Fitzgerald et al., 2013) and Kappelman et al., (2018). Thus, this research agrees with the involvement of key stakeholders from corporate, business and functional levels within organisations for devising the DT deployment strategy.

As per the literature review, it is evident that technology is imperative in the DT phenomenon within traditional firms undergoing tremendous pressure to manage expectations from customers by elevating resource re-calibrations. The outcomes are drawn from academic researchers and industry practitioners (Lucas & Goh, 2009; Westerman et al., 2011; Downes & Nunes, 2013; Porter & Heppelmann, 2014; Karimi & Walter, 2015), provides the insights

that disruptive technologies are key factors in increasing the dynamics of expectation and behavioural change from the customers.

Traditional organisations must fundamentally transform their business model restructuring holistically to survive (Hartl & Hess, 2017; Porter & Heppelmann, 2014). The undertaken literature review noted the contributions by researchers and practitioners to define the DT phenomenon, which primarily resulted in creating some understanding and knowing the attributes for embracing the DT successfully. However, in the context of the research case study sector, there is a lack of clarity on the relevance of attributes discussed in earlier literature sections as fewer studies were undertaken on the dynamic traditional WMS sector. Despite few researchers conducted studies to explore the critical features of DT deployment, highlighting the role of culture and regulatory framework in derailing the efforts of organisations towards embracing the DT. However, there is no comprehensive literature exhuming stakeholders' perceptions involved in devising and implementing the DT deployment strategy. It is critical to understand the stakeholder perspectives for successfully digital transitioning as the human and technology are critical attributes.

Despite all availability of resources, capabilities and digital expertise, the WMS firms are still struggling to navigate the shift from legacy to digital due to underlying challenges in adapting to the speed of digital transitions. As per the theoretical review of practitioners' frameworks, viewpoints revealed the focal point of challenges in digital evolution in traditional companies, blamed for technology, but the reasons are divergent factors contributing to investment waste into digital change.

Thus, this research study explores the perspectives of research stakeholders on the extent of the DT phenomena in the chosen traditional WMS sector.

2.8: Extractions of theories and conceptual framework

Drawing out the outcomes from the literature review, the factors like culture within traditional organisations and the criticality of having a unified understanding of vision from embracing the DT change is significant. However, devising of DT strategy is inclusive of several perceptive elements for successful implementation.

According to the Alpha FMC report (global fund media ltd publication, 2018), the survey of the 15 largest asset management firms in the UK found two primary obstacles in this industry's digitalisation process: culture and mindset approach.

- A. 62% of results states that the company culture and mindset is a significant obstacle
- B. Legacy and traditional process hurdle to adopting digital transformation
- C. Disapproval mindset towards disruptive technology.

Considering the literature outcomes on DT attributes, there is a lack of stakeholder perceptions in devising the DT strategy in WMS sectors. The research gap identified a significant focus towards pre or post-deployment strategy on the adaption of disruptive technology. Hence in light of the above discussion, the appropriate perception-based model is the TAM model and Dynamic Capability Model for developing the conceptual framework for research.

2.8.1: TAM MODEL

There is a fragmented understanding of defining the DT and the underlying failure in the WMS sector. As per the HBR report, around \$1.3 trillion amount spent till 2018, \$900 billion, went to wasted (Behnam et al.,2019). This indicates the gap still exists for holistic reasons in the case study sector. However, there are many frameworks and models available in literature pieces, but they lack stakeholder perception for appropriate application to the current scenario of the traditional WMS sector.

The author would testify the TAM model (Davis, 1986), although the TAM model has been revised into several versions by Venkatesh & Davis (1996).

TAM (Technology acceptance model) was developed by Fred Davis on this doctoral thesis (1985). Davis's first framework was formulated on components linked with beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours (Chaniyas, 2017). As the TAM model has streams of revision on the framework, the first model initially proposed to respond to user motivation, which is directly influenced by the external stimulus of the system component's features and capabilities. TAM-1 model has improvised the discussions on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use which linked with the attitude towards using the technology, while TAM 2 (Arbore et al.,2014) is an extension of the framework including the three social forces and their impact on the opportunity to adopt or reject a new system. TAM 3 (Venkatesh et al.,2003) was again relooked and redesigned to understand the acceptance patterns specifically for e-commerce. This model was widely accepted but lacked prime focus factors like trust, cybersecurity, or customer privacy (Baby & Kannammal, 2020).

The TAM model had gained all attention based on its strength, but the current rapid digital change scenario has turned into its weakness. Continuous disruptions in the business ecosystem has their threats building up their impact on service delivery mechanism, technological change and sustainability.

Another end of this development of disruptions unlocks potential business opportunities (Lai, 2017; Parasuraman and Colby, 2001). Meuter et al.,(2000) focussed on customer intentions, adapting to new technology, which is a valid point in the chosen context. Consistent pressurised situations lead to adapt change management linked with TAM elements. The new version of TAM frameworks has limitations and criticism attached to variables pertaining to the user's behaviour, subjective intentions and influences. In contrast, interpersonal influence is subjective as in organisation as within firms superior can influence an employee to use technology to perform any particular task in a specific way, but an external person cannot influence (Ang, Ramayah & Amin 2015; Shan & King, 2015) recommends that TAM framework is not plausible or accurate in the disruptive ecosystem.

IT-enabled organisational transformation rests heavily on business rationales due to IT (Information Technology) potentials for making organisational operations more efficient. As Robey and Sahay (1996, p.93) expressed, transforming organisations with information technologies is a crucial business objective because traditional structures are often ineffective in producing desired levels of productivity, customer service, employee welfare, and shareholder value". However, since the mere implementation of IT systems provides limited benefits for an organisation without accompanying changes in organisational characteristics and conditions, organisational value is modulated by the extent that the organisation can change (Venkatraman, 1994).

Therefore, organisational resistance or inability to change following the introduction of new IT has become an essential subject in IT-enabled organisational transformation (Besson & Rowe, 2012; Keen, 1981; Silva & Hirschheim, 2007). Indeed, Besson & Rowe (2012, p.105) argued that it "is organisational inertia that makes (organisational transformation) an important theoretical and practical problem". The general notion of inertia is perhaps best explained as "a complicated way of saying that no matter how you try, nothing seems to happen" (Keen, 1981, p.24), hence outcomes of earlier research in the field of digital transformation, organisational culture is a significant factor for the success of DT adaptation.

So, based on theoretical research, it is necessary to uncover the critical drivers. This gap in existence is the central theme in formulating the second question of this research study.

- Q.2 What are the critical factors for achieving successful digital transformation?

Thus, to evaluate the foundational factors in understanding the digital transformation, the first TAM framework model (Davis, 1989) is pertinently helpful in uncovering the four elements in understanding the external variables, perceived usefulness, perceived use and attitudes in the process of embracing DT. The exploration of literature hindsight the of various resistances factors, hindering the change management. Agile management approaches can rebuild customer perceptions positively. Hence management approach is the main factor in DT change.

2.8.2: Dynamic Capability Model

Capability building has been a central theme for research for academic scholars in change management and strategic management (Teece, 2007; Schilke et al.,2018; Yeow et al., 2017). The dynamic capability framework (Teece, 2007) provides the further extended vision to resource-based view to capabilities which organisations can realign according to their intangible and tangible resource base (Vial, 2019).

Leading researchers and practitioners' definitions of organisational capabilities explain the dynamic capabilities aspect in digital transformation adaption.

- David Teece et al., (1997): The firm's ability to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments.

- Zollo & Winter,(2002): A dynamic capability is a learned and stable pattern of collective activity through which the organisation systematically generates and 67 modifies its operating routines in pursuit of improved effectiveness.
- Helfat,(2007): The subset of competencies/capabilities allows the firm to create new products and processes and respond to changing market circumstances.
- Eisenhardt & Martin(2000): Dynamic capabilities are the organisational and strategic routines by which firms achieve new resources configurations as markets emerge, collide, split, evolve and die.
- Zahra & George(2002): Dynamic capabilities are change-oriented capabilities that help firms redeploy and reconfigure their resource base to meet evolving customer demands and competitor strategies.
- Lee et al.,(2010): A source of sustainable advantage in Schumpeterian regimes of rapid change
- Zahra et al.,(2006): The processes to reconfigure a firm's resources and operational routines in the manner envisioned and deemed appropriate by its principal decisionmaker.
- Ambrosini et al.,(2009): There are three levels of dynamic capabilities related to a manager's perceptions of environmental dynamism: Dynamic capabilities, renewing dynamic capabilities and regenerative capabilities.

David Teece (1997) has coined the term "dynamic capabilities "as the ability of firm's while Zahra et al.,(2006) has mentioned processes within the firms. Eishenhardt et al.,(2000) defined capabilities as routines of the organisational process. The complexity of the process varies by the criticality of the process within organisations.

Hence, the argument of organisational routines and capabilities focused on the complexity of the project transformation requirement. Nevertheless, before setting new routines, it is a priority to understand the required set of capabilities for change transition, which will differ in every business practice.

Traditional firms must evaluate their capabilities and competencies to build digital capabilities (Morakanyane et al.,2017), as a firm thrives on leveraging and exploiting the potentialities to achieve the objectives.

Hence it utmost necessity to access the nature of dynamic capabilities to build the capabilities. As described by David Teece (2007), dynamic capability includes all ordinary and dynamic competencies. The extended version of RBV theory (Resource-based view). The DC model combines three foundational components of theory, the strategic three foundational components of theory involving all firms' technical and ordinary components.

There is agreement over its high concentration focus on core capabilities required for business survival (Jiang et al.,2019; Schilke et al.,2018). With this dispute on the meaning of foundational focus of capabilities, Morakanyane et al.,(2017) claimed that DT focussed organisations, must-have digital capabilities aligned with technologies to create value creation. The critical review of the outcomes by researchers must evaluate how firms can gauge their capability requirement for digital change. This research will focus on analysing the existing platter of capabilities in the traditional WMS sector.

The capability is a continuous evaluation as technology progression is constant; hence capability needs to change with the flow to match the speed of change requirement. While from the perspective of dynamic capabilities, organisations to integrate, realign their resources and capabilities to renew or alter their capability cluster required for coping with tremendous change transition (Teece, 2007; Helfat & Peteraf, 2015).

The critical review of diversified literature on capabilities Showed existing clusters of a specific area of capabilities like Customer services (Chari & David, 2012; Solis et al., 2014), value chain services and managerial capabilities (Helfat & Peteraf, 2015; Lee et al., 2017) and supply chain capabilities (Barney 2012; Ranganathan et al., 2011). So, the capabilities are a set of routines, which becomes an internal core process of organisations abilities. There is a high risk of being reproduced by other organisations; hence, these dynamic characteristics of capability have raised researchers' diversified interests. A few factors are linked with the theme of capability, which requires a critical review of the organisation's size, structure, and complexity of the

internal process (alignment issues). Teece, Pisano & Shuen(1997, p.516) defined dynamic capabilities as the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments.

This definition opens up the questions with an aspect of the DT, like the firms' ability to adapt DT, how they get impacted, and how to identify them with the right capability for context. These are signposts towards narrowing the theory over capability construction.

2.8.2.1 Relationship between maturity and dynamic capability

The retrospection of an organisation's holistic internal capability factor is crucial from the organisational readiness aspect for DT changes. As capability well-defined as an organisation's ability to "perform a set of co-ordinated tasks utilising organisational resources, to achieve a particular result" (Helfat & Peteraf,2003), the ability to engender or reconfigure an organisation's existing capability is the dynamic capability (Zahra et al.,2006).

The two prominent researchers David Teece (1997) and Eisenhardt et al. (2000), have defined dynamic capabilities in the following perspective. "The firm's ability to integrate, build and reconfigure its external and internal competencies to address rapidly changing environment" (Teece,2007). The organisational and strategic routines by which firms achieve new resource configurations as markets emerge, collide, split, evolve and die" (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). Analysing of definition by Teece(2007) has been significantly considering external and internal competencies, which formulates from the internal process and activities involving the employees of the firm the external competencies like competitive environment are two essential facets of dynamic capabilities, while Eisenhardt et al.,(2000), states, all strategic process and activities organisation undertakes for creating new competencies are just repetitive.

Researchers have different perspectives on the construction of dynamic capability. Firstly, strategic alignment is the critical area of top management in WMS firms. Hence the involvement of experience, knowledge and process alignment is highly recommended. Secondly, the development of capability is not instantly. Thus, a set of specific routines in

delivering the services the ordinary capabilities can prove dynamic in any disruptive environment. Does every organisational process is the firm's dynamic capability or contribute to forming dynamic capability? While intriguing the nature of dynamic capability.

Mclaughlin (2012), has mentioned "Organisations have traditionally focused on the orchestration of processes to achieve desired and repeatable outcomes to a specified standard, in a nutshell, "systemising internal activities".

In the pursuit to embrace the DT, organisations tend to adapt to new technologies rather than internal capability readiness. In the current scenario, organisations can leverage technological advantages based on the maturity of firms and adapting capabilities. Thus, it is a prerequisite to analyse the maturity levels for digital transformational evolution.

2.8.2.2 Models of digital maturity frameworks

From the available literature and reports from researchers and industry practitioners from IS and change management practices fields, comprehending that organisations achieve maturity by associating capabilities like strategic decisions, resources, culture, and suitable technology leads to achieving the digital maturity model. There are several organisational maturity models in recent literature, focusing on specific issues within various businesses' scope. Kane (2017c) has defined maturity as the capacity to respond the change appropriately, while Vial (2019) argued that dynamic capabilities might be beneficial to understand how firms can design and maintain maturity mechanisms to ensure adaptability factor.

The dynamic capabilities are changing based on the nature of disruptions and the advent of new technological advancements. Digital maturity is a signpost for organisations to understand each critical factors' level of readiness associated with digital transformation. The theme of dynamic capabilities is of interest among practitioners and academics.

Generally, as per business practices, firms involve external expertise to critically evaluate the existing process and evaluate the extent so the realignment of the process with the set of vision, basically fresh pair of process experts for assessment and calibration in stabilising the

change requirement. Following are the leading organisational maturity framework, been evaluated in assessing the core factors in understanding the necessities of dynamic capabilities in the DT adaption process.

Based on the evaluation of these maturity models, the following factors emerged as significant factors in the calibration of dynamic capability framework: leadership, culture, customer service approach, value chain analysis and process modifications. Hence, top management's involvement is crucial to understanding their perceptions and challenges in building a conducive ecosystem in the WMS industry.

Table 4: Theoretical approaches on digital maturity

	Framework/model	Institution/researcher	Assessment /approach
1	Industry 4.0 Maturity Model	Schumacher, Eril, Sihn [2015]	62 maturity items which are grouped into nine dimensions: strategy, leadership, customers, products, operation, culture, people, governance, technology
2	Interrelationship between the digital transformation, strategy and organizational capability	Schumann, Tittmann [2015]	Assessment in three dimensions: digital transformation, digital business strategy, organizational capability
3	Digital transformation framework	Matt, Hess, Benlian [2015]	The four different dimensions: use of technologies, changes in value creation, structural changes, financial aspects
4	Five digital aptitude business domain model	KMPG Report(2016)	Suggested domains: vision & strategy, digital talent, digital first processes, sourcing and infrastructure, governance
5	The Digital Maturity Model 4.0.	Forrester/Gill and VanBoskirk 2016)	Four dimensions determine digital maturity: culture, organization, technology, insights
6	Digital Acceleration Index	BCG [2016],Consultancy report	The 4 building blocks evaluated: business strategy driven by digital, digitize the core, new digital growth, enablers
7	Digital REadiness Assessment MaturitY model	De Carolis, etc. [2017]	Evaluation the maturity indexes of company's process area: design and engineering; production management; quality management; maintenance management; logistics
8	Digital Services Capability Model	Wulf, Mettler, Brenner [2017]	17 capabilities of digital transformation in eight classes: consumers, services, processes and activities, organization, information, technologies and infrastructure, strategies, environment
9	Organizations digital readiness framework	Sánchez, Zuntini[2018]	External and internal analysis including: ecosystem collaboration, five forces analysis, resources and capabilities, value chain analysis, initial conditions, barriers

2.8.3: Historically transitioning in dynamic capability approach & development.

The earliest theories on dynamic capabilities connect their roots from an era in the 1920s, based on an extensive literature review conducted in the context of capabilities. The following relevant literature and their limitations are listed below the table. The literature to evaluate the understanding of the significance of capability in a dynamic environment. The analysis evidence connects the concept of capability initialised in an era of the 18th century by Knight(1921, p.268), discussing the capability to act in uncertain times based on opinions rather than knowledge. The limitations of this theory are underestimating the importance of knowledge. In continuation, in the 1950s, the categorisation of the workforce was at its peak based on individual abilities.

The resource-based view(RBV) theory by Rumelt (1984) has changed the approaches in strategic management about tangibles and intangibles attributes in gaining competitive advantage. Barney(1991) added an extension to the RBV model by identifying the VRIN framework later modified into VRIO components to evaluate the capabilities in terms of value, rare and imitability and organisation. The theory is a significant relationship between the internal attributes of the organisation to performances, but this is irrelevant in a dynamic environment embracing the digital transformation, specifically the financial industry environment.

From the year 1996 to 2007, the approaches had shifted from application to integration capacities of identified, researchers like Grant (1996, p.109); Teece (1997a 2007b); Eishenhardt et al.(2000) and Winters(2003) integrated the focussed on identifying the critical capabilities for specific outcomes towards dynamic capability approach, in Teece et al.(2007) dynamic capability framework conceptualising the foundational components "*SENSING, SEIZING and TRANSFORMING*" which highly prevalent in current dynamic environments.

The extensive literature review provides holistic approaches towards capability factors from the industrialisation era to the digital transformation need.

Table 5: Relevant literature on capability factor

Serial No.	Authors	Research Topic	Components	Limitations
1	Daniel Skog, D.A., Wimelius, H., Sandberg, J., (2018)	Digital Disruptions	research provide holistic view of integrates of digital transformation and digital innovations	Limitations in this research, required to empirical evidence of various case study to support the explanation of digital transformation process.
2	Dr. Florian Wiesböck & Prof. Thomas Hess (2018)	Understanding the Capabilities for Digital Innovations from a Digital Technology Perspective	Research study on digital innovation capability from digital transformation perspective.	As focused only on particular aspect which ignores the impact on other capabilities development
3	Adrian Yeow (2018)	Aligning with new digital strategy: A dynamic capabilities approach	Research study explains the complex integration of alignment process of capabilities with disruptions requirement	Study is adaptive version of David Teece's dynamic capability framework while focus on top - bottom integration of capabilities.
4	Thomas Hess et al., 2018	Digital transformation strategy making in pre-digital organizations: The case of a financial services provider	Research study of asset management companies in analysing the DT formulation and strategy	study is pre- digital investigation of strategy formation, analysis pre condition for setting the digital stage lack future perspective of successful adaptation and implementation.
5	Dr Tega Cosmos Akpobi (2017)	Dynamic Capabilities and Strategic Management: Explicating the Multi-Level Nature of Dynamic Capabilities	Research study is on micro foundations of dynamic capabilities in IT security industry based on David Teece's framework	Outcomes are replication of Teece's framework applied on IT security industry
6	Buell-Armstrong, Kate (2015)	Dynamic capabilities: the emperor's new clothes?	case study research underpinning the contribution of capabilities in firm's performance in digital ecosystem	Research is case study on Admiral plc, hence doesn't cover wider aspects of influence and integration of capabilities in case with digital transformations.
7	Karimi, J., Walter, Z., 2015.	The Role of Dynamic Capabilities in Responding to Digital Disruption: A Factor-Based Study of the Newspaper Industry	Has proposed the RPV constituents helping in manage digital disruptions.	Paper has fairly generalized only on newspaper industry and elements of RPV models.
8	Warner, Karl S.R. (2014)	Networking capability development in new venture internationalisation: a theory building approach.	Author has brought fresh thought process on network capability development by emphasizing on dynamic capability , networking and social capital	The study contributes in entrepreneurship and capability network framework on particular dynamic capability.
9	Kappelman et al., 2013	Key issues of IT organisations and their leadership	Key issues in leadership and IT in organisations	This MIS report is excellent research on impact and involvement of leadership in digital impact within organisation.
10	Westerman, G.; Calmédjane, C.; Bonnet, D.; Ferraris, P. & McAfee, A. (2011),	Digital Transformations : A road map for billion dollar organizations	Focused research on how manager can bring transformational phenomenon by focussed vision	Paper is process orientation of digital transformation implementation within organisation by focusing on key stakeholders within organisation
11	Barreto (2010)	Dynamic Capability: Review of past research and future agenda.	Review on past key literature on dynamic capability	Suggestions on gap identified variables and covariables of framework.
12	David Teece (2007)	Dynamic capability and strategic Management	New version of dynamic capability framework	Ongoing arguments on sets of dynamic capability cannot be competitive advantage.
13	Sidney Winters (2003)	Understanding the Dynamic Capability	Arguments on zero to ordinary capabilities of organisation	
14	Eisenhardt et al.,(2000)	Dynamic capabilities: What are they ?	Established the ordinary capabilities existence and creation of new capabilities.	focused on specific outcome
15	David Teece (1997)	Dynamic capabilities and strategic management	First version of capability framework, integrate, build and reconfigure the internal and external competencies	extended form of resource based view theory but consideration of set of dynamic capabilities create competitive advantage
16	Robert Grant (1996)	Towards knowledge based view	theory based on structure, process, behaviour and performance of firms	Focused on knowledge application disregard than knowledge creation.
17	Barney (1986)	advanced Resource based view	development of dominant approach of sustaining competitive advantage	Limitation of the theory due to static consideration
18	Rumelt (1984)	Resource based theory of enterprise		
19	Alchian and Demetz (1972)	Suggested the incentiviation rather than just knowledge asymmetries	research was build on how team co-operation as major capability	theory had limitations on organisation topology impacting on relationships within organisation
20	Era of 1930's, 40's and 50's	focussed on developed of industrialization, optimum utilization of manpower	formation on category of manpower expertise	
21	Schumpeter, 1934	Coined the term "Creative Destruction"	focussed on process, product innovation in context of capitalism	
22	Knight, 1921: 268	Economic theory	evidence of capability was described in earlier times on uncertainty, to act on opinions rather than just knowledge.	

2.8.4: Role of Dynamic capability framework in DT phenomenon.

There is a difference in perceptions & attributes of dynamic capability. As Teece, Pisano and Shuen(1997) argue on the link between capability and competitive advantage. While in Teece (2007, p.1341), updates argue that dynamic capabilities are the foundation of enterprise-level competitive advantage in rapid technological change regimes. This further breaks into component capabilities necessary to sustain superior enterprise performance in a highly dynamic environment(2007, p.1319). As per historical literature, "Schumpeter(1942) stated that competition fuelled by the introduction of new products and processes is a more powerful form of competition: Competition from the new commodity, the new technology, the new source of supply, the types of organisation- a competition which commands a decisive cost or quality advantage and which strikes not at the margins of the profits and the output of existing firms, but at their foundations and their very lives".

In dynamic capabilities, the scholars still feel murkier about the dynamic capabilities framework's content in Teece's model. As its emphasis on the firm's competitive advantage, the author strongly argues that competition will be an underpinning agenda to build foundational factors to create a competitive advantage. Schumpeter's (1942) proposed that dynamic competition is preferred in comparison to static competition.

To analyse dynamic competition driven by innovation, rapid response to change in creating new products, service level & market opportunities. While organisations are expected to identify new opportunities, markets, and change as per customers' perception through technology, top management's significant role in firms is to keep the organisation's innovation process with digital strategy suitably.

While another side of the competition, static competition reflects an Intellectual framework, basically in a static environment, where knowledge and expertise exist in the organisation. However, a lack of innovation can make the organisation vanish in a dynamic environment. Hence, firms with the digitalising strategy of achieving the marginal cost, which ultimately dies out or is taken over by dominant counterpart for expansion of plans, which is generally familiar in static competition, unveils the reasons for the company's failure to adapt to changes and innovation

2.8.5: Strength and Weakness: Dynamic Capability Framework

Dynamic capability is "the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments" (Teece et al.,2009). Winters(2003)stated that dynamic capabilities could be distinguished from ordinary capabilities, which is requisites for organisational, operational roles and processes, while Helfat et al.,(2007) describes the dynamic capabilities as the "Capacity of an organisation to create purposefully, extend or modify its resource-based".

According to David Teece(2009), dynamic capabilities are those capabilities integrated, reconfigured to meet the challenges created by technological changes, with a combination of three concepts from his framework(Figure no 13,p.76):

- (1) Sense and Shaping opportunities and threats.
- (2) Seize opportunities
- (3) Transforming through enhancing, reconfiguring the organisational intangible and tangible assets.

Dynamic capability originated from the Schumpeterian era, wherein the organisational competitive advantage was coined as "Creative destruction" of existing resources and alignment of new resources, gearing to develop dynamic capabilities (Teece et al., 1997). Dynamic capabilities framework is aimed to match external and internal resources in pursuit of changing business environment, hence considering this framework as the basis of developing the conceptual framework for this research study aiming to identify a critical and non-imitable set of capabilities for the creation of fluidity in a disruptive technological environment.

Dynamic capability framework has been a central theme for all researchers in strategic management, focusing on competencies and capability. The author considers the dynamic capability framework to develop the conceptual framework for the theoretical foundation. Although dynamic capability theory from David Teece et al.,(1997) was seminal work generated a steep rise in interest research of leading scholars on competence and capability development.

The author conducted a comprehensive review of available literature and articles, including the Master level and Doctoral thesis, which more than 16000 work conducted from 2007-2019 and identified the critical gap in dynamic capability framework (David Teece,2007). However, the dynamic capability framework to adapt to new technological advancements and gain competitive advantage but still lacks the ground specific factors associated with three factors of the framework "seizing, sensing and transforming". One of the meta-research stating that connecting dependency between organisational capability and competitive advantage is inconsistent (Pezeshkan et al.,2015), while Teece's framework explores the capabilities to leverage the competitive sustainability disruptive environment stating the capability and sustainability are consistent. Hence there is no acceptability of sustainability factors in both thesis research papers.

Schreyögg and Kliesch- Eberl (2007) proposed the consideration of "capability monitoring," a separate organisational function removed from the operational level and intended to observe both a firm's capabilities usage and evolution firm's external environment. Teece (2007) suggested that, in addition to the resource reconfiguring capability, two other "classes" of capabilities are considered: the capability to sense and shape opportunities and threats and seize opportunities. Although more indirectly, Makadok (2001) also undertook this approach by distinguishing two rent-creating abilities, those related to resource picking, which he associated with the RBV, and those related to capability building, which he associated with the dynamic capability framework.

Helfat et al., (2007) had proposed fitness and evolutionary as two yardsticks for calibrating capabilities. With groundwork on the preparation of digital adaptation journey, "fitness" is defined as the use of capability performance, while "evolutionary" refers to how well the capability enables the firm to achieve the goal (Teece,2009). The dynamic capability framework refers to firms adapting to transformation, but it more focusses on shaping up the capabilities according to evolutionary requirements. Jekel (2009) argues that its firm's process adjustments towards the external requirement for any change.

Earlier Teece et al.,(1997) defined dynamic capabilities as a firm's ability to integrate, build and reconfigure capabilities to address change. Zollo & Winter(2002) defines that dynamic capabilities, not just capabilities but process and routines. There has been an unsettled argument over dynamic capabilities creating the focus on a particular strategic word to functionalised by researchers Zahra et al.,(2006), on ability and Helfat (2007) on capacity aspect.

Based on capabilities and routines as referred by researchers from academia, dynamic capability constructive collaboration of ordinary and dynamic capabilities and capacities, this framework enables the organisations by identifying the micro-foundations of firms internally and externally towards adaption of change transformation, following are three foundation

- ***Sensing*** (Teece, 2014,p.328): Identifying the competitive trigger points within the ecosystem and competition trends, similarly applying this micro component with scenarios in the WMS sector, is highly relevant to analyse the evolutionary situation assess further development opportunities.
- ***Seizing***: mobilising resources to address the needs and opportunities to evaluate the value emerging (Teece, 2014, p.332). This phenomenon can be applied in the wealth management sector to recalibrate the identified resources (tangible and intangible) to analyse the value creation by integrating all processes to meet the customer expectations
- ***Transformation***: this micro foundation component of the DC framework, which refers to continuous renewal (Teece, 2014, p.332) of the firm, digital evolution is constant up-gradation which demands from organisation continuous assessing the development of capabilities. The dynamic capability perspective analysis is relevant to the research objective and viewpoint in engaging with this framework to develop conceptual development further.

2.9: Conceptual Framework

After a brief review of the relevant literature, a conceptual framework acts as a lens to access the identified gaps and build solutions and knowledge towards the problem. Considering the nature of the WMS business model, the combination of the Dynamic capability framework (Teece et al., 1997) and TAM (Davis, 1989) forms relevant components essential to investigate the scope of DT and its impact over a problematised area in traditional business settings.

This paragraph is about the justification of the integrative approach adopted by this research study for proposing the conceptual framework. Due to inadequate research on the WMS sector, there is a gap in defining the scope of DT specific to the chosen case study sector. The proposed conceptual framework represents the foundational elements: sensing, seizing, transforming and perceptions by various stakeholders. Their phenomenological approach to understanding their experiences will support exploring the scope and impact factors in the digital transitioning of traditional WMS firms.

According to Teece (2014), identifying or sensing critical external/ internal influences is critical in current scenarios in the financial industry due to its volatility and dynamic nature. The leaders and top management executives need to sense the critical factors and scope of impact over the existing business model. With relevance to available literature, there is a lack of a unified approach in understanding the objective of DT among the stakeholders. Thus, seizing beholds as the critical factor to explore through TAM components of perceived usefulness and perceived use of technology involving the relevant stakeholders, crucially important for research aim. According to Venkatraman (1994), technology can provide leverage to access expectations to improve processes and organisational value.

The conceptual framework stand out relevantly to explore the underlying perception of digital phenomena. The model will help identify why the established and matured WMS firms still struggle to seize the digital transformation in this process.

The human link with technology is significantly crucial in change transitioning. Hence the research thoroughly verified and recruited the participants with relevant experiences to potentialize their experiences and perceptions, as explained in the above paragraph following the conceptual framework. The complete information of research participants is provided in the appendix (Appx no- 4 p.251))

Figure 9: Conceptual Framework (Author's development)

According to Penrose theory (1959;1995), business firms are known by their product, services, and capabilities, and it is a constant repetitive process of identifying and rewiring focused internal capabilities. In alignment with Penrose theory to the research case study, firms must constantly review their capabilities to match up to their maturity with the speed of technology. However, there is inadequate information on variables in the configuration of capabilities in the traditional WMS sector.

At the same time, strategy refers to setting these organisational capabilities into action based on its set objectives. According to Powell & Micallef(1999), a study revealed that only technology could not produce sustainable performances. The companies need to leverage intangible aspects like human talent, flexible culture, ethical leadership and integration approach, which resulted in an agreement with Chuang &Lin,(2015) research on one hundred nineteen companies in Taiwan, enhanced positivity and value creation by positive companies by enhancing internal service capability and innovation.

According to the literature, there is a vague sense in early detection of factors that later compels the traditional firms to enforce the changes into their legacy routines leveraging the technology. The forced changes lead to resistance and inertia elements; hence this conceptual framework is paramount in understanding the perceptions of involved stakeholders and reasons.

2.10: Summary

Chapter two provided an extensive review of the literature from academic and practitioners' understandings towards the DT phenomenon. The review of the available literature resulted in the chosen case-study sector is under-researched in context to stakeholder perceptions towards embracing the DT. Although to a certain degree, business consulting firms are constantly researching the digital movements of traditional WMS firms digital journey. The literature review extracted a few critical elements linked with any business organisations' objective of transforming from the current state to a digitally transformed one. However, due to inadequate research on the WMS sector, there is a gap in building concrete insight about the relevance of identified elements suitability to the problem area. Thus, the researchers used the problematization approach to present the existing scenario within the sector.

The existing literature provides a blanket understanding of the DT as a phenomenon but is unclear on various aspects like culture, constraints of leadership, process integration and alignment issues that do not fit current issues in the case study sector. The different theories highlight the linkage of these factors in creating an ecosystem for digital change, but inadequate hindsight over the relevance of these reasons in traditional firms' derailment of digital initiatives. Hence the summarization of identified literature supported in proposing the conceptual model for this research.

The research bridges the gap by exploring the perceptions and variables critically linked with adapting the digital transformation successfully by traditional WMS firms. Hence this research is exploratory, adopting the interpretivism paradigm with semi-structured interviews for data collection methods, discussed briefly in the following research methodology chapter.

The next chapter discusses the research methods, design and data collection tools and justifies the adopted research methodology.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3. Introduction

Chapter three presents the research methodology and designs that adopted the conceptual framework to investigate the perspectives of the main stakeholders towards the DT, to understand the extent and impact of the DT in chosen study sector. This chapter discusses in detail the philosophical research stances, paradigms and interpretative methodologies adopted for further exploration.

The research is exploratory, and inductivism forms the philosophical stance for research and the interpretivism paradigm employed for this research study. The semi-structured interviews were employed for empirical data collection. The stakeholder analysis was conducted to potentialize the maximum data extraction themes from relevant internal and external stakeholders. Thus, the research adopted the purposive and snowball sampling techniques, and all these elements were structured into the research onion.

Chapter three structure is as follows: Section 3.1 to 3.5 explains and justifies selecting research methodologies and philosophies. It discusses the relevance of selected philosophical stances and research paradigms. It further explains the significance of chosen research methods and their relevance with the conceptual framework. Section 3.6 to 3.10 explains the chosen inductive methods, semi-structured interviews for the empirical data collection. Highlights and explains reasons for the change from the initial plan of data collection and the impact of the Covid pandemic over the data collection process. Section 3.11 to 3.14 discusses the thematic analysis tool used to analyse gathered empirical data from four groups of stakeholders from the WMS sector. This section briefly outlines the ethical principles followed for the research conduct and the reliability and validity factors of research.

3.1: Philosophical assumptions in the research

Philosophical assumptions have a significant role compared to other research methodology concepts, as they drive all processes required to conduct research further. Three philosophical assumptions act as foreground in selecting methods to choose relevant research designs and data collection methods tools.

Ontology: Eriksson & Kovalainen (2008) define “Ontology” as the existence and relationships between people, society, and the world. At the most general definition, ontology is a view of “what is reality”. Although Searle(1995) suggested that reality in the physical world has an objective, the ontology and social world have an ontologically subjective existence mode. Easterby-Smith et al.,(2002) argue that the philosophical debate between objectivism and subjectivism. Ontology in this research confirms the diverse realities existing, confirming the researcher’s belief that the nature of reality is subjective and objective.

Thus, applying the ontological angle towards the aim of research evaluates DT’s extent in the WMS business ecosystem. The perception of how, what and why of the DT phenomenon in the context of the WMS sector was explored. Thomas & Hardy (2011) emphasised that harnessing the resistance to change focuses on the benefit of organisations rather than looking for ways to eliminate resistance. Hence with these underlying concepts, this research helps explore the main stakeholders’ perspectives from their experiences in the digital transformation phenomenon.

Epistemology: The knowledge shaping the ontology into questions like “what and how to do the reality”. According to Burrell & Morgan (2017) and Saunders et al. (2009), epistemology represents the assumptions about knowing what constitutes proper, legitimate knowledge and how we can communicate knowledge to others. Hence the epistemology of this research is underlying, mainly within the constructivism approach to explore the understanding of reality on the digital transformation phenomenon. The constructivism approach is based on reality taking shape from individuals experiences and perceptions.

Epistemology of the research is understood through perceived knowledge. This research explores the underlying reasons for the complexities of DT adaption. Hence in specific to this research, the approach describes the interpretive philosophy.

Axiology: According to Guba & Lincoln (1994), the two defined characteristics of philosophical assumptions, “ontology and epistemology”, are primary directives in determining the research design. However, Heron & Reason (1996) suggested nature of value is intrinsically significant in research, and Heron (1996, p.11) argues “ the values are guiding reasons for all human actions and values as the basis for making judgements about what research is conducted and how we are doing it.” Thus, philosophical approaches are guidelines for setting the proper research ethics in principal with value decisions in conducting research. The research follows three principles of ethical conduct of research by Diener & Crandall (1978), briefly described in further paragraph.

- *Lack of informed consent*
- *Invasion of privacy*
- *The possibility of deception*

Axiology refers to an outline framework of understanding the concepts of right and wrong behaviour in research (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017). The following table below illustrates the philosophical stance of this research study.

Table 6: Philosophical stance of the research study

Ontology (nature of reality or being)	Epistemology (what constitutes acceptable knowledge)	Axiology (role of values)	Typical methods
Interpretivism			
Complex, rich Socially constructed through culture and language Multiple meanings, interpretations, realities Flux of processes, experiences, practices	Theories and concepts too simplistic Focus on narratives, stories, perceptions and interpretations New understandings and worldviews as contribution	Value-bound research Researchers are part of what is researched, subjective Researcher interpretations key to contribution Researcher reflexive	Typically, inductive. Small samples, in-depth investigations, qualitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be interpreted
Postmodernism			
Nominal Complex, rich Socially constructed through power relations Some meanings, interpretations, realities are dominated and silenced by others Flux of processes, experiences, practices	What counts as 'truth' and 'knowledge' is decided by dominant ideologies Focus on absences, silences and oppressed/ repressed meanings, interpretations and voices Exposure of power relations and challenge of dominant views as contribution	Value-constituted research Researcher and research embedded in power relations Some research narratives are repressed and silenced at the expense of others Researcher radically reflexive	Typically, deconstructive – reading texts and realities against themselves In-depth investigations of anomalies, silences and absences Range of data types, typically, qualitative methods of analysis
Pragmatism			
Complex, rich, external 'Reality' is the practical consequences of ideas Flux of processes, experiences and practices	Practical meaning of knowledge in specific contexts 'True' theories and knowledge is those that enable successful action Focus on problems, practices and relevance Problem solving and informed future practice as contribution as contribution	Value-driven research Research initiated and sustained by researcher's doubts and beliefs Researcher reflexive	Following research problem and research question Range of methods: mixed, multiple, qualitative, quantitative, action research Emphasis on practical solutions and outcomes

3.2: Research Philosophy

According to Creswall(2009), it is crucial that before selecting the research methods and design, it is appropriate to select philosophy which is the foundation for further research. Edmondson & McManus (2007,p. 1173) quote “research philosophy as the involvement of many forward and backward movements in research.” Philosophy is the researcher’s assumptions that serve as the foundation for research design (Saunders et al.,2015).

This research study is exploratory and aims to investigate the extent of DT by exploring the experiences and perspectives of the research participants in the DT phenomenon. The author’s earlier background in the WMS sector is a motivational factor (briefed in the next section of this chapter) to understand the underlying complexities in embracing the DT and its allied environment. The synthesis of factors outlined in chapter two from past literature is a contributory influence on this research. It provides the lack of clarity and relationship between identified factors and their relevance to the current scenario in chosen traditional Wealth Management Services firms.

Although earlier discussed factors are holistically critical in the given context. However, the regulatory, competitive service model and the management factors make the WMS sector distinct and dynamic from other business sectors.

However, due to inadequate outlooks and directives in this context of the WMS industry, this research adopted the problematisation approach. The reality by problematisation aspect enables the flexibility of research in investigating the phenomenon (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011; Sen, 2018). The primary philosophical stance is epistemology, ontology, and axiology (Heron, 1996; Eriksson & Kovalainen 2008; Saunders et al.2009; Koch et al.2015; Burrell & Morgan, 2017). The followings critical approaches used in IS researches are positivism, interpretive, pragmatic. In quantitative and qualitative research, the practical approaches adopted are either positivist or interpretive (Bryman,2008; Saunders et al.,2009; Gill & Johnson,2010; Flick, 2011). The epistemological stance in research endorses an inductive approach to investigate the research questions and follow qualitative empirical data collection tools.

• **Interpretivism:**

The interpretivist approach concentrates on studying the consciousness and object of direct experiences, seeking to understand the phenomenon in a specific context. According to Terre et al.,(1999), the research process has three significant dimensions: *ontology*, *epistemology* and *methodology* that defines the research's nature. According to Saunders et al.,(2007), Interpretivism is subjective philosophy about creating new meanings, enhancing a rich and clear understanding of the phenomenon in organisational realities from interpreting the feelings and experience of human beings lived in that event.

The significant factors related to "interpretivism" are individual's participation, collaboration, and engagement (Henning, Van Rensburg, & Smit, 2004). In interpretive philosophy, the researcher distinguishes the themes and meanings of social actions specific to research (Carr & Kemmis, 1986, p.88). Interpretivism strongly promotes understanding the humans in our role as social actors. This approach advocates the differences of researching a different set of people rather than physical objects, and the "social actors" is a metaphor used for participants in the study at various levels to understand the phenomenon and interpreting

their perspective (Saunders et al.,2012) There is various research paradigm considered before proceeding with the final version of research philosophies for this research study.

As interpretive philosophy constructs social actors in the research process leading to subjective perceptions, while Hennink et al.,(2011) say social reality may change and create multiple perspectives as human perspectives which are subjective. Robson (2002) argues that these subjective experiences, beliefs, and individual understanding fundamentals interpretivism philosophy. In comparison to positivism, Interpretivism has a flexible framework and more adoptive research design as the significant aim is to capture human understanding, experiences and perceptions on phenomena.

According to Carson et al.,(2001), researchers must perceive the research context to understand realism. However, as per Neuman(2002) and Edirisingha(2012), the researcher should be the observer and interpret participants' meaning rather than generalisation. Thus, the researcher's background adds to a critical place in the interpretivism approach. As indicated earlier, exploratory nature, the knowledge/reality required to be known through the individuals from their experiences, perceptions and formed perspectives specific to the context. The assessment of some key literature in relevance to the theme of this research indicates the adoption of similar epistemological and philosophical choices in approach and research design. The research aims to seek perspectives based on human observation and experiences, and individual interpretation of events and circumstances in real situations are relevant to understand the underlying phenomena (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

Table 7: Key research literature adopted the similar qualitative interpretivism approach

Author	Topic	Adopted philosophy	Date collection Method
Warner & Wager.,(201	Building dynamic capabilities for digital transformation: An ongoing process of strategic renewal	Qualitative Interpretive research	In-depth Interviews
Porfirio et al., (2021)	Leadership characteristics and digital transformation	Qualitative comparative analysis	fsQCA
Chanas et al.,(2019)	Digital transformation strategy making in pre-digital organizations: The case of a financial services provider	Qualitative Interpretive research	In-depth Interviews
Fitzgerald et al (2014)	Embracing digital technology: A new strategic imperative	Qualitative Interpretive research	Semi structured interviews
Sebastian et al., (2017)	Embracing digital technology: A new strategic imperative	Qualitative Interpretive research	Semi structured interviews
Kohne (2017)	It's not just about technology: The people side of digitization	Qualitative research method	Interviews
Hess et al., (2016)	Options for formulating a digital transformation strategy.	Qualitative Interpretive research	Interviews

Thus, in context, this research aims to investigate the perspectives of main stakeholders on digital transformation phenomena specific to the WNS sector. The interpretive research is recommended, as it captures participants' personal experiences about the process and business model change that occurred during this strategic transformational shift and how the business identifies the core capabilities required to recalibrate or customize for its digital goal.

Positivism: The philosophy of positivism is generally viewed as a branch of science that focuses on the importance of observable reality searching for regularities and causal relationships in data to create law-like generalisations like those produced by scientists (Gill & Johnson,2010). Positivism philosophy leads to produce accurate and credible data by using existing theories to develop hypotheses. These hypotheses will be tested again in further research, concluding that the quantifiable observations will lend themselves to statistical analysis. (Saunders et al., 2009, p.135)

Bryman (2008, p.13) summarises some assumptions of the positivism approach:

- *The only phenomenon confirmed by the senses can warrant knowledge.*
- *Theories used to generate hypotheses that can test and all explanations of laws to be assessed (Deductivism)*
- *Knowledge can produce by collecting facts that provide the basis of laws (Inductivism)*

However, there is a significant argument in positivist philosophy that research should be value- free. Gill & Johnson (2011) explains that a positivist approach should follow the statistical analysis as it favours the scientific evidence, but not exclusively to result towards quantitative research methods considering the research objective and generalisable findings. Hence, the empirical data is less likely to produce rich, complex and practical views of organisational fusions. While the author concludes that this research is an exploratory study, the research emphasises individuals' experiences, behaviours, and understandings. Hence positivism is not favourable for this research.

Pragmatism: Kelemen & Rumens (2008) emphasise that the relevant concept only supports the action. This philosophy of reality considering the instruments of thoughts, action and their practical consequences of specific contexts. As theories, concept ideas and research findings are not in an abstract form but realism. The research initiated the problem and contributed practical solutions for future practice. The researcher drives the reflexive inquiry process initiated by doubt and something wrong (Elkjaer & Simpson, 2011). The researchers' Van de Ven & Poole(2005) states that the stance understands that the different positions can complement each other without choosing any specific position and denying others. Pragmatism is about adopting different types of knowledge and methods. Pragmatists approach interprets the world in many ways, that no single point of view can ever give the entire picture and that there may be multiple realities. According to Saunders et al.,(2009, p.109), "it is possible to adapt the combination of all three epistemological stances formulating into Pragmatism."

Hence pragmatism is not likely appropriate for this research study. The interpretative approach perfectly suits this research to fundamentally understand the strategic perspectives and the behaviour in embracing the digital transformation.

Table 8: Philosophical stance of research.

Assumption Type	Interpretivist	Positivist	In context of this research study
Ontology (Nature of world) (Reality)	Nominal access to world Multiples realities (Relativism) Proactive	Have real access to world one true reality(universalism) Reactive	1. Reality of transformation in world. 2. Exploring the reality through direct interactions with stakeholders. 3. Many social realities existing within organisations varying as per every individual's experience and knowledge, practices, interactions and feelings.
Epistemology (Assumptions about the knowledge & relationships)	Opinions & Narratives Individual, context and specific Perceived Knowledge	Facts Numbers Law like generalisations Possibility of achieving hard objective knowledge	1. Interviews and personal mode of data collections. 2. Actions decided based on interpretations of researcher after interactive sessions with interviewee. 3. Contributions to knowledge.
Axiology (What is the role of values in research)	Understanding Value bound integral	Explanation Value free detachment	Researcher acknowledges the research is value laden.
Methodology (Focus oriented & Researcher's role)	Use of pre-knowledge and understanding is essential Allows feelings and emotions (Subjective)	Rational, verbal and logical approach Clear demarcation between reason and feeling.	Researcher collects data through semi structured interviews

3.3: Researcher's background

The researcher's role is recognised as an interpretive researcher. Goldkuhl(2012) explains interpretivism principles connect researcher and practitioner. In this context, the prior knowledge or experience will be beneficial as the research progresses.

In this research context, the author's earlier experiences in the WMS sector as part of a change management programme stands as a motivation factor in pursuing the research, further exploring the research design & methodology for the optimum outcome to answer the formulated research questions. The WMS firms are resourceful in terms of investments, talents, and capabilities, but they still fail to embrace the change to achieve their DT goal. I wanted to explore those reasons or factors that obstruct their digital goals with their own experiences and observations. The strategic approaches adopted by top management are critical in creating the push or pull strategy for customer loyalty and behaviour, which involves various factors like culture, leadership, alignment strategy of resources and capability within the organisational ecosystem. Hence, traditional WMS firms constantly renew and calibrate the newer capabilities to adopt disruptive technologies to meet the expectations and sustainability in the competitive environment. Having worked earlier in this active environment, the author understands the dynamic settings of this sector and their sensitivity to external factors vibration. The banking and financial services sector are the most digital sectors in every economy of the world. Although the FSI sectors are dynamic in adapting to technological changes, due to legacy and silo working culture, interdepartmental fail to integrate synergies between front, middle, and back-office processing departments. The sector faces compelling internal and external pressures to digitalise the work processes for value creation. However, this disruption of the work- processes without clarity about vision creates friction within traditional settings. The large database of customers with trust-based relationships managed by financial advisors/wealth managers is still the competitive advantage of these traditional firms. Now, the foray of Fintechs in the wealth management sectors is disrupting the traditional model and influencing the investment expectations of customers.

Nevertheless, every business organisation is susceptible to challenges and constraints in embracing the digital change transformations in such conditions, which are currently inadequate literature to understand the DT's related issues. The introspection of digital readiness and maturity aspects is critical in aligning the resources towards the DT goals. The DT phenomenon is like a jigsaw puzzle unless every puzzle piece is integrated. There is the scope of resistance, inertia which can derail the investment, resources and customer trust factors in the traditional WMS sector.

My background experience of the FS industry and being a part of change management proved vital in developing the mind mapping in line with the literature review (Appx 5. p. 251). It proved beneficial to develop a research strategy to explore the further stages in the research in meeting the research aim.

3.4: Justification of adopted interpretive philosophy

In continuation of a discussion about research philosophies in earlier paragraphs, this section justifies adopting the interpretivism paradigm for this research. Following are reasons for selecting this philosophy: In light of the research aim, is to explore the existing reality, not to create a new reality. Thus, the understanding the dominant reality and perceptions on existing phenomena in traditional WMS firms embracing the digital transformational change. However, the perceptions, experiences, feelings and associated emotions cannot be quantified or measured. Hence the positivist approach is irrelevant to the nature of this research. The critical theory philosophy depicts the influence of power relations in constructing knowledge and reality. Hence, critical theory is eliminated as it is not suitable for this research context. Lastly, pragmatism philosophy generally adopts all three epistemological stances to view the entire picture as pragmatist view interprets the world in many ways, so paradigm believes of no single way to view the problem. Hence it favours for mixed methodological approach; thus, this is not relevant to this research philosophy.

Hence the qualitative approach is best suited for the research approach, exploring the elements of influence and compelling factors, which impediments the WMS firm's digital embracement process. The qualitative study is adopted to meet the requirements and selection of data, confluence with the challenging research questions the adoption of the "Hermeneutic phenomenological" philosophy in evaluating the complexity of DT. Hence, the author's interpretations and understanding of the topic cannot be a bracket in this research study. At the same time, Smith (1973) supported Heidegger's philosophy by stating that we and our activities are always "in the world" our being in the world. So we do not study our activities by bracketing the world. Instead, we interpret our activities and the meaningful things with contextual relations to the things of our world.

Based on discussed aspects above, the research will be adopting Heidegger's Hermeneutic philosophy with interpretations as Heidegger's phenomenology provides the methodological directives for qualitative seeking to explore the lived experiences and perceptions on the phenomena from identified strategic stakeholders' groups from various WNS organisations.

3.5: Research design considerations

According to Yin (1994), the research design refers to the researcher's logical sequence of framework to address the specific research questions. It is critical to choose the appropriate design followed in further research to collect empirical data and analyse it.

According to Saunders et al.,(2007), "the main components of research design are research purpose, approach, research strategy and data collection. Mouton (1996, p.175) defines the research design as "a plan, structure and execute" the research to maximise the "validity of the findings". The research design is a master plan, briefing each phase from the theoretical literature review as a foundational phase for data inquiry from the qualitative approach. The research design refers to Saunders et al.,(2007) systematic framework to fulfil the aim and objectives of this research study. Following are key elements explained in further paragraphs.

3.5.1: Research Purpose

The three categories of research purpose are exploratory, explanatory, and descriptive. Robson(2002) explains that exploratory research is about finding answers to “what and how questions and exploring the phenomena through an understanding of the problem and looking for new insights and perspectives (p.59). Two significant research designs are qualitative and quantitative (Saunders et al.,2009; Bryman & Bell, 2011). The exploratory process is followed with qualitative research methodology using interviews and focus groups for empirical data collection. The qualitative research methodology includes exploring and understanding the individual and group interpretation of social or human problems compared to quantitative research. The second category is explanatory research, which favours the statistical methods and knows hypothesis testing. Generally, quantitative research methodology is associated with this approach. The third is a descriptive research methodology, and this research type depicts the accurate description of the phenomena in the research question (Robson,2002), which generally favours a mixed-method research methodology approach either one of them.

In line with the conceptual framework of research (p. 90), the existing literature has explained a few factors which can be critical in determining the extent and scope of digital transformation phenomena with the traditional WMS sector scenario. However, there is still scope to explore the relevant reasons for derailing the efforts of organisations in embracing the DT. Hence from all discussions on choosing the relevant research methodology, there is a clear definition that the research is exploratory, which explores the factors in the form of reasons causing the impediments in scope and impact of DT in specific to traditional WMS firms.

Saunders et al.,(2016) stated that the researcher’s role depends on gaining physical access to participants, building rapport, and being considerate towards access to their data.

Empirical data collection methods in qualitative research are non-standardised to flexible to change the course of questions that emerged during the research journey, which needs to be naturalistic and interactive. Hence this research adopted the non-probability techniques of sampling technique.

3.5.2: Research Approach

Bryman & Bell (2011, p.11) and Saunders et al.,(2009.p.141-146) stated that literature defines three approaches, a) deductive, b) Inductive, c) abductive. The research approach is generally directing the whole research design. Some studies suggest that interpretive research attracts the inductive approach more in line (EasterbySmith et al.,2008), and he also argues that knowledge of different research traditions enables to adapt the research design. Carson et al.,(2001) say inductive and deductive reasoning to be balanced, particularly interpretive research is a purely inductive research approach. While Saunders et al.,(2007) inductive researchers, do not study a subject without competent knowledge about researching the area.

- **Deductive approach:**

This approach theory is tested through the data, which often leads to the formation of the hypothesis (Mantere & Ketokivi, 2013, p.71). Due to its structured nature without flexibility, this approach is often used for quantitative research. Thus deductive approach will be unsuitable for this research.

- **Inductive approach:**

Bryman & Bell(2011) stated that the inductive approach's primary purpose is to create the theory from the data, precisely opposite to the deductive approach. The inductive approach helps create a better understanding of humans' meanings attached to events, hence its non-statistical approach. Saunders et al.,(2009) approve by stating that the theory produces from data collected and measures. Blaikie(2006, p. 83-84) claimed that research should generalise after seeing similar trends emerging.

- **Abductive approach:**

The abduction approach is a combination of both the above approaches, deductive and inductive approaches. Saunders et al.(2009, p.145) confirm that collecting the data to explore the phenomenon, identify themes and explain the patterns, generate a new or modify the existing theory, which again tested through the additional data collection. Hence this subsequent collection of data leads to the possibility of forming many probabilities.

The research constructs the connection in pursuit to create knowledge-based on individuals experiences. Hence, there is no scope for exploring the subjective experiences bound to change each data collection. Thus, this approach will be irrelevant for this research study. Based on below mentioned significant differences between inductive and deductive approaches. The epistemological, ontological stances of this research theme are well supported through an inductive approach.

Table 9: Research Approach

Inductive Approach	Deductive Approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research is gaining an understanding of the meaning of human perceptions to event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on scientific principles
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection of empirical data through qualitative methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection of empirical data through quantitative methods
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A more flexible structure to permit changes of research emphasis as research emphasising on the progression of research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of controls to ensure the validity of data, highly structured approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less concerned with the need to generalise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The necessity to select samples of enough size in order to generalise conclusions

The research design aims to gather data from primary and secondary sources through non-probability methods to explore DT's perspectives and their associated maturity and readiness factors. The outcomes will contribute to developing the solution in the form of a framework for the smooth embracing of digital transformation.

The first two formulated research questions are descriptive and exploratory, attempting to assess the challenges & constraints and identify the critical success factor. The third objective is to contribute the framework for analysing their capabilities requirement. These are significant research study ideologies focussing on the inductive approach to develop the themes from thematic analysis of empirical data. Moreover, the Inductive method usually adopts the bottom-up approach focusing on emerging patterns from data gathered on the following factors: perceptions, robustness in process description, and behaviours in crucial phases. This research adopts the inductive approach to explore the themes for critical connections with context and recommend the framework.

3.5.3: Research Strategy

The research strategy defined the methodological link between research philosophy and the following methods to collect and analyse data (Denzin & Lincoln 2011). The research design selection was decided on the availability of time, knowledge depth and philosophical assumptions adopted for the research (Macalintal & Chepkasova,2017).

3.5.3.1 Phenomenological research paradigm

Phenomenological research is interviewing the right set of people about the phenomenon in their situations, focusing on individuals understanding, experiences, feelings and behaviours, interpreting through the emerging patterns.

Husserl(1970) stated that phenomenological research pursues description rather than explanation perspective free from hypotheses or preconceptions. According to Husserl (1970), it is a transcendental study of phenomenology can be done by bracketing or reducing one's judgements. The earlier researchers have described phenomenological reduction or bracketing (Jones,1975; Polkinghorne, 1983; Osborne,1994; Klein & Westcott, 1994).

The bracketing is defined as setting aside personal evidence, biases, preconceived notions about the research topic and including the earlier research, findings, and theories about the research topic. While Heidegger (1889-1976), a German philosopher and student of Husserl, had branched out from opinions and ideology of Husserl, Heidegger's opinion on phenomenological research is lived out interpretively in the world, hence bracketing or settings aside out emotions and understanding is not possible forming Hermeneutic phenomenological research.

Hermeneutic process: Interpretive process is an iterative process moving back and forth from pieces of observations (text) to the social phenomenon to construct the themes and theory based on the individual's experiences of participants. These researchers' observations will help iterations between the understanding the phenomenon and observations until saturation is reached, basically till no yielding of any new themes into the context of research data analysis. The following figure illustrates the research design for this research.

Figure 10: The research design

3.6: Data Collection

The vital & practical part of research is the data collection method, and this exploratory research adopted qualitative research methodology with direct interviews as a tool for empirical data collection method. The novel Covid pandemic had a substantial impact on the data collection process. Before the Covid outbreak, the original plan included direct interviews and focus group discussions with relevant profile and experienced executives from various positions in the digital-change mechanisms process within four established Wealth management firms. The identified profiles included a few well-known leaders from the WMS sector, known for their digital leadership capabilities in steering the DT change management.

In December 2019, I began the semi-structured interviews with executives from the selected organisation following all ethical processes and approvals, concurrently trying to reach other participants for confirmation on interview dates and venues. The snow-ball technique was adopted to get references from participated executives. Until March 2020, I would conduct only eight direct interviews of various executives while the Covid-pandemic lockdown restrictions were imposed with immediate stay-at-home order in the UK, disrupting the data collection process.

Suppose in the situation of no outbreak of the Covid pandemic. In that case, the empirical data collection could have resulted in a comprehensive inside-out view exploration of how DT has impacted the digital shift of the traditional business model and supply chain by involving other various functional layers, including the supply chain. With uncertainty and a chaotic situation within financial services sectors across the UK due to remote working culture due to lockdown situation. It accelerated the use of technology for virtual and remote working practices, proving a critical step towards changing the mindset shift towards digital transformation. However, the virtual and remote working situation was an obstruction for conducting the research study to get access of executives for data collection due to new culture of remote working resulted in the decline of participation interest by many senior executives and lost many contacts of middle management executives due to no access to their personal contact details as they had shared only office direct lines numbers. Few participants requested to postpone their interviews for a few more months ahead.

Due to the uncertain situation, the data collection phase stretched till July 2020 (Started from December 2019). The researcher had to reiterate the process of identifying the potential stakeholders for research interviews through professional online platforms like LinkedIn. Thus, the research strategy had to be changed to focus on relevant experience profiles from the wealth services sector instead of a case study of only four WMS firms. Data collection focuses on executives with relevant DT experience from the WMS firm in strategic functional roles involved in strategizing, work process changes and capability development. The stakeholder analysis framework was developed to identify the right profile before reaching out to confirm participation interest.

Thus, the phenomenological paradigm was adopted to explore stakeholders' understanding, perceptions, and behaviours in volatile and constantly changing situations. Strategy for qualitative exploratory research involves direct interviews to capture their behaviour and expressions while interviewing sessions. There are three types of qualitative interviews:

Structured interviews: These interviews are generally focussed on standard questions wherein the same questions, the same sequence of questions similar to survey methods, are inappropriate for the phenomenological adopted approach of the research.

Semi-structured interviews: preferred tool of data collection of this research as despite great scope of open-ended questions still, it is defined and provides the focus for an interview. Saunders et al. (2009, p.320) describe that semi-structured interviews provide clarity and help identify organisational nature and interrelations to research questions. Semi-structured interviews are open-ended questions. Patton(1980) classified these interviews further into informational conversational, general and stood open-ended. The primary data was gathered from the narratives of interviews by various stakeholders. The secondary data supplemented are company reports, annual statements, white papers, datasheets, and various regulatory bodies reports. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with diverse groups within multiple organisations. The detailed structure of sampling explained another part of the research proposal.

This research study will be using a mono-method qualitative study process such as Semi-structured interviews is a single data collection technique as unstructured interviews may not fixate on the research theme as may loose on critical issues to be addressed during the session. Hence the semi-structured interview technique will be adopted in this research.

Unstructured Interviews: These interviews are in-depth discussions but without any pre-determined directives on-topic, not necessary focussed on any particular issues or topic. Thus, this approach of unstructured interviews cannot be aligned with this research objectives.

3.7: Stakeholder Analysis

In order to get answers to the research questions, it is critical to focus on the relevant case study firms and participants to maximise the outcomes from their interviews sessions. Hence the research opted for stakeholder analysis. The literature review outcome generally focused on stakeholders' perspectives (Mole et al. 2008; 2011; Kim, 2014).

Financial firms operating in dynamic environments need to be flexible in business models to meet customer expectations and manage sustainability. Hence, the line of services is vast and diverse operations managing the different segments of customers, hence required to analyse the few coordinates to identify the relevant case study firms for this research. Following are coordinates grid points used for shortlisting the relevant firms and executives backgrounds.

Table 10: Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder	Mapping Coordinates	Reason of inclusion
The Wealth management firms	An investment strategy in DT Length of business in the UK Markets Size and structure of the organisation	Relevant case study firms to identify the executives with appropriate experience for empirical data collection
Senior Management executives: Directors, CEO, Managing partner	Experience, functions, education background, leadership roles	Key decisional role in DT adaption and implementation
Middle Management executives: Wealth Manager, Relationship manager	Experience, role & duties, educational background	Catalyst role in digital strategy and planning, customer interactions and accountability
External DT consultants: DT experts from consulting companies.	Experience in the field of the WMS, expertise in digital transformational implementation	Critical role in organisation's digital transformation strategy. Linking strategy into action
Customers: Clients investing through the wealth management services firms	An investment portfolio with the Wealth Management Firm	Understanding the DT phenomenon through their perspectives from lived experiences

1. Coordinates for mapping organisations

- length of business activities in the UK market
- last seven years of history on organisation's initiatives in digital change space.
- Size and structure of organisations
- The digital investments in the last five years of the WMS firms

2. Analysis of the impact of digital transformation on stakeholder's role.

- From the current scenario and industry reports, DT change has a high impact on strategic and functional roles within the WMS firms. In order to evaluate the impact of digital change over the dimensions of these job roles, thus it is crucial to involve participants from various functional and strategic roles within these organisations. So, these executives are involved in the digital change process implementation. It is essential to analyse the scope of functional changes due to digital disruptions in customer relationship management, business model change and sustainability strategies. This will provide directives for the semi-interview process to explore the swift role changes in the context of DT adoption.

3. Access to diverse stakeholder groups.

- Thus, in this phase of research gained an understanding of technology that is just a medium to imply the changes. However, the major shift is in the culture and mindset approach within organisations, the integration process led by the leadership team in assessing the existing resources and capabilities for achieving the firm's set objective.
- According to existing literature, the DT is a top-down approach as well as it requires a horizontal and vertical cascade of communication but generally, in practice, it horizontal flow (Chanies & Hess,2016). Thus, it is significant to comprise the strategic decision-makers, top management and leaders in roles like CEO, CTO, CDO or Managing director and Partner, the relationship/ wealth managers followed within external DT consultants, and finally with the customers for empirical data collection to understand their perceptions and constraints.
- **Middle Management:** Middle-management executives in the WMS organisation comprise functional front office, back office, and middle-office departments. However, this research aims to reach out to the front-office roles like wealth managers, financial advisors, or relationship managers to explore their lived experiences and perceptions of digital change navigation.

- This group of participants are middle management executives directly in contact with their customers squarely. Thus, the involvement of these executives in research data collection is significant in comprehending the DT phenomenon.
- **Technology experts (external digital consultants):** As per the HBR(2019) report on the FSI sector, DT has been the main concern for top management and senior executives as 70% of firms do not meet the established DT objectives. Around \$900billion investment was wasted till 2019 on DT initiatives(HBR, 2019). Thus, traditional WMS firms seek external technology and strategy expert consultants to avoid further investment wastages, rolling out new revenue avenues, and managing the digital change in the traditional business ecosystem. These external management consultants support the operations efficiently by providing expert knowledge in developing the customized strategy and implementation planning for a smooth swift of the legacy process into the agile process. External DT consultants are critically significant in elevating the digital culture with the integration of traditional values. Hence it utmost necessary to include their perspectives in the data collection as they are an integral part of the change process within the organisation. Hence, their perspectives on the DT phenomenon is very significant in further research analysis.
- **Customers Stakeholder group:** According to a Deloitte survey (UK Finance/Wealth Management Association, Feb 2020), A potential 2.2 million investors use the Wealth management services for their taxation, retirement planning, and investments, including all age groups.
The central focus of digital change is to catering the customer expectations. Hence their outlook is equally essential in understanding the change phenomenon and underlying reasons for the shift in their behaviour. The perception of the DT related change in customer service and its impact from the customer stakeholder is critical to understand the relationship with traditional firms attempt towards value creation leveraging digital technology and customers' reasons for shift behaviour and expectations.

Following the table illustrates the profile of each stakeholder selected for the data collection of the research study.

Table 11: Profile of research participants from four stakeholder groups

Role	Experience	Industry	Location	Relevant experience
CTO/CDO/CEO'S Director	10-20 years	WMS	London	YES
Mid-Management Level	10-15 years	WMS	London	YES
External Consultant	7-20 years	BFSI sector	London	Yes
Customers	Five years of investing experience using wealth management services for investment purposes			

3.8: Piloting

The pilot study is an initial process conducted to ensure each step is designed for empirical data collection of a research study. The piloting is conducted in a smaller group or with research participants to understand the feasibility of research protocols for the main research. The pilot study was conducted twice with two separate groups. Initially, the pilot study was conducted with three participants from different layers of the same WMS firm, which resulted in early saturation of themes in just three participants due to the factors like culture, leadership and similar objectives. The further evaluation of early saturation identified the reason for being in a similar culture, work processes under the same leadership yielding the same wave-length in creating the same perceptions of ongoing digital change within the firm.

Hence, again, the second set of the pilot study was conducted with four participants from multiple WMS firms from the London region, resulting in exciting facts and different perceptions from participants. Thus, choosing the participants from different firms was found to be appropriate for research.

The first participant who agreed to be interviewed was an external digital consultant from a global management consulting firm. This participant had relevant technical expertise in managing and implementing the DT change with the traditional WMS firms. At the same time, three participants requested no video or audio recording of their interviews. Each participant was mailed back the transcripts of their verbatims to confirm the originality of the transcript to be used for further thematic data analysis. The other executives who participated in the pilot study have relevant industry experiences in the WMS industry but different functional backgrounds.

All research questions designed for the pilot study were focused on exploring the understanding and perceptions about the digital shift in the traditional WMS industry and how it has impacted their job roles and responsibilities. Many questions were open-ended hence tailed with further supplementary questions based on participants answers. It was observed that senior management executives were comfortable in their offices in comparison to middle management executives. Hence, based on these observations made during the pilot study, the following flexibility is considered for the main data collection process.

Based on observations made during the pilot study, changes were adopted for the main conduct of research interviews. Few questions were changed to bring criticality and focus, so more questions got added for each stakeholders group after receiving the directives through pilot testing. The research questions were embarking with research aims and objectives as research aimed to explore the extent and impact of the digital transformation in the traditional WMS sector.

The pilot study aims to validate the questions, interview process, and empirical research data collection tools. Hence it is noted that during the semi-structured interviews, field notes and observations can be part of empirical data as many of non-verbal actions of participants are a form of data, i.e. hand moments, facial expression and tone of voice changing during questions all inform the depth of information and experiences held non verbally.

The pilot run of research interviews and data analysis was significant organising, conducting the interviews with the practitioners, specifically coordinating with senior management executives by clarifying all their doubts and questions on research and sharing all requirement research approvals and documentation. The glitches experienced initially in interviewing the senior executives in forming probing questioning spontaneously.

3.9: Research Settings

The research aim is fundamentally perception-based interpretative research. Thus, it is highly critical to have participants with relevant experience and background. Most participants were selected through the professional platform and attending the financial services industry events to make initial new- contacts with the potential participants. LinkedIn (the leading professional network platform) has been resourceful in getting contacts of prospective participants during the Covid- stricken period.

The following table below illustrates the relevant potentialities used to check the profiles in LinkedIn platforms for the suitability of prospective research participants and the snowball technique adopted to reach the right experienced executives.

Table 12: Background of research participants

Role	Experience	Industry	Location	Experience in DT initiatives & Strategy management
CTO/CDO/CEO'S Director	10-20 years	WMS	London	YES
Mid-Management Level	10-15 years	WMS	London	YES
External Consultant	7-20 years	BFSI sector	London	Yes

Most of the participants had sent their consent confirmation through the mail and approval for an audio recording of interview sessions. However, 15 participants were interviewed virtually using online platforms such as zoom/skype/ Microsoft teams due to lockdown restrictions. In virtually conducted interviews the only 2 participants gave consent for video recording of the interview while all others were only audio recorded. All interviews were transcribed and shared with respective participants to confirm typed verbatims for further data analysis.

Every interview was allocated a schedule of 30-45 minutes, but most interviews ended within 55-60 minutes. Few interviews with senior executives got stretched more than 70 minutes as they were flexible in discussing in-depth and provided more examples of current scenarios and happenings in the industry.

Bernard(2012, p.183) stated, “the type of interview determines the type of information sought from research participant”. In agreement with the above statement, the questions were carefully designed based on exhaustive literature review gaps. Personally, coming from the WMS industry, the experience was well wetted with legacy processes and internal change intricacies within the firm. The discussions provided great flexibility in creating comfortable discussions and good rapport with all participants during the semi-structured interviews environment. Hence, this flexibility is significantly helpful in probing questions to explore the brief answers on their understanding, perspectives over the DT theme.

This conversational interview pattern is helpful and valuable in capturing the insights of DT related perceptions, and it explored the importance of the human aspect in the success and failure of the DT phenomenon. Due to work and some travelling restrictions during the Covid lockdown situation, participants had been stuck at different locations. Hence few participants were interviewed from foreign locations like Spain, Italy, and India using telephonic skype interviews and MS-teams platforms. Only 8 Interviews were conducted directly (face to face), while with other participants, it was conducted virtually using various platforms like Skype, Ms-teams and Zoom. However, the initial discussion started with a self-introduction and explanation about the research theme and gradually moved into the main discussion modes of interviews.

In both modes of interviews, data generated data emerging into themes and does not comprise in quality or detailing of interview throughout the interview process. The researcher realised that participants are more relaxed in skype or telephonic mechanisms as they are comfortable being at home or their private place where most of the interviews scheduled for 30minutes stretched to 45 to more than 1hour in few cases.

In direct interview sessions, senior executives were interviewed in their office premises but observed being interrupted by calls, visitors, and immediate skip meetings. While the middle-management participants were not comfortable with interviews in their office premises hence it was carried in neutral locations. In most cases, virtual interviews were completed on time, while observations and reactions were noticed during direct interviews were visible in all virtual interviews conducted. The participants' expressions and reactions were noticed on few probing questions asked, and reactions were noted carefully. In each interview, questions curved in to understand the participant's viewpoint of DT.

During the interviews with research participants, the interviews were focused on the *GINC* component to explore the "How" and "why" aspects of DT transitioning and associated parameters relevant to the digital phenomenon. As significant to understand the impediments in embracing transformational change. Subsequently, the sub-questions continued to answer the mainframe of questions (Appx- 3, p.246). After eight interviews with participants, the researcher developed the soliciting skills to explore more profound perceptions and experiences through tailed questions.

Although the research formulated perceptions based questions to participants, there are fewer chances of data saturation stage, but still, after the seventeenth interview, a set of themes from all stakeholders started saturating and yielding similar themes. Hence, no new themes being explored, so interviews were concluded after interviewing twenty-three participants. All semi-structured interviews were carried out between December 2019- July 2020.

Data analysis is a repetitive process. After each interview discussion, it was immediately transcribed to reduce the chances of losing out from memory about any important point discussed or informed during the interview, which is relevant for the research context.

All interviews were audio-recorded with participants' approval, except few executives didn't want their discussions to be audio or video recorded. All interview transcripts were typed and shared with the respective participants for their approval on transcripts accuracy for further data analysis. During the data analysis process, the mail communication was made with respective participants for further clarifications in case of any doubt or unclarity.

Field Notes/ Observations: The field notes created during a visit to participant's place of work, location for interviews as being financial services organisations, these firms follow the high-security process and access approvals. Due to these restrictions, I wasn't allowed into any main events or meetings with participants without approval. Hence all field notes and observations are only made during visits to participant's office settings, expressions and reactions during the interview discussions. According to Taylor & Bogdan(1998), field notes are more reflective and descriptive information during interactions, and these are subjective notes by the researcher and are also part of the transcription of interview data.

Secondary Data: The secondary data consisted of information about the WMS sector and available online documents about WMS firms of participated stakeholders in research interviews. The following documents gathered on the WMS firms included case studies, digital investments and revenue models, prospective future investments, company brochures, in-house newsletters and available information on the organisation's websites and newspaper articles and published white papers by leading management consulting companies. The tertiary data sources are mainly sourced through the online database, company indexes and financial associations websites, and all mail communication between participants on any clarification sought on collected data is also part of data collection.

3.10: Research Sampling

This section of the chapter explains the data collection tools adopted for research data collection and discussing the sampling methods, sampling sample, ethical issues and data analysis.

This research follows an interpretive paradigm with the phenomenology approach in data collection, exploring stakeholders' perspectives about the DT phenomenon. Hence sampling size is critical in empirical data collection as the research theme is connected with large-scale complex digital change transformation. On the practical side of process implementation, only key executives or few teams within the firms build the strategy, planning and implementation of digital navigation. Thus, this research identified those critical positions and executives within the organisational topology. As this research is a perception-based approach, the perception-based model was used to develop the conceptual framework of the research study. The TAM model (Davis,1989) constitutes relevant perspectives components for developing the conceptual research framework. The following theoretical components are considered for choosing the relevant sampling size for the empirical data collection process.

1. Perceived usefulness element employees of companies

- Top layer within organisations: CEO, CTO, MD, PARTNER
- Middle Management (Functional): Wealth manager, relationship manager
- Business strategy level (Business): External Technology consultants

2. Perceived Use elements

- End-user: Customers who are investing through these companies.
- Middle management & top management group

As interpretative phenomenological research, the primary focus of purposive sampling will be the main stakeholder of the WMS firms, the senior & middle management executives, followed by external digital consultants with WMS industry experience and the customers, who are using WMS firms for their investment planning.

According to Creswell(2014), it can be either random or non-random sampling to select research participants, but this research is non-statistical, not using statistical tools for data analysis. Hence stakeholders for this research will be selected non-randomly. Saunders et al.,(2009,p.233) confirm that non-random sampling (non-probability sampling) allows sampling based on subjective judgement. This research aims to explore the perspectives of stakeholders based on their experiences in digital transformation adaption and implementation.

3.10.1 Interview Guidelines

As discussed in the previous third chapter of research methodology, the research design was formulated based on ontology and epistemological stances as an appropriately chosen, phenomenological interpretative approach for gathering data using purposive and snowball sampling techniques. Henceforth guidelines for the semi-structured interviews focus on the aim of the research study by capsulising the main components of interview questions are broken into the more minor elements to capture maximum perspectives and understanding probed further with sub-questions.

All interviews were conducted considering the ethical elements from participants and researchers ends. The following things adhered like starting the interview session on the confirmed day, all required information shared with participants well before interview day, time and place mutually agreed with respondents. Started every interview with the initial introduction about the research topic, aim, process, and researcher's background details to reduce reliability biasing. After self-introduction, again confirmation sought permission to record audio and video of the entire interview session. However, few participants, specifically senior management executives, did not want their names to appear in any study, which confirmed being anonymous in the report and any shared data. The name or number will be accessible only by the researcher till the completion of the research, and then it will be destroyed.

The "***GINC Perspective framework***" (***GAPS, ISSUES, NEEDS & CAPABILITY***) was used to design the main research questions and for further probing through tailed questions. The following diagram below is a framework designed for exploring the potential answers from research participants.

Figure 11: Interview guidelines in the backdrop of GINC perspectives (Author's illustration)

3.11: Data Analysis

Data analysis is the last section of the research methodology chapter, the most crucial part of the research process. According to Bogdan & Biklen(2007), data analysis is a vital aspect of qualitative research, following the non-statistical approach generating much more qualitative data than quantitative research. The qualitative data analysis requires the systematic data sorting process as themes generation is ongoing. Hence this research study has adopted the following steps in the analysis process.

This research is adopted the analysis process designed thematical by Braun & Clarke (2006, P.84)

- Familiarising by reading the date to understanding repeatedly
- Breaking the relevant data into parts “Units” for further analysis
- Forming the “Themes” from identified units
- Reviewing, defining and naming themes
- Synthesising or summarise the final report

3.11.1 Thematic Analysis

Data analysis posits qualitative study and perceptions emerging from various epistemology, ontology, and research axiology. Guest et al.,(2012, p.10) explains, “Thematic analysis is the frame of words and themes, forming and describing implicit and explicit Ideas within the collected data.” The name explains the purpose of the analysis is emerging themes from the data. Braun & Clark (2006, p.79) defined “It as a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data, patterns identified through a rigorous process of data familiarisation, data coding, and theme development and revision.” Thus, the data analysis was conducted in three states of the thematic nature of the analysis.

Marshall & Rossman (1999, p.150) stated that qualitative data “Bringing order, structure and interpret to the mass of collected data searches for content among data.”

Additionally, thematic analysis is interesting as the researcher found it repetitive and flexible in generating themes. The researcher was updated immediately after every interview and found themes embedded throughout the interview sessions. Similar to thematic analysis is content analysis, as a researcher needs to evaluate the relevant data analysis process of data collected.

Content analysis: This analysis uses a descriptive approach in coding and interpreting coded data of quantitative counts of codes (Downe-Wamboldt, 1992; Morgan, 1993).

Table 13: Thematic Vs Content Analysis

Thematic Analysis	Content Analysis
Familiarising with the data	Content analysis requires a priori ('before the fact') design (Neurendorf, 2002).
After familiarising with transcribed data, preliminary codes assigned to describe the content.	While the content analysis, due to prior decided codes, provides a deductive scientific approach to research.
Focussing on relationships between data themes	Focusses on the relationship between words
Does not lead to calculation	Can be calculated
Interpretative approach	Descriptive approach

Hence, this exploratory research study is an interpretative study with a phenomenological approach. Adopting the thematic analysis will develop maximum possibilities of understanding the themes, codes from data collected on stakeholders' perceptions through their experiences & understanding of the digital phenomenon, through thematic analysis than any other data analysis methods.

3.12: Data organising and managing: Interpreting reduction and analysis

The qualitative empirical data gathering can generate more data than is required due to the nature of data collection tools used in the process. The author Uwe Flick (2009) explains that qualitative data analysis is lined with several themes. Firstly, understanding the complexities of the DT phenomenon through in-depth experiences and understanding of the stakeholders who participated in the research. Hence, data organising and analysis can easily understand the concepts or identify the relationships between the concepts.

Thus, the data reduction process is significant in editing the collected data, summarizing the relevant data and presenting it. According to Huberman & Miles (1994), the potential universe of data is reduced in an anticipatory way linked with the developed or chosen conceptual framework, research aim, objectives and questions and methods used. However, this research considered the field notes, interview transcripts, audiotapes and other secondary data available into further relevant data selection and condensation.

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The audio recordings were often heard to familiarise with data to understand the theme formations after repeated readings and listening. Classifying the data into contents, units, sub-themes and main themes coded. Braun & Clarke (2006, p.84) introduced the concept that themes are semantic and latent. The participant's semantic themes are what the participant says, while the latent theme looks beyond respondents' spoken words by identifying the underlying ideas, assumptions, and conceptualisations.

So eventually, in this inductive research, both these semantic and latent themes are analysed and coded as initial concepts. During the interviews, participants discussed various scenarios and situations in DT related to business model shifting, highlighting the unsaid latent concepts linking to the DT phenomenon. Coding identifies the relevant phenomenon by analysing the commonalities, differences and patterns (Merriam, 2009; Wolcott, 2008). Hence this part of the analysis is significant for understanding and familiarising the data to form sub-themes and main- themes.

Henceforth, the research used thematic analysis on empirical data gathered by classifying the narratives into units, contents, sub-themes and significant themes. After a complete analysis of data from all stakeholders' groups, the pattern and thread were visible in critical factors within various WMS firms' layers and interlinking themes

3.13: Ethical Principles

Ethical consideration is a fundamental principle to protect participants' interest, integrity, accuracy and void any research bias. The author Oliver(2010) stated that relationship cementing and trust-building are critically ethical considerations. The research adopted the Diener & Crandall (1978) following three areas in ethical consideration. 1. Lack of informed consent 2. Invasion of privacy 3. the possibility of deception

- **Lack of informed consent**

Informed consent: consent is a confirmation by an interviewee on agreeing to participate in the research study. With context to this research study, identified stakeholder was reached out through appropriate communication channels, providing brief information on the research aim and purpose and seeking confirmation on participation. The information on research aims with guidelines on the interview process and the ethical approval details were shared with every participant. This research proposal was approved for further conduct as it adhered to the ethical and doctoral committee guidelines (2009) laid by the University of the West of Scotland was approved to proceed further.

- **Confidentiality and Anonymity (invasion of privacy)**

During the empirical data collection process, all participants' details and information maintained to strict confidentiality will not be identified at any given point of research. The pseudonyms codes were created to maintain participants' complete privacy and confidentiality. Participants were assured before the data collection process that information shared will be only used for research purposes, and data will be destroyed once the research is complete. The system on which information is recorded or stored will be used only by the researcher, and it is password protected.

- **Deceptions**

Deceptions occur by misusing the information shared by participants in the context of research. Hence to avoid any deceptions at the given chance, research purpose, process and proposal were shared with each participant well before the interviews dates were finalized and conducted. The contact numbers and email ids of the researcher, the lead supervisor, and the UWS, London doctoral office was shared with each research participant.

3.14: Limitations of the study: Reliability and Validity

- **Reliability**

Reliability in qualitative research provided lies with consistency, and there are various paradigms of measuring reliability in quantitative research methodology. According to Eisner (1991,p.58), “Excellent qualitative research can help understand a situation otherwise be enigmatic or confusing.” However, a similar element cannot be measurable in qualitative research as the difference in evaluating the quality of studies in quantitative and qualitative research is that the concept of reliability is irrelevant in qualitative research (Golafshani, 2003). Hence due to unsettling arguments in measuring the reliability, many various paradigms have been formulated for both research methodologies. Crotty (1998) defined one of the paradigms known as “constructivism” from the social perspective because all knowledge-meaning reality is contingent upon human practices constructed in and out of the interaction between human beings and their work, developed and transmitted an essentially social context.

In order to reduce the bias factor, all direct interviews were conducted in a neutral location to avoid influencing respondents and avoid any researcher’s bias. Background information of the researcher and aim of the research was shared with participants well beforehand of interviews. The verbatim interview discussions were shared as transcripts with each participant to get approval and confirmation on the originality of transcripts.

- **Validity:**

Validity in qualitative research means “appropriateness” of the tools used in the data process. According to the following researchers (Yin,2003; Saunders et al., 2012; Bryman & Bell, 2011) have confirmed that the most significant literature used for this qualitative research writing is validity, reliability, transferability, dependability, confirmability, transparency and consistency. While Stenbacka(2001) disapproves of validity in qualitative research, she argues that the concept of validity should be redefined for qualitative research. This describes reliability as one of the quality aspects of this research, which should solve to claim a study as part of proper research.

Hence, to validate this research methodology, the study adopted construct validity. This research aims a perception-based approach, leading to adopt an inductive strategy to meet the aim of the research. Thus, the research adopts a phenomenological approach to explore the perspectives of main stakeholders involved in digital transformation planning, strategy and implementation within the WMS firms.

- **Access**

Saunders et al.,(2009)define a case study as a strategy for research as the empirical investigation of a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context using multiple case study firms. To get approval for research in the WMS firms was the most challenging phase of the research journey. Being an international student with no internship in the WMS sector in the UK made the task more difficult to gain access. Few firms disapproved of conducting doctoral research due to the level of stakeholders involvement and GDPR related issues. Hence, I shortlisted multiple firms with a background history of digital transformation from the last seven years based on their secondary data available. All shortlisted WMS firms are mid-sized and dynamic investments in digital change, business model transformations, customer service updates, and supply chain integrations. This followed by identifying the relevant experienced executives from these shortlisted companies for the empirical data collection.

After scrutinising their experience and background, all stakeholders were contacted through various social media platforms and organisations' official websites. Secondary sources like companies' websites, published reports, case studies, and fact files are primary data support. Once the access is consented to by identified stakeholders, they were mailed detailed information on the research background, objectives of the research study. The consent forms and ethical approval information was shared, briefing in detail for participants reference and knowledge and gaining their consent on participation. The direct interview process was finalised with the date and time for semi-structured interviews.

- **Autonomy**

In qualitative research, the autonomy principle is followed by seeking consent from participating in the research study (Kvale,1996). In advance, all participants are informed verbally and by mail about the research background, aim, objectives, and purpose. The participants were well informed about data confidentiality during the interview and for data analysis. They were Participants were informed of their right as autonomous people to volunteer to accept or refuse any time to participate in the research process. Contact details of the researcher will be provided to all participants before the study is initiated.

- **Non-maleficence and Beneficence:**

As per the ethical standards, this essential principle for a research study ensures that participants will be free from physical and emotional harm during investigations. The contact details of the researcher's contact details will make available all to participants. Participants' identities are held confidential, and pseudonyms codes are used to avoid any identifications. Any quotations by participants are required to add in reports. The researcher will be taking their consent to add their quotations with anonymous identity in the report.

- **Justice & inclusiveness:**

The justice principle demands equal share & fairness to participants. Participants are selected impartially without any difference due to gender, age, culture, ethnicity, disability, language, colour, religion. A copy of the published research will be shared with every participant, policy-makers, and traditional WMS firm to strategise the DT adoption with an inside-out perspective.

3.15: Summary

Chapter three provided an overview of the research methods and their relevance to the research objectives. This chapter briefly discusses suitability and provides justifications for adopting philosophical stances for this research. Subsequent sections in the research explained the relevance of the researcher's background to the research study aim, which proved to be research motivation. In continuation, further discussed the selected research design, purpose and adopted interpretive paradigm for research. The chapter presented the empirical data collection methods tools adopted and their relevance to the conceptual research framework.

Further, this chapter describes the significance and process of the thematic data analysis followed in this study. This chapter explains the pilot testing and the reasons for conducting it twice in different settings and outcomes in finalizing the main research data sampling. The concluding section highlights the ethical code followed in the conduct of the research study.

The next chapter will be discussing the outcomes of thematic analysis from the empirical data gathered from four groups of stakeholders from the chosen case study sector. Chapter four presents the sub-themes and themes from each participated group, explains the significance of themes relevant to interview questions asked to participants, and provides critical quotations from interviews.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS

4. Introduction

The research methodology chapter covered the research paradigm, philosophy, methodology and data analysis of empirical data collected. As explained in the last chapter, this research adopted the qualitative research method to explore the extent and impact of the DT phenomena in the traditional Wealth Management Services sector. This chapter presents the thematic framework on data gathered from four internal and external stakeholder groups with the WMS sectors. The research explores the extent of the digital transformation through understanding and experiences of involved executives in adaption and strategizing the digital transformation shift. Hence the thematic analysis is adopted to identify the emerging themes for the research questions.

The findings of semi-structured are presented with respective sub-themes and entailed with main themes. Lastly, each main theme from each group is organised into a *GINC* perspectives matrix for an easy understanding and relationship from emerging indicators on the extent and impact of the DT phenomena in the traditional Wealth services sector.

Chapter four structure is as follows: Section 4.1 provides a research overview briefing with the objectives of research through formulated research questions and discusses the further conduct of thematic analysis of data collected from main stakeholders of the WMS sector followed by external DT consultants and finally with customers stakeholder. Section 4.2 to 4.5 presents the sub-themes and main themes group-wise. The findings are presented along with few critical and relevant quotations from participants along with an explanation further. Section 4.6 summarises the chapter and explains the next chapter briefly.

4.1: Research overview

The outline of the chapter presents the perspectives and voices of participated executives from various levels of the organisations in the WMS sector. The research aims to explore the perceptions of stakeholders with traditional WMS organisations undergoing digital change. Hence, the focus of the data collection process will be within the space of the following main research questions.

1. *What is the extent and impact of Digital Transformation in the WMS Sector?*
2. *What are the constraints and challenges in embracing the digital journey?*
3. *What are the critical success factors for Digital Transformation adaption?*
4. *What are the strategic capabilities vital for digital change?*

As discussed earlier in chapter three, all shortlisted participants clustered into groups based on their experience and job- roles and functions within the WMS organisation. Hence the findings of all fours groups are structured in the following sequence. Firstly, **group A** consist of top management executives in leadership roles like CTO, CEO, Managing Director, Partner. Secondly, **group B** comprising of middle management like Wealth managers, relationship managers or advisors. Thirdly, **group C** consists of external digital transformation experts from management consulting firms for strategizing the DT implementation in collaboration with the above groups. Lastly, **group D** includes the customers or clients, have been investing through WMS firms for their investment planning, retirement and tax.

According to Bryman & Burgess(1994), data familiarisation of selected data is when researchers return to notes and transcripts to identify the key issues, concepts, and themes. Hence, setting up the thematic framework or process will be significantly helpful in filtering and sorting the themes.

Thus, this research adopted the thematic framework for data analysis by Braun & Clarke (2006). A thematic analysis produces the thematic meanings and performance by identifying, analysing and documenting the data. The following are steps followed for the thematic analysis of data collected.

4.1.1 The thematic analysis:

1. All the interviews verbatims were transcribed immediately after interviews with every participant. A typed transcript of interview verbatims was emailed for respondent's reading and confirming before further analysis in cases of no recording permission.
2. Transcripts are read multiple times to familiarise participants' content and meaning and critical underlying meanings. For example, the participant's example is an analogy to specific situations. Thus, repeated reading of contents identifies keywords or meanings into "Units" or "Concepts".
3. Concept formation carried the further steps by identifying the enormous chunks of information, directing towards similar meaning, issues, or the DT phenomenon presentation.
4. Each unit of concepts then formed into a group of emerging sub-themes categories from all four groups.
5. Finalisation of sub-theme list again coded by form clusters representing the main themes representing the larger picture of issues, challenges, or newly emerged gaps, identified from stakeholders' perspectives.
6. Pattern sequencing and construction of main themes from sub-themes and these group-wise main themes are condensed into the main grid of research findings.
7. Subject to the phenomenological approach adopted by the research study, data saturation is subjective as perceptions of humans keep changing. Hence, data collection through semi-structured interviews continued until twenty-three participants when similar outcomes surfaced in data analysis, which is when interviews were stopped.
8. All group-wise emerged themes from stakeholder groups are clustered as *per the GINC perspective* framework.

4.2: Findings from Group A (Senior Management participants)

According to an academic literature review on the DT phenomena, the top management leaders in any business sector are the most significant actors in embracing the right approach and cultural change. As this research is specific to the WMS firms based within the London region, few executives who agreed to participate in the research were well-known figures in the leadership circle in digital space and the WMS industry as they frequently appear in industry-related talks shows. Following are the background profiles of the senior executives selected for semi-structured interviews. The purpose of including the top-management leaders is to unpack the complexities of DT phenomena and explore their perspectives about the extensive complex change, as this research aims to explore the extent & impact of DT

The following table summarises information on research participants (RP) and their names codified (pseudonym) to follow participants' anonymity.

The thematic analysis resulted in 6 major themes from group A comprising the 40 sub-themes revealing the current state within the industry and senior executives perspectives on DT. The outcomes highlighted the embracing and implementation challenges, business sustainability issues, and capability constraints. The following is an overview of the coding of themes mined from the data collected.

1. DT adaption Challenges:

The first question to participants started with defining the DT phenomena, followed by series of sub-questions in exploring their understanding, decisions, and experiences. The interview questions probed on the process of undergoing digital change and change occurring in their functional roles, responsibilities, decision making, adaption and implementation planning, transitioning impediments in transitioning across all levels and key learnings and failures as leaders. The outcome of interviews with all respondents resulted in yielding into the following sub-themes.

A¹¹: Lack of unified understanding of DT

A¹²: Mindset and cultural issues

A¹³: Mismatch of service and expectations

The majority of participants from group A expressed that current digital change and DT affairs as messy due to the lack of a unified approach within the top management. It highlighted that their knowledge and understanding of the expected vision from the digital transformational is critical in the process. Moreover, the top management executives confirm diverged opinions arise due to a lack of integration among core strategy teams within traditional firms. Following are few critical quotes from the research participants relevant to the context of themes.

- *"People sitting on board of these management firms do not have a real history in technology they have been using it out but not implementors on. So they are making decisions about of that product which they have a low level of knowledge about it."*
(A-PL-2).

- *"IT department does not have representation on the board of these firms, so you get senior sponsorship programmes from people who do not have adequate knowledge about it, hence change leadership is poorly done. As a result, around 70% of these projects are failing because bad change leadership management probably stemming the bad breadth from the outside too much flexibility allowed to external technology provider" (A-JE-6).*

Due to inadequate participation by top leaders in DT role-out programmes and the creation of digital education and training. The leaders' engrossment in strategizing the change movement but not being part of practical implementation impacts culture in building the essential mindset for digital adaption. These behaviours of senior management indirectly develop the sense of apprehensions among others layers within the organisation, impacting the scalability of DT shifting. Thus, management plays a significant role in strategising the clarity of vision and value creation by understanding the existing state of the organisation in terms of customer acquisitions, service expectations, and product enhancement leading to the invention of newer revenue models and filling the gap between expectations and delivery.

In traditional WMS firms, the human element is crucial in an advisory function, and it is a revenue-generating business unit for the Wealth Management business sector. During the interview discussion with group A participants, most participants indicated industry anxiousness about adopting new technology, which will change their existing profitable business model as these traditional firms do not want to lose their revenues.

- *"The changes they try make changes are like they try to change engine in-plane when flying. So I do think if you got hold of some systems, old process, old people are used of using those old traditional systems when you are trying to embed the new digital systems and culture into systems which will help grow the customer base from future generation/ customer, not from an existing customer based "(A-PL-2).*

Further questions were initiation in the interview to explore the reasons for customer shifting behaviour, and their responses indicated the disruptive technologies as one of the contributing factors in increasing customer expectations. However, according to the respondents, the current legacy business model does not allow expected transparency and flexibility of services due to the nature of the operational process and traditional methods of managing the clients' portfolios.

The customers in the WMS sector are categorised into three different groups based on their investment capacity like UHNI (Ultra-high net worth), HNI(High net worth investor), and retail (Retail investor) and these customers are charged with transaction fees as well as fees to manage their investments. Hence, the advisory service model involves the human advisor's time and effort in the consultive process and these legacy methods, which involve higher transaction costs, including the administrative charges.

With the growing fintech invasion in the Wealth management sectors, customer expectations have constantly been shifting due to the availability of similar services with more flexibility and transparency in lesser transaction costs than traditional WMS firms charge. According to respondents, the retail and HNIs customers generally prefer investing through these agile platforms provided by fintech firms due to fees factors.

2. Constraints in transforming the traditional business model

The analysis reveals the following impediments in transforming the existing business model by adopting advanced technologies. The interview questions were initiated with participants to understand their perceptions about constraints in digital navigation of traditional firms in the sector.

A¹⁶:External Forces

A¹⁷: Lack of vision: leadership

A¹⁸:Management approach

A¹⁹: Regulator framework

A²⁰: Cost and investment buy-in issue

A²¹:Cannibalisation of business

A²³: Customer base linked with DT investment

According to senior management respondents, the abovementioned factors are obstructions or reasons for withholding the further developments related to the DT in the traditional WMS sector. At the same time, fintech firms are already leveraging the technologies in their advisory, trading, and risk profiling functions. These developments and availability of agile services create a halo effect over traditional industry and influence customer expectations.

In addition to these challenges, there is a restricted regulatory framework by FCA(Financial Conduct Authority), which is changing the landscape of the wealth services industry holistically. The regulatory restrictions are for the security and welfare of investors as rapid technological led disruptions occurring within traditional WMS sectors. According to respondents, these regular interruptions by financial regulatory bodies cause intermittent changes in the planned digital investment and digital transitions by Wealth management organisations. These regulatory interruptions do not resolve the current issues on adopting technology into the traditional process, but frequent changes create implementation challenges.

- *"The challenge of regulatory bodies for the wealth sector does not address any issues about technology implementation" (A-JE-6).*

The dynamic ability of leaders to steer the digital navigation are critical skills to uphold the integration of the vision and value creation match. However, as expressed by participants, the underlying issue is about the short stint of leaders in critical positions like CTO, CEO & CDO roles responsible for steering the digital navigation for traditional WMS organisations. But however, these leaders have a short span of self-life in firms maximum association of 5-7 years. These top-management executives develop the culture through their behaviour, expertise, and involvement in organisational growth, which have an impactful ecosystem, but the leader's departure impacts existing culture and dynamics within the organisations. Especially the leader's departure during the phase of DT leaves a vacuum to develop the panic, confusion and digital change obstacle in the transformation cycle sprouting into resistance and inertia factors among employees for further DT initiatives.

- *"I think other reasons of firms are unable to embrace the DT completely, as senior management executives are generally nearing their retiring period. Most of them are nearing the end of their careers and do not understand technology dynamics; hence, they resist massive investment to bring in roller coaster changes within organisations, hence tendencies to delay digital initiation" (A-PL-2).*

Respondents raised their concerns and uncertainty about whether digital transformation and technology advancement might cannibalise their existing revenue-generating business model. In comparison, Fintechs are already introduced disruptive technology-led processes in the advisory services through the "Robo-advisory model", which is cost-wise is lesser than traditional WMS firms advisory framework.

- *"Company "X" introduced the Robo advisor known as "Smart Wealth" a few years ago across all its customer base by digitalising the investment process under FCA approval. But company "X" lost its revenue margin due to loss of customers base, due to complete automation without knowing the perception of customers" (A-JE-6).*

Hence, automation intensifies the concerning challenge for the traditional WMS firms about completely transforming their service model. The digital transformation phenomenon has many pros and cons, holding up the doubts, concerns, and scalability of services by adopting new technologies.

According to reports from Harvard Business Review on the FSI sector(2019), around 2.2 million people in the UK do investment planning and portfolio building with the help of advisory experts from the WMS firms. As discussed earlier, the advisory consultation and associated services are designed based on customers' investment size. Thus segmented into UHNI, HNI and retails customers. It highlights the relationship between the customer market base and DT investment strategy. The reason is that traditional WMS firms are concerned about the revenue generation aspect from existing customers before initiating technology adaption and disrupting the current business model.

- *"The fact is that so much digitalisation so much more digital braces if wealth manager can cater to that requirement" (A-BB-5).*

3. Capability Challenge :

The thematic analysis of empirical data from the group A respondents, the most spoken theme is a capability extant. It indicated that the advancement of technologies had stimulated the focus on capability quotient in the WMS industry. There are various elements interlinked with capability factors. The following are yielded sub-these from the analysis.

A²³: Value Chain creation

A²⁴: Capability & Talent

A²⁵: Unified vision at involved groups

A²⁶: Service model Synergy

A²⁷: Scalability and agility

Digital transformation is impacting society, businesses, and every individuals' life in various ways. The technology is disrupting the existing value chain structure and service model design for every business across all sectors. Specific to the Wealth services sector, there is disintegration in traditional value chain structure as digitalisation has reduced the barrier of entry of new service model by Fintechs. Their agile business model is tumbling the sector by developing the new expectations of value chain creation.

- *"Just technology cannot create value chain, but traditional firms can create value chain by developing or creating an experience through the innovative medium of technology enhancing the services with a good understanding of expectations and requirements" (A-RC-4).*

Talent and skills are well-defined themes discussed during all interview discussions. Top management executives spotted the issue of reducing the number of advisory professionals in the Wealth management sector. This concern was observed during the discussion on enhancing digital education for advisory professionals to develop unified knowledge. The value-chain creation starts first meeting during the customer acquisition process with prospective customers, and lack of digital skills will hinder the customer acquisition. However, there is a lack of synergy in adopting digital innovations in the current scenario as top management and functional level executives lack uniform understanding.

- *"Current challenges of tighter regulations, shifting, ageing and inadequate digitally informed talents and advancing innovative technologies is making the adaptation process slower in traditional wealth organisations" (A-PL-2).*

The scalability of business in the digital transformation is interlinked with many internal and external factors unless the organisation is apparent clear with the DT vision and expected goals from digital transition. The current issues discussed in scalability includes the above themes discussed earlier. Due to Inadequate internal talent in the execution of a digital transformation, the most traditional WMS firms partner with external DT experts for their talent and expertise.

- *"Well, I think internal stakeholder management is a significant hurdle in traditional management. The process is designed to do not meet the requirements of the digital-savvy requirement and expertise. Hence, most firms partner with external consultants to build a digital ecosystem and its execution" (A-NM-3).*

4. Competitive advantage

The traditional WMS has been experiencing turbulence from rapidly changing customer expectations and behaviour towards the investment patterns and services, which compels traditional organisations to adapt quickly to the new agile business model. The major sub-themes emerged from the synthesis of data gathered to understand the competitive advantage factor of traditional firms.

A²⁸: Size and structure

A²⁹: Business Model restructuring

A³⁰: Market capture: FinTech's

A³¹: Talent development & retention

The participant quoted an example of a leading organisation's failure in adopting the Digital Transformation due to its large size and complex hierarchical structure. The WMS firms scaled their operations over the years into a number of branches and franchisee business models primarily. The example quoted by the participant is principle issues in developing a unified culture approach and precipitating the vision uniformly across hierarchies.

In terms of change transitions, elements like alignment factors, processes unification, strategy, implementation process are likely to be problematic to manage due to the size and structure of firms (Chan et al., 2006)

- *"Size of the organisation is significant in change practices and execution, larger the size more the complex scalability of change dimensions" (A-NM-3).*

Another perspective about the size and structure of firms explained by another respondent is the intricacies of managing the bureaucratic culture.

- *"Generally, at lower functional levels, there is minimum liberty to express any innovative ideas as management support and funding is negligible" (A-BB-5).*

The more profound analysis of data showed many factors interlinked attributes in the digital transformation cycle. Similarly, the sub-themes emerging indicate the rigidity of traditional companies in bringing flexibility within their business model. As advisory business is a significant revenue-generating business line, hence there are apprehensions around developing or embracing automation in that business line. However, there is the compelling influence of external factors currently cascading on this legacy model.

Fintechs firms are seizing the existing market base from traditional wealth management firms with agile and specialised services. The following scenario concerns the leaders of traditional WMS firms due to fintechs agile model and fees structure. There is a dichotomy in perceptions among top-management participants about the fintech association factor. A few participants see fintechs as competitors, while others participants think there can be synergy in partnering with Fintech to support specialised services across the customer base.

- *"Fintech's are a threat to private banks and firms because they focus on those areas where banks or firms are grumpy, or they look out for high margins" (A-BB-5).*
- *"Fintech's are not competitors, but by associating with fintech will be able to provide specialised services to our clients" (A-RC-4).*

5. Sustainability perspectives

Following sub-themes emerged from data analysis with indication on sustainability avenues in the Wealth Management Sector.

A³²: Hybrid business model

A³³: Resistance & Synergistic factors

A³⁴: Objectivism of DT goals: Phases

In precise, business sustainability challenges are different for traditional wealth management firms. According to data from the responses from senior-executives participants, more significant problems are rapid changes due to technology in financial service sectors. It is changing the behaviour of millennials and younger gen X, Z and Alpha. These critical issues were queried further with sub-questions to understand solutions for these problems, which resulted in suggestions by the respondents in embracing the hybrid business model.

Based on changing market conditions like customer expectations and rapid development of innovative technologies, these factors influence flexibility and agility in existing processes and business model structuring rather than transforming completely. There highly recommendation of a hybrid business model fundamentally integrated with a vision from the digital transformation phenomena.

The second subtheme directed the significance of the hybrid business model. According to senior management executives, the shortage of talent, technology speed, and rising customer expectations. These factors lead to a collaborative strategy with fintech firms to produce the agile service model for their customers. This strategy calls for the inorganic growth of traditional firms by opting for M&A(Merger & Acquisitions)with fintech companies. But they also see this growth as challenging in adaption at internal levels.

- *“The firms which have seen inorganic growth through M & A and partnerships have adapted well. The technology required to enhance and create customer value change by meeting their demands efficiently by following hybrid mechanisms of Robo and human advisory” (A-MB-1).*

Thus, further questioning management stakeholders participants about their perceptions of challenges in adapting a hybrid model revealed the communication, involvement leaders to granular levels as critical factors in the process.

- *“Strategic decision to associate with a fintech company to promote advisor network providing online services creating competitive advantage”(A-NM-3).*

Understanding of DT phenomena by each individual is different. At the same time, few interpret DT from IT aspects, few from the angle of digitising the operational functions while digitalisation and digital transformation are different phases. However, respondents indicated during the interviews that a lack of unified approach and understanding about DT disintegrates the organisational DT vision or automates the digitalising of the few operational processes.

6. Reasons for DT failure:

The concluding question to group A participants was about their perceptions on DT failures within established companies, irrespective of the resources and experts availability. The thematic analysis yielded the following sub-themes.

A³⁵: A leadership approach

A³⁶: Management buy-in

A³⁷: Retention of top management executives

A³⁸: Resistance & traditional operational mechanisms

A³⁹: Failure of unified vision sharing

According to industry participants, most DT failures in the WMS industry are linked with a mismatch of strategic leadership approach and aligning the vision by integrating resources and mechanisms. The participants' feedback towards exploring the underlying reasons highlights the lack of the right approach from the top-level within the organisation contributed to resource mismatch.

- *“The organisation’s sustainability and growth all depend on leaders if the leader has that ability to translate the strategy into some meaningful decisions on technology investments, which will impact directly on goal and vision of what they want to see themselves as an organisation” (A-NM-3).*

The above statement from the participant directs the scenario in the industry about the lack of synergistic factors in terms of the strategy conversion into smaller tasks towards integrating the digital initiatives. The tendencies of DT projects getting frozen is quite common in traditional WMS settings due to high transformation costs and expectations of quick returns from board members and investors, which further freezes the investments.

- *“The large scale of transformations requires buy-in approval for investment and budgeting allocation to initiate the project” (A-NM-3).*
- *Generally, management in the WMS firms starts developing cold feet on returns expected or freeze the further investment as well”(A-MB-1).*

As stated by participants, top management tends to expect returns on investment (ROI) within a stipulated time. Moreover, the exit of senior executives in specific roles like CTO, CEO or MD, leads to influence on digital change. A new leader brings his experiences, attributes, and ideas towards the digital change adaption, which is likely to delay embracing the digital mindset.

As the DT transitions cannot be completed without people and resources alignment, leaders should sense and seize the opportunity to collaborate the right capability with technology in approaching a targeted customer base.

4.3: Findings from Group B (Middle Management Participants)

Group B encompass middle-management executives from the front office team(front-ending roles, direct interaction with customers). Generally, these executives are designated as wealth managers, relationship managers and financial advisors in the traditional WMS sector. Primarily, these roles are significant for this research because middle management executives are the catalyst in building value creation by integrating the services in line with the organisational set vision. Key attributes of this role encompass capabilities like their financial knowledge, expertise, digital skills, ability to create bonding with the customer by understanding the customer requirements. As factors like trust and relationship are critical attributes in advisory functions. These capabilities develop the trust and relationship factors for the customer loyalty element.

Thus, it is critical to explore middle management perspectives over the digital transformation and impact rapid developments in technology, its impact on their job roles and challenges of customer management aspects. The following table presents the executives' relevant background and functional experience in the wealth management sector.

The participants are certified wealth/relationship management professionals, managing a large client base from customer acquisition to back-end administrative integration for their client onboarding and execution.

The primary research questions followed with sub-questions to explore their perspectives over the complexities and challenges of digital transformation. Following are themes derived from the thematic analysis of data gathered.

1. Managerial Perspectives

The following are the yielded sub-themes from the cluster of data from middle managers participants.

B¹¹: Disruption of legacy business model

B¹²: Recognised improvement by technology

B¹³: Mis-alignment of vision and goals

Middle managers' perspective over the DT phenomena is a polarised approach. The holistic perception of transformation is linked with each person's functional role experience and understanding. However, there were disparities in responses over the transformation of traditional advisory functions due to disruption due to technology. Following are few quotes from participants.

- *“Effects of technology are positive. It has increased the speed of operations and security issues manageably, quick transferring of information to clients” (B-TK-10).*
- *“Technology has influenced the customer's behaviour, and major challenges is their shifting behaviour and changing investment partner”(B-AH-7).*

During interviews, there is a significant discussion over the concerns about the disruptions in the fees and cost of portfolio management, and wherein traditional businesses face challenges from Fintechs. While participants acknowledge their optimism about digital advancements in the wealth management sector, digitalization strengthens organisations' synergies by reducing gaps in the back, middle and front office processes. The participants feel agile and transparent in back-office processing work that can help the customer onboarding journey.

- *“Digital Transformation is a big wave of change that has introduced many changes in traditional sectors. The changes in terms of working process, regulations and culture as well actually to discuss with you, it is like a tsunami of digitalisation”(B-KH-11).*

Despite the recognised positive impact of technology over the traditional process, there are polarised perceptions as top management executives lack a collective approach towards the

DT. Further exploration probing on this approach holistically about implementation strategy of transformation resulted in responses about lack of collective approach or involvement.

Due to insufficient information and communication by the strategic team of the firm about digital transformation, leaders to fear and confusion at middle and lower management executives about role sustainability.

- *“Lack of visibility is a major concern in adopting digital transformation, and fear around transformation is also one reason for the resistance in the direction of transformation” (B-BV-9).*

Few wealth manager participants expressed their dissatisfaction about the way the few organisations conducted the DT change. They have apprehensive about their roles in the future as there are constant changes in the advisory role due to innovative technology, which might leave their role as an only executive rather than consultation and advisory.

2. Customer Alignment

Following are the sub-themes yielded on questions related to customers onboarding and portfolio management experiences.

B¹⁴: Customer acquisition & retention challenge

B¹⁵: Existing approach – Product centric

B¹⁶: Adaption of technology linked with the customer base.

In the current scenario within the WMS sector, the significant challenges for wealth managers are customer acquisition and retention issues, which is similar situations across all traditional firms according to group B participants. The traditional WMS firms in the sector have a competitive edge over new Fintechs. Earlier firms have a large customer base with established relationships and trust factors built over years of services provided by the firms, while later firms have agile service models and disruptive platforms providing similar services at lesser fees but still, not all customer segments are confident of fintechs. The younger customer generations (gen Y,Z) are keep about trying digital platforms due to flexibility and agile services as well as fee factor is attractive to these generations, resulting in the rapid switching of parter investment firms.

- *“Technology has influenced the customer’s behaviour, and major challenges are their shifting behaviour and changing investment part ”(B-CP-8).*

Respondents stated that managing trust and transparency in the relationship is becoming more demanding at present. The confluence of various disruptive elements leading customers to compare the various factors and behaviour in service expectations.

- *“For my DT in wealth management is more of replacing the analytical aspects of it as more of the judgemental part remains still with the human while rest will take care by the system, so it is radical change”(B-CP-8)*

The human element in the advisory business is paramount in the WMS industry, but the constant digital developments are changing the approach from product-centric to customer-centric. The introduction of AI-led Robo – advisory has compelled traditional firms to shift their business approach.

- *“If traditional organisations push themselves for an online model, they might lose the revenue model as transactional banking can be automated, but traditional companies still have a competitive advantage as the human element attached to advisory cannot be automated”(B-KH-11).*

During the interview process, respondents endorsed that the customised hybrid business model for the organisation would be a sustainability factor for the traditional advisory model.

3. Business Model

Automations in the service-oriented industry like the Wealth management sector has brought challenges to the existing plethora of pros and cons of the DT transitions, which raises the questions of scalability of service lines in the wealth sector. The deeper evaluation through a series of questions explored the following sub-themes linked to the business model theme.

B¹⁷: Lack of unified DT approach

B¹⁸: Top Management outlook on DT adaption

B¹⁹: Disparities in the service model

B²⁰: Capability Development

A substantial indication from interview verbatims indicates the lack of unified understanding about expectations set by organisations on embracing digital change. A digital journey of traditional firms gets critically affected by the disconnect of awareness and digital upskilling education, which sprouts into resistance behaviour towards a holistic transformational process. The following quotes from verbatims of respondents from middle management are a clear indication of different perspectives on DT.

- *“The WMS is a traditional sector, currently compelled by the revolution of technology which is one main reason for influencing the customers' behaviour” (B-AH-7).*
- *“According to my understanding, Digital transformation in wealth management sector is more of replacing the analytical aspects with automation, but judgemental part remains still with a human while rest of process will be taken care with digitalisation, so it is a radical change”(B-CP-8)*

There is agreement from past literature and current practices regarding the significance of top management roles in any change management phenomena. While technological change requires expertise, knowledge, and understanding, most traditional firms seek external expert support to embrace the change within organisations. Hence the top-bottom approach by senior management is critical in the application of change across.

- *“Maturity levels cannot build overnight; it happens over the years by including the best use into practices” (B-TK-10).*
- *“Irrespective of whatever the automation work we do, will change in the course of work based on the decision, mindset, approach and size and structure of the organisation” (B-CP-8).*

Middle-management respondents highlighted the disparities in the service delivery model existing, which is a gap in the current scenario in financial markets.

- *“The real challenges currently is in personalisation touch, expected irrespective of the size of client investment or institution investment going today, so that is going to sustain for a long time in a competitive environment” (B-LP-12).*

Respondents wanted to voice out that critical disparities in the services model in traditional WMS firms are linked with a customer investment size. In contrast, transitions due to technology and the fintech model might compel traditional firms to change the current segmentation of services to uniformity across.

With the absence of a yardstick to measure the capabilities, as each wealth service firm has its own ordinary and dynamic capabilities, resources are vital in the path of digital change. Due to the cultural imperativeness element being different in every organisation, the capability element cannot be generalised but demands customisation.

- *“The fact is that so much digitalisation and technology advancement is evolving, so much more digital braces but whether the wealth manager can cater to this requirement” (B-BV-9).*

The above statements indicate that the gap will widen if the management does not invest in employees' capability development.

Data is a driver, and participants emphasised the importance of leveraging the available data for changing business focusses. Data can identify the patterns and trends from available information and is enormously helpful in directing the resources and synergising them in the right direction.

- *“Technology can be helpful with the relevant data and figures which is the key driving factor for the decision-making process” (B-CP-8).*

4. Current Challenges for Middle management executives

Following are sub-themes that emerged under the theme of current challenges.

B21: DT Maturity levels of traditional firms

B22: Regulatory Frameworks

B23: Influencing & Compelling factors

B24: Perceptions on DT failures

The industry is undergoing the re-invention of the traditional business model, seeking to increase scalability by leveraging disruptive technologies.

Most group B participants stated that constant changes in the path of embracing digital maturity. The major impact indicated from the data towards maturity levels of organisations critical for any transformational changes. With a focus on exploring the challenges from all stakeholder participants, few themes are similar to group A themes like regulatory frameworks and influencing factors.

- *“As an organisation, it is essential to understand the DT vision that built, and hence each step taken should connect with the firm's vision”(B-AH-7).*

According to internal stakeholders' data analysis over current industry challenges, both groups emphasised a domino effect of the regulatory framework by FCA (Financial conduct authority) over the organisational effort in adapting digital changes.

- *“There is the challenge of regulations for the wealth sector, which needs to address for any technology being built or used for end-users, i.e. customers”(B-TK-10).*

Middle management participants highlighted the impact of the Covid pandemic in accelerating digital adoption in traditional WMS firms. Few shared their experiences in advisory functions during a covid pandemic will change modes of providing consultation permanently in the wealth service industry.

- *“Due to Covid 19, many processes are fast-tracked lot of technology and process, they work on many things introduced over 15-18 months generally but due to Covid situation, they fast-tracked many processes”(B-KH-11).*

Covid has accelerated the digital adoption in services, and customers realise the benefits of online services, especially during the pandemic situation. Hence, industry stakeholders see this as a challenge for their current functional role, which is that they see it changing in the longer run.

The perspectives towards failure in adapting the successful digital transformation by group B executives are consolidated on leaders ability to translate the strategy into action and involvement of stakeholders from all departments for increasing communication interaction.

4.4: Findings from Group C (External Consultant Participants)

The disruptions within the WMS sector are due to technology development. The traditional firms are partnering with technology experts in embracing and executing Digital Transformation. As per industry reports, the organisation's top executives like CEO, CDO and CTO have DT as their agenda to rewire and build the strategic capabilities. The significant pressure due to external competition and insufficient expertise within traditional firms seek support in implementing technical and strategic directives to execute a large-scale transformation.

Hence, it is critical to interview suitable executives as part of research data collection to explore their perspectives on the DT phenomenon in the Wealth Management Sector. The DT execution is generally pre-planned and phases with senior management and relevant executives' significant involvement from different functionalities and associated external firms. This journey has limitations and constraints, which is the aim of interviews to explore these perspectives.

Following is the background and profile of external consultants who participated in research interviews.

1. Polarised Perceptions on the understanding of the Digital Transformation

The data synthesis gathered from group C executives shows the polarised understanding of DT phenomena as critical among the main stakeholders. Following are vital sub-themes yielded from data analysis.

C¹¹: Technology focussed outlook

C¹²: Gap in Industry experience

C¹³: Disconnect of goal setting and value creation

According to data outcomes, knowledge about the DT phenomenon is closely linked with actors' roles within organisations. Hence opinion varies from person to person. Similarly, expectation also differs in connection to DT change.

- *“There is much misunderstanding about DT; everyone’s opinion is different on this phenomenon, generally related to the digital transformation. In the case of digitisation, they did not transform any business processes; they were the same but just changed ” (C-AB-16).*
- *“The need for transformation at a large scale is about focused change need in all required processes to achieve a common goal, but firms do not want to change the process. They just want the digitalisation of some process; hence this is not digital transformation” (C-SP-15).*

There is a disconnect in understanding the DT phenomena within all levels of management executives. However, although digitisation and digitalisation are fragments of Digital transformation, each fragment is a high cost of the implementation process. The group C respondents highlighted their experiences of managing the DT change operations within traditional WMS firms are generally automating the legacy process transforming from paper to paperless initiative as transformation without much creating the value out it. The participant discussed that DT successfully integrates major 3P’s of the system, i.e. People, product and process, but in many cases, it only focussed on any one of the single P’s, which is the failure of the objective.

The role of external technology experts in DT execution is like a catalyst between the organisation's existing business model to an expected model. Hence an explicit knowledge and awareness of industry objectives and cultures are necessary. Due to competitive factors, pressure and the rapid development of technology demand the expertise support for implementation with efficiency and speed. They create the blueprint of the DT journey, teamwork with the single unified approach towards creating the process and integrating the vision with value.

- *“Many organisations hire a leading consultant just to understand the current competition and trend in the market”. Although technology external consultants are hired to understand the existing practices and trends in businesses, consultants support aligning the organisation's internal and external capabilities for digital transformational prerequisites”(C-FP-13).*

For successful digital transitions, there should be a clear path set for integrating vision and value elements for the organisation. However, according to group C respondents, there is a gap in setting the right approach and culture for any external stakeholder to understand the requirement for vision and the expectation to create the value chain.

- *“You need to know the industry well to understand the problems existing within. I mean technology to solve problems, but if you are not aware, you cannot solve anything if you only know the problem”(C-AB-16)*
- *“You embark on the transformation exercise as you know of that nature, then it is important before you embark to understand what is it that I hope to I achieve it.” (C-FP-13).*

2. Perspectives on the challenge by DT experts

According to group C executives' interview data, the following are sub-themes yielded under themes of current challenges as per the participated DT experts.

C¹⁴: The competitive advantage

C¹⁵: Mindset and Culture factors

C¹⁶: Size and Structure factors

Although traditional WMS sectors are under tremendous pressure from digitally-enabled Fintechs, the traditional firms are robust on customer data. The data contributes to creating a strategic service model in the path of competitive advantage. All group C participants emphasised the supremacy of traditional wealth services firms over Fintech firms. The availability data can identify the patterns and trends of changing behaviour from customers data which is highly valuable in synergising the resources in the proper use of customer services.

- *“The amount of details of data provided how interactives is it how much it is disposal you can make it like trading ability or information providing services” (C-SP-15).*

As per the verbatims of group A & B respondents, it stated the customer expectation regarding the agile and transparency services and the requirement of human element specifically at UHNI and HNI customer segment. Hence, the competitive edge of traditional firms over Fintech lies in available data of existing customers, the data mining of databases to a different extent to understand trends and behaviours by using AI technologies.

Findings yielded from interview data exploring the challenges experienced by external DT experts are similar to finding from groups A & B. The senior management had quoted various reasons internal, external factors and the inadequate mindset for digital approach. In contrast, middle management executives indicated the top leadership skills are critical in steering the digital shift within organisations. The respondents from group C have the same opinion that leadership insights in managing a large scale of digital change transition are critical. It becomes challenging to move a big elephant unless the elephant does not want to move ahead. Thus, a similar analogy applies to traditional WMS firms in the current scenario. Large organisations cannot adapt to the DT unless the organisation is clear with expectations for digital navigation. This initiative can be smoothly managed if there is complete involvement by top leaders within organisations by creating a smooth strategy flow of communication and planning and developing unified matured understanding across

- *“Mature leadership is essential to move into Digital transformation; this means leaders must not be afraid of change ”(C-MT-17).*

- *“Company will not be ready for it so change management, and the process needs to very robust, a lot of organisation call for “crawl -walk -run” type of approach which is a very systematic approach in what we do and when do our organisation is ready when these new capabilities are ready for implementation” (C-FP-13).*

The interview participant discussed the “crawl-walk-run” strategy generally adopted within the industry to match innovative technologies' speed. The challenges and constraints in findings from group A respondents are relevant to findings from group C respondents' data analysis. Due to various constraining factors, few organisations are successfully adopting the above approach in the adaption of DT. Hence there is severe stress on the role of leaders in setting the right approach and mindset in the change movement.

Regarding the DT execution and implementation, respondents from groups C indicated the complexities of the WMS sector due to size and structure. The organisation size and structure are linked with elements like alignment aspects, control, process sophistication and implementation strategy(Chan et al.,2006)

- *“Size of the organisation is essential in change practices, larger scalability of change dimensions” (C-SP-15)*

Thus, DT experts indicate the execution challenges due to size, internal structure, and mindset towards the DT phenomenon.

3. Talent and Capability Integrational Issues

Following sub-themes yielded from the data analysis into the main themes focussed on exploring the angle of capability integration with DT expert executive.

C¹⁷: Raising expectations from the customer

C¹⁸: Operational Challenges

C¹⁹: Management buy-in approach

The earlier themes discussed in the above paragraphs show the disconnect between customer expectations and DT navigation.

The external factors compelling the traditional firms to rewire their existing advisory module, but again, high transaction fees and portfolio management fees are challenging for traditional firms compared to fintech.

- *“There is a mismatch of technology and capabilities in people understanding within the industry, and it needs vertical implementation while most of IT companies engage in horizontal direction” (C-FP-13)*
- *“Fundamentally, innovation cannot be seeded in a large organisation, and it has taught down that by power roles like CTO, CDO AND CEO”(C-AB-16).*

The group C stakeholders discussed the execution gap of strategy at the organisational level, wherein top management executives should translate the strategy into action as communication is a critical contribution in increasing the flow of digital change-related information and knowledge. However, research respondents revealed that critical information is withheld in certain top layers of organisations in practice. Only filtered information and limited knowledge are shared vertically, leading to operational confusion and chaos due to inadequate awareness of strategy in adopting change, leaving a scope of resistance.

- *“Non-mature leadership will deny required change as long as possible and push for the status quo and attempt to force resources underneath the status quo organisation to move to DT without changing the upper leadership” (C-SP-15).*

4. Impediments in DT execution

The external DT consultants participants in the research interview indicated the impediments at each phased execution in traditional services firms. Following are sub-themes under this main theme of impediments in DT execution

C²⁰: Resistance issues

C²¹: Cost factors

C²²: Maturity of traditional organisations

C²³: The exploitation of expertise in technology

The underlying resistance issues were discussed and highlighted the criticality of the factor by other groups of stakeholders as well. However, group C participants have highlighted similar experiences of underlying resistances by internal WMS employees in supporting DT implementation. Group C participants expressed a scenario with traditional WMS firms due to incomplete information and knowledge about objectives from digital transition among operational and functional level employees. Lack of knowledge about the organisational DT strategy leads to the situation without adequate support on various process automation by internal staff, fearing the uncertainty over job roles. The following are quotations indicating the real reasons behind the resistance and inertia in the traditional industry.

- *“For a large organisation, the idea of embracing the automation creates the fear about job losses, changes in the job role diminishing the importance of their job profile”(C-MT-15).*

In response to the question regarding the approach of top management executives, the following is a perception quoted participants from executives.

- *“The important factor in the sizeable traditional organisation about change transitions is that the top management cannot sit in the pavilion and watch the game but is required to be part of a match to bring change efficiently” (C-16-AB).*

According to the group C participants, possible reasons for the resistance situation are the lack of uniform infiltration of information and strategic planning among all required departments and units. In functional levels, only specific directions are shared with particular teams. Hence, holistically there is inadequate understanding of the entire phenomena. Another challenge generally encountered by these participants is top management expects quick revenue generation and starts having the cold feet about further investment due to rising costs due to regulatory requirements, customer protection and cybersecurity.

- *“The leaders are apprehensive about setting out DT journey as management is accountable to board of investors and shareholders regarding DT investment and value generation from the investment as its is super expensive and risky ”(C-FP-13).*

According to few respondents from this group, the traditional services firms tend to overlook the maturity and readiness elements before embracing the digital transformation. The factors like digital readiness, maturity in terms of approach, capabilities and resources are not integrated as expected.

- *“Organisations’ digital readiness/maturity depends on the situational circumstances, but various pressure points compel or influence the changes in firms. If the traditional firms trying to build digital maturity from scratch, then due to many legacy impediments in the process requires collaboration or firms are failed in embracing it” (C-MT-17)*

The above quotations highlights the insufficiencies in the integration aspect of internal capability, resource and the right mindset to embrace the change in traditional settings.

Towards concluding the interview discussion, the participant expressed experiencing the exploitation behaviour by large WMS firms to extract crucial information about their competitors' investments and digital strategy as the DT consultants happen to associate with the more firms in the WMS sector for their digital role-outs.

- *“Many organisations hire a leading consultant just to understand the current competition and trend in the market” (C-AB-17)*

The confluence of various elements causes friction in the digital transition and implementation, which gradually develops into resistance planning.

4.5: Findings from Group D (Customers Participants)

The role of customers' stakeholders is substantially essential for this research to explore the extent and impact of DT. The significance of choosing each stakeholder group is discussed in chapter three, starting with the main stakeholder of internal top & middle management executives, external DT experts, and customers' group. The underlying core structure in traditional WMS firms is similar to other sectors in the financial services industry. The vertical top-bottom structure follows from top-management layer ends to customer point. Hence the Circular Transformation Cycle (p.66) involves stakeholders from top management to customers, entire strategy, planning and action are targeted to meet the customer expectations. Hence, it is essential to understand the customer perspectives on this research aim. Following are customer profiles participated in the semi-structured interviews. Hereafter these stakeholder sets of customers are addressed as group D.

The customers' stakeholders are identified through the snowball technique and focus on their age factors and investments. Customer demographics are a significant factor as well influencing element in organisational DT investment strategy. As per the participants from earlier groups, all customer segments in general within the WMS industry concurrently influenced and impressed by agile services model by fintech sectors as well technology infiltration is the major reason behind expectation rise and behaviour changes.

Thus, based on outcomes and claims of earlier internal stakeholders regarding customer change perceptions, questions were formulated to understand their understanding, experiences and perspectives over the entire DT phenomenon in traditional WMS sectors.

Following are the yielded the sub-themes and main themes from data gathered

from group D

1. Perception about DT phenomena by group D respondents.

Before starting with interview questions with group D participants, the general introductory discussions confirm that they are fully aware of the ongoing digital transformation with the WMS industry and subsequent changes undertaken in back-office processing. The data analysis of the verbatims yields some interesting perceptions shared from their personal experiences of being part of the ongoing digital transitioning of traditional wealth service firms. The main reason to adopt the DT by traditional WMS firms surfaced from senior and middle management executive's data is a rapid expectation and behaviour changes in customers. Hence interview questions were directed to explore their phenomenological view about these shifting patterns and behaviours. Following are the critical sub-themes yielded under the main theme about their perception of digital phenomena.

D¹¹: Trust and confidence

D¹²: Human advisory element

D¹³: Visibility factor

During the interviews with group D, the author observed that the customers are committed to their investment firms due to their trust & long relationship with a financial advisor, which is a sticky element in keeping the loyalty element. This relationship nurtures with organisation's ability to provide agile services, understand their requirements and provide secured investment options. The relationship manager is the first person to cement the relationship with a customer with his/her financial knowledge, skill to navigate the customer into investment and provide customized services.

The other groups (group A, B & C) indicated customers' behaviour on shifting firms due to transaction fees, and the cost of trading in traditional firms is higher than newer Fintech firms. However, the outcomes for the interview provided a contrasting perception. Few participants highlighted their reasons for switchover of investment firm due to their relationship manager, service incompatibility and product offerings.

- *I had one instance where I changed my relationship manager or got him changed as he was very poor in terms of even basic service, never contacted me after the initial investment and was uncontactable himself most times” (D-SI-22).*
- *“The wealth managers understand my required financial goal for a particular investment and able to explain their model. It has to be tailor-made and not generic” (D-SK-18).*

The above statements from participants indicate the service satisfaction linked directly with customer loyalty and the reason for shifting the firms.

As discussed in chapter two regarding the current scenario of the WMS sector, the advisory function involves the human element in creating the trust-based relationship. This model is currently disrupted due to Robo- advisory, which is already in use. Middle management executives have expressed the fear of their current advisory role turning into a mere executory role, instead of advising customers on financial investments, they might execute the orders from the customer in managing their portfolio.

- *“Human element / Robo advisor- Trust factor, I do not think any form of artificial intelligence can replicate the human element. I want my advisor to be human, knowledgeable in investment and regulations” (D-VH-21).*
- *I will always go with human advisory rather than Robo-advisor, which needs human interaction, while robots can add value by being used for service management processing and back-office, not for advisory(D-NH-20).*

On probing with few deeper questions about their perspectives on using the Robo-advisory services, most of the participants agree with the significance of human advisor compared to Robo advisor. Especially, the HNI and UHNI customer segments responded clearly about their preferences in having a human advisor advising them for investment and planning rather than a machine or robot.

Even though traditional organisations have been sharing the training and information on their digital transitioning, they provide all updates on operating procedures and processes in producing transparency to customers regarding their investments. However, the research participants had expressed the disconnected feeling in this whole process of the digital transformation of the wealth services firms.

2. Challenges: Customer outlook

Following are sub-themes yielded from the data gathered. The experiences shared during the interviews are purely based on participants experiences with their investment partner firms and their everyday interaction with their relationship/wealth manager. The questions were focused on exploring the challenges and constraints as a customer they have experienced in their onboarding journey.

D14: Influencing environment: Overload of information

D15: Cyber risk & threat

D16: Service differentiation linked with portfolio

The DT is not just the evolution in process change within the organisation but also the evolution in mindset of every stakeholder involved in the transformational shift. Hence, the digital transitioning process includes each stakeholder's understanding of phenomena, experiences, involvement and unified mindset and approach towards embracing the DT. As per industry leaders, integrating each individual's mindset embracing DT is a horrendous task, especially for traditional WMS firms. As these firms have followed legacy processes and procedures for generations, bringing in digital culture is a gigantic process that leaves many failures.

- *"Sometimes, I experience too much information confuse my decision-making ability, and then you start agreeing to an advisor without knowing the relevance of that product to me" (D-SI-22).*
- *"There are too many robots, no clear thought process, transformation to suit cost-cutting or regulatory, no actual customer benefit, and no longevity" (D-BR-19).*

These narratives show that rapid technological developments intimidate the customer decision ability. Most older generation customers are concerned with security and trust factors in digital ways of investment. This requires the involvement of the wealth/relationship manager as a helping hand in the smooth transitioning of these customers from a manual process to digital means introduced by WMS firms.

- *“Digitalisation is future, and it is risky as cyber safety will be an ongoing challenge” (D-SK-18).*
- *Risk and trust in digitalization in the WMS industry are not risky. But however, the awareness has not picked up among the investor. The automation is good, but it needs to clearly understand along with market risk” (D-NH-20)*

There is positivity around technology advantage and embracing digital transformation among all participated stakeholders. But the process of establishing new procedures and processes according to adopted technology involves the repetitive nature of the work. Currently, group A & B respondents see this repetitive technology transitioning period as a challenge, which can upset the customers and supply chain stakeholders. Thus, organisations prevent sharing digital transitioning strategies with external stakeholders to avoid hindrances, but again this approach sometimes creates a sense of chaos and confusion for customers.

- *“Client engagement -It is mixed. I guess it is all dependent on the portfolio size given to manage. They probably pay greater attention to profitable customers or customers with larger net worth” (D-SI- 22).*
- *“I need a relationship manager who can filter and curate the information for me to suit my needs” (D- MK- 23).*

The WMS firms leverage big data and analytics to design specific customer service levels to understand customer spending profiles, behaviours, lifestyle trends, and investment portfolios. While in the case of HNI & UHNI clients, there is a high level of collaboration between wealth managers and their customers to provide exclusive and customized services.

3. External element of influence

Although, according to earlier participants, fintech services were a significant influencing factor for change in customer behaviour. However, the data analysis contributed by revealing the following reasons for the change in expectations. The thematic analysis of data indicates the following sub-themes capsuled under the theme of external influence over customer decision making.

D¹⁷: Impact of Social media

D¹⁸: Fintech Services

D¹⁹: Transactions Cost element

In the 4.0 industrial revolution, the internet is the most influential factor in decision making. The internet is a vital part of our lives, and thus, technologies bring more offerings by disrupting traditional systems. Hence, business organisations attempting to create a value proposition by inducing the digital aspects in legacy design. With changing trends in customer demographics, legacy organisations embracing big data and AI (artificial intelligence) led advancements to potentialize the customer market from all segments and age groups.

- *“I do invest through my WMS firm, which I got to know through social media about its services offering and products” (D-19-BR).*

In continuation to fintech’s invasion in the wealth services sector, traditional firms are conflicting perceptions about collaboration with fintech. As fintechs’ specialises in providing niche services to investable customer segments. These specialised services are created by using disruptive technologies like Big data and AI. Fintech firms have developed their ability to adapt and leverage innovative technologies to provide customized services at a lower fee, which is an attractive factor for generations Y, Z and Alpha.

- *“ FinTech’s are definitely a threat to private banks and wealth services because they focus on those areas which are grumpiest issues, e.g., the high margin in investment/ per trading and fintech’s are specialist in it”(D-VH-21).*

All research respondents hinted about the threat ahead for traditional financial services companies from Fintech's companies if traditional wealth business does not quickly adapt their business model approach, then might be in future, Fintech's companies take over wealth services.

Transaction Cost element

The legacy processes in the WMS sector have been practised from the early industrial revolution, catering to the wealthy customer's investment requirement with tailored solutions. For ages now, wealth managers have been advising on investment advice, tax planning, trust management and retirement solutions. Thus, this advisory function requires in-depth financial instruments, regulatory framework knowledge and skill to understand and tailor the solutions, which is an expensive service. Thus product-centric approach was developed to provide customized products to wealthy customers but change transformation in the industry currently. This approach is required to transit from a product to a customer-centric approach.

4. Critical Gaps

The following are themes yielded from the analysis of data

In connection with thematically analysed data from group D, sub-themes emerged as gaps in the customer journey with the WMS firms.

D²¹: Legacy operational process

D²²: Push strategy of firms

D²³: Digital capability of Wealth Manager

According to the data analysis from group D, the following issues have merged as gaps in the current service processes model as research conducted interviews with customer segments to understand their perceptions and investing journeys experiences. It highlighted that traditional WMS firms have a push strategy while Fintech firms follow a pull strategy

- *"Initially it was not as per my requirement more selling me their product, but after some discussion, advisory understood by the objective of investing" (RP- 20-NH).*

The group D participants expressed concerns with traditional WMS service regarding the product offerings as, on many occasions, it is not relevant to their requirements but pushed by the wealth managers. The experiences shared by participants regarding onboarding journey, false claims by their relationship managers. There is a disconnect between claims by front end managers and other processing units. There is inadequate transparency and a long wait to confirm account progress and trading details.

- *“A lot depends on the quality of the relationship manager, and it would be difficult to tie that to the organisation's approach” (D-SI-22).*
- *“I personally felt in my initial meetings that products were not tailored enough to match my needs, but they kept pushing for a sale, rather than explaining to me the product and the long-term benefits. I had to gain some knowledge by reading the documents.”
(D- NH-20).*

The push strategy displays the product-centric mindset of firms rather than customer-centric there. The gap is observed and descended into cultural practices in interactions with customers.

The data highlights another crucial insight on upskilling issues in front line managers. The customer expectation with regards to their relationship/wealth manager to be financial and digital experts. However, few participants had contrast experiences to their expectations. They expressed their dissatisfaction with wealth managers regarding their inadequate digital knowledge about digital process platforms. These customer complaints are forwarded to compliance teams for resolution, which are time-consuming and lead to customer frustration.

- *“Yes, I did change my advisor as I was not happy with their advisory or the knowledge level” (D-BR-19).*
- *“I did ask for a change in advisor; however, the same advisor came back with a fresh approach, which was kind of acceptable. However, I have to probe for more details, rather than him giving out proactively” (D-NH-20)*

In a nutshell, technology is not a major pulling factor in customer shifting behaviour or expectations. The research analysis explored the underlying granular complexities within traditional WMS systems.

The push approach, inadequate product customization, and insufficient digitally upskilled talents are few critical themes yielded from the analysis and discussed in the next chapter.

4.6: Summary

Chapter four presented empirical data collected from the 23 participants within the Wealth services sector. The gathered data is thematically analysed and presented into group-wise subthemes and themes. This research explores the extent of DT and its impacts on stakeholders' perceptions from strategizing to execution of the digital transformation in the WMS sector.

This research approach is perception-based, so it adopted the stakeholder analysis to select potential participants with relevant experience in the industry specifically involved in DT transitioning. The stakeholder analysis is conducted without any bias on gender and age. Hence, each research participant is shortlisted and contacted further based on their education, experience, job roles and involvement in the digital transformation navigation in the WMS sector. The data analysis finding highlights its relevance to the literature review but contributed to developing the granular view of underlying reasons and impediments in digital navigation.

The next chapter discusses the relationship between yielded themes and sub-themes and evaluation to research questions. The outcomes of research findings are consistent with the literature but explored the inside-out perspectives by each involved stakeholder group in digital transformation planning and implementation.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

5. Introduction

Chapter five presents the detailed evaluation of the research outcomes from thematic analysis of empirical data from the four groups of executives associated with the WMS sector, at various roles and functional responsibilities. Each of participated executives is part of the ongoing digital transformation initiatives in the WMS sector. The analysis of data analysis from each group has yielded the set of sub-themes and themes presented and explained in chapter four. This chapter represents the final themes of research using the *GINC* perspective framework.

The research presents key six themes from the synthesis of group-wise themes, and each theme is further interpreted in context to literature. Moreover, the research findings unpacked vital factors from a granular view providing clarity over critical reasons indicated by existing literature and providing panoramic perceptions about the DT phenomena. The outcomes have revealed the inside-out view of factors stated as impediments in the path of the DT in the traditional WMS sector.

Chapter five structure is as follows: Section 5.1 outlines the overview of the research background and problematized scenario of the WMS sector, section 5.2 presents the *GINC* perspective framework and six main themes from thematic data analysis. Section 5.3 discusses the significance and interpretation of each theme to the available literature. Section 5.4 analyses the outcomes are connected to the research questions and evaluates if the outcomes justify as answers to these questions. Next, section 5.5 assesses the significance of research outcomes to the research participants and their perceptions. Lastly, sections 5.6 and 5.7 present the research contribution in the form recommended as “ the Capability Framework” and its significance to the current scenario in the WMS sector, and the final paragraph summarises the chapter briefly.

5.1: Overview of research

The research aimed to explore the extent and impact of Digital Transformation in the WMS sector. The adaption of the DT in traditional WMS firms primarily demands changes in the existing business model, but digital shift increases the sustainability, revenue generation and value proposition. Hence, this research plays a significant role by exhuming the critical impediments in the process of the digital shift. The outcomes of research are beneficially for decision-makers of traditional firms.

According to Sebastian et al., (2017), traditional firms struggle to cope with disruptions caused by technological advancements. The old & large companies tend to overlook internal readiness over their competencies and resources (Deloitte, 2017). Therefore, based on gaps identified in the literature review, it is essential to unpack the underlying reasons for the current situation. The following four main research questions were posited for research.

- Q 1: What is the extent and impact of DT in the Wealth Management Services sector?
- Q 2: What are the constraints and challenges in embracing the DT in a traditional WMS environment?
- Q 3: What are the critical success factors (CSFs) for digital change transitions?
- Q 4: What are the strategic capabilities essential for the successful DT change?

An extensive literature review was conducted to understand the vital information and explore the answers to research questions. The literature review provided the essential framework of a few critical factors significant in embracing the digital transitioning. The literature highlights the lack of a unified approach in the adaption of DT and late detection of competitive and influencing elements in the process, which can compress the DT transitioning movements. However, the existing literature presents brief knowledge about the DT phenomena, but available literature is focused on particular industry scenarios or case studies.

Existing literature has represented DT phenomena in hospitality, manufacturing, luxury goods and retail fashion industry or banking sectors (Agarwal et al. 2010; Valdez-de-Leon,2016; Hess,2016; Colli et al.,2018; Canetta et al., 2018). Thus, due to inadequate research literature available on the traditional WMS sector, and this gap leaves many questions about ongoing DT transitioning in the traditional sector open. Hence, the problematisation approach is adopted to examine the DT phenomenon in the chosen case study sector. According to Alvesson & Sandberg(2011), the problematisation approach of reality extends research flexibility in examining the related phenomena.

The conceptual framework of research was developed using Davis (1986) **TAM Model** and Teece's(2007) **Dynamic capability framework** to gain the panoramic view over DT and perspectives of main stakeholders from the WMS sector, followed by DT consultants finally with customers of WMS firms. The key constructs of the conceptual framework are explained briefly with relevance to the literature review outcomes. The research methodology adopted is a qualitative interpretative methodology with a phenomenological perspective using semi-structured interviews with the participants from different roles and responsibilities as well as external consultants and customers of the industry. All research stakeholders have relevant WMS background, education and experience in DT transitioning.

The thematic analysis adopted for data collected from all four groups of research participants, the analysis yielded six major themes organised into *GINC perspectives*. The key themes are discussed in the below sections.

5.2: Presentation of the research themes

The thematic analysis of empirical data from each participated group yielded eighteen main themes, but a few themes were repetitive, similar to another group of stakeholders. Hence, to avoid the similarity of themes, they are grouped under GINC components and arranged into the framework. The purpose of grouping themes into *GINC perspectives* is to understand the underlying relationships between derived themes to explore the answer to research questions. Hence, from the analysis, the final six major research themes are derived and evaluated further to connect with the literature review.

Figure 12: Major themes of research data analysis

The above-presented research findings are consistent with the literature. The derived six research themes are discussed and evaluated further to check if the findings answer the formulated research questions. The consequent research themes justify the gap in comprehending and exploring the digital transformation phenomena in the traditional WMS sector and exhumes the perspective gaps in integrating factors for embracing digital change.

The research findings fill the existing gap by exploring the underlying reasons for DT adaption failures in the traditional business ecosystem.

5.3: Interpretation of empirical findings

Notably, many researchers and practitioners have expressed the "adapt or die" situation for financial services firms due to the speed and impact of disruptions caused by technologies. Despite available expertise, resources, and skills, there is still a gap in synergising these capabilities to interlace the digital mindset and approach within the traditional WMS organisation. However, existing literature has provided some insights regarding few critical factors to align digital transformation integration but insufficient evidence of factor relevance to chose sector. Hence, to explore the inside-out view about DT perspectives, the research involved the internal stakeholders from the WMS firms followed by external DT consultants with active involvement in DT transitioning and finally with customers. The research findings have yielded six significant themes. Following is the interpretation and significance of major themes.

1. Unified approach strategy:

According to the research outcomes, there is a high acceptance and recognition of disruptive technologies like AI, big data, cloud computing, and many others, developing new revenue models and disruptive service levels in traditional settings. The major challenge faced by top management is to integrate a unified mindset and culture to adapt to the digital transitioning. On further assessment by this research through perspectives of main participants resulted in a lack of unified understanding of digital phenomena among the executives within a WMS organisation. The flow of information from top management about digital transitioning is not unified among key executives. Hence in these scenarios, the involved stakeholders' perspectives towards DT change are developed based on his/her functional role instead of an organisational goal.

The top leaders in the traditional WMS firms are focused on critical issues like business sustainability, strategizing the DT investment and swift revenue generation model, and selecting the right technology.

External factors influence traditional businesses due to disruptions in customer expectations and behaviours, which compel them to adopt the newer technologies. According to Sebastian et al.,(2017), the divide and conquer mindset is not well suited to digital transformation phenomena. In agreement with Sebastian et al.(2017), there cannot be a divide and conquer approach, as the adaption of DT needs a unified understanding of change transition with explicit knowledge of impact over the supply-chain process.

Holistically, top leaders of organisations strategically plan the concept of DT by involving the key executives from various departments, so information is cascaded further for strategy development at functional levels. However, due to legacy culture within WMS firms, the participation of key executives in core planning is limited. Resulting in a lack of complete information, confusion, and varied perceptions about DT phenomena. Hence many executives assume digitalization of internal processes as a complete digital transformation process. These findings align with literature that has defined the significance of each phase of digital transformation, but in reality, the business practices failing to integrate an approach, unified understanding and culture.

The groups B and C participants revealed inadequate knowledge at board management levels about the scope of technology and DT, which acts as fences around the existing legacy model. This avoids developing a digital ecosystem by transforming the traditional business model of WMS organisations. The major reasons quoted in the outcomes are that budget constraints or buy-in decisions from top management stakeholders are impediments in the path of DT. On the contrary, the top management executives expressed their fear of losing out on existing revenue generation model-specific from the advisory business unit by automating it.

2. Impact of barrier elements at the stakeholder levels

According to Andrus et al.,(2017), 90% of traditional financial services organisations attempt to be digital champions (Deloitte report,2017). However, the latest report by Deloitte Consulting(2020) on financial services firms confirms that only 10% of traditional WMS firms have comprehensive and strategic understanding, which is leading them into the digital maturity category (*Industry 4.0*, Deloitte,2020). The research findings align with the above information on industry statistics about DT transitioning by wealth management firms.

As discussed in earlier chapter four, critical barriers have a tumbling impact on involved stakeholders roles and functional responsibilities in the case study sector.

The research conducted interviews initially with three groups of executives in different roles and responsibilities to have a panoramic view of critical challenges in the digital transitioning process. The research outcomes show an interlinked relationship between factors principally and the various barriers in embracing digital mindset, and these barriers are again different for each stakeholder in the process. Hence this research conducted the concluding interviews with customers of WMS firms to understand their perspectives over this phenomenon and barriers, as they are a crucial part of change transformation.

For customer stakeholders, the barrier highlighted was the repetitive changes undertaken by traditional WMS firms in digitalization of the administrative & other processes, which confuses their decision-making ability on investments and trading. They admitted that firms provide excess information related to undergoing digital change but lack handholding in the smooth transition of customers from legacy to digital ways of managing their investment accounts.

Meanwhile, existing literature holds the culture as a critical factor in integrating relationship development and synchronising into expected vision. However, research findings indicate the product-centric approach rather than the customer-centric approach, and the customer stakeholder participants confirm the mismatch of their expectations and services offered by traditional firms. In the context of WMS firms, the trust factor is vital between wealth managers and customers, and these mismatch factors can soar the loyalty of customers.

According to the group D findings, these external DT consultants expressed exploitation to know competitors' DT planning and investments, as they tend to work on various DT projects in the same sector. The lack of continuous training and technical knowledge about technology upgrades at the management creates resistance and budget approvals in the customization of traditional processes.

The identified critical barriers from participated groups A & B impede the process of embracing the DT in unifying the understanding of vision set from digital transitioning and common mindset and approach among all stakeholders.

Leaders face a critical challenge in setting the right culture and technology for the organisation, translating the vision into functional roles and targets among employees. Another critical barrier explored is constant regulatory changes by the financial watchdog (FCA) with their objective to secure the interest of customers funds, data, and cybersecurity, limiting the adaption of DT.

3. Strategic change practice: Innovative practices

The WMS firms operate in a dynamic environment that encounters constant external volatility that impacts the capital markets offerings to clients. Due to macro and micro changes, market volatility induces the necessary regulatory changes impacting the WMS organisation's strategic plans and investments towards digital transformation.

The findings indicate the relationship between the various barrier elements in developing the digital mindset and culture within the traditional wealth services firms. As indicated earlier in chapter two, identified two different approaches adopted by WMS firms, firstly, targeting the right technology to adopt then integrating the resources and capabilities around. Secondly focus, on developing the right mindset and approach with strategic capabilities and then embracing the right technology advancement to transform the business model. The research findings claim both approaches are right but strongly linked with the organisation's digital maturity to adapt quickly.

Hence, the findings hold significance in bringing clarity over the obstructive perceptions of stakeholders, which can derail the efforts towards transformation. The WMS business model is primarily built on trust and relationship factors, while earlier researchers (Oilver, 2010; Ross et al., 2016; Hartl and Hess,2017) have emphasised that communication and visibility are crucial ingredients for nurturing goodwill, trust and relationship factors. However, in the current scenario, the frequent changes in technology, disruption of service model and regulatory framework impacts the cementing factors of trust and relationships with customers. Thus, the result suggested the "Digital Twin concept" for traditional firms.

The Digital twin is creating a prototype of the critical processes to upgrade and identify the obstacles without hampering the customers' front-end service offering. The changes accommodated as per regulations and enhancements required to officiate customer service value creation.

Samuel,(2018) states that for the digital transformation process to be successful, then use many enablers to make it happen, not just technology but also the alignment of vision with business models through the medium of technology through digital twin can be achieved.

The concept of the digital twin serves dual solutions in traditional WMS settings. Firstly, the internal legacy processes are the hiccups of processes integration. With digital twinning, the front, back, and middle processes can be integrated by creating the prototype of these legacy processes, transforming and verifying these processes before opening the application to the end-user. Secondly, it meets the customer expectations of the speedy, efficient and accurate process without frequent changes.

4. Limitations and constraints: Legacy business model

The Wealth Management Services sector existence dates back from the 1933 era(Fowler, 1933). In the early years, the Wealth services firms provided all types of financial services in investment, tax, regulations to all customer segments. During the 1970s, companies like Goldman Sachs, Morgan Stanley, and a few others initiated exclusive services in consultation and advisory to wealthy customers(Traff, 2016). This enhanced consultation involves the wealth manager/relationship managers nurturing the trust and confidence of customers to increase the loyalty element. Thus, the WMS firms are continuing with a traditional business model from the era of the 1970s. However, in the current scenario in the WMS sector, disruptions are caused by rapid technological advancements that impact traditional business operations and compel firms to adapt to changing ecosystems. The research findings highlighted that the younger generation Y&Z are inquisitive and experimental, so they are interested in managing their investment portfolio supported by wealth managers with more data visibility. At the same time, traditional wealth managers are uncertain about their job role, as technology might empower the customer, and their job role might turn from advisory to more of execution roles.

Another significant research findings explored the changing landscape in the customer market base. With growing numbers of young customers using wealth services, the impact of technology has made the “Alpha” generation think about their investments and higher expectations.

With this changing landscape of the customer market, the younger generation is less interested in the current traditional advisory process and more keep towards agile digital ways practised by fintech firms. According to a report by HBR(2019), around 2.2m people invest through traditional WMS firms, the segmentation of services is linked with fees generated from investment portfolio size. Currently, fintech firms are invading a larger market share due to their digital adaption in providing agile, efficient and customized services at lesser fees than traditional WMS firms.

The change of leaders (specifically CEO, CTO and CDO) in mid of the digital transformation cycle creates turbulence across the organisation, causing a disturbance in the smooth transitioning and implementation process. New leaders' funding strategy and approach in setting vision and integrating new culture bring confusion and a resistant environment. Few participants expressed their experiences under new leadership in mid of DT implementation delayed the project due to differences in mindset approach and leadership style.

5. Capability impact.

As per the report on the industry by Oliver Wyman(2020), top leaders of financial firms feel 50% of their digital spending is wasted without even knowing the reasons or factors responsible for wastage. Hence this scenario pulls attention to the capability element in digital transformation, which is a critical need in the digital transitions of the traditional firms. This research adopted the Dynamic Capability framework model(Teece et al., 1997) and the TAM model (Davis, 1989) in developing the conceptual framework for the further research process, specifically addressing the requirement of sensing, seizing, and transforming as foundational elements of capability for digital transformational change. The research findings contributed to exploring these three elements of the DC model are very significant in identifying the synergistic and inertia factors in the vertical and horizontal implementation, which impedes the transformation.

According to the synthesis of subthemes and themes, there are varied expectations like raising customer expectations of WMS firms. The regulatory requirements and industry influences by adapting to new capability leveraging technologies to track the customer behaviour trends.

The usage of data in building the customer-centric approach and hybrid business by adapting the digital twinning in the internal process to provide a better approach to the customer as well as business impact.

6. Learnings from failures

According to the available literature and industry reports, a significantly lower percentage of companies learn from their mistakes in practice. The research outcomes indicate that the cultural mindset & approach is crucial to success in digital transformational change. The research explored various deeper issues from human side complexities at participants level within various organisations resulting in new outcomes about failures.

- A. The vision and strategy discussions are limited to only a few sections of people within an organisation. This approach creates resistance and a panic environment about automating the back & middle office, resulting in fear of job loss.
- B. Top management and leaders are involved in integrating the resources towards set goals. The pre and post-digital strategizing do not showcase the involvement in every level of executives associated with organisations. The outcome of research explored that many executives believe that DT is the automation of existing processes to simplify the process and reduce the time for each job task. Hence there is a lack of flow of communication vertically as well horizontally within the organisation
- C. The digital skills enhancement training for front office teams like marketing and advisory team is critical in creating better client relationships, acquisitions and retention.
- D. Research findings revealed the challenge ageing advisory professionals are retiring faster than new generation advisors joining on board. This leaves a gap for new-generation customers to switch over to competitors for comprehensive and agile services. Talent harvesting is an inevitable solution to current challenges and opportunities as well.

5.4: The answers to the research questions

Based on the thematic analysis of collected data, the following six themes are derived from a synthesis of sub-themes from all participated stakeholder groups, and the outcomes find the answers to raised research questions.

- ***Q.1: What is the extent and impact of DT in the Wealth Management Services sector?***

The review of the literature identified two approaches, *firstly*, "with technology being the centre argument of strategy and organisations align themselves towards it" (Fichman et al., 2014; Hess et al., 2016; Vial, 2019; Collin et al., 2015). *Secondly*, organisations focus on specific dynamic capabilities and then adapt to the right technology to meet the digital transformational aim (Morakanyane et al., 2017; Aldrich & Ruef, 2006; Vial, 2019; Liu et al., 2011). Thus, however, it is evident that technology and capabilities are the most critical variables of the DT transitions. Having known the criticality of these factors, not necessarily these approaches are successful in embracing the DT. The financial research consulting firm, Nucoro's reveals that 84% of firms fail in wiring their competencies towards the DT objectives despite capabilities and resources (Further challenges of Wealth Management, 2020). Hence to explore the missing pieces in the digital transformation phenomena, the research involved the relevant executives from the WMS industry in understanding their perceptions in defining the underlying extent and digital transformational impact.

According to the literature review, it's seen that researchers have agreed on the significance of human-technology links irrespective of various research case studies (Kotter, 2012; Schwertner, 2017; Kane, 2017; Kohnke, 2017; OECD, 2018; Deloitte, 2018). Knowing the two factors critical in digital transitioning of traditional firms, what approach to be adopted based on capability and vision of leaders within an organisation (Fitzgerald et al. 2013; Oberer & Erkollar, 2018; Kane, 2017; Kohnke, 2017) which determines the maturity state of the organisations (Aldrich & Ruef, 2006; Kane, 2017c; Hartl & Hess, 2017; Osmundsen et al., 2018a; Vial 2019) in integrating all resources leveraging the technology for co-creating the efficient revenue-generating business model.

The findings of the research are in line with the available literature on defining the phenomena of DT. The results revealed that perception of DT is formed from with executive's functional background within the organisation. Hence research outcomes argue that lack of visibility on change transitions will lead to constructing their version of DT around their conclave of functional responsibilities rather than co-creating towards meeting organisational value proposition.

Thus research confirms the critical role of leaders in co-creating vision and percolating that vision horizontally and vertically for building the scope to potentialize from digital transformation.

The scope of findings is coherent with available literature over the obstruction elements in DT implementation due to traditional firm's size and structure factors (Teece, Pisano & Shuen,1997; Chan et al., 2006). Findings revealed the importance of flat hierarchical structure in alignment aspects, control dimensions, process and implementation is much easier in the communication flow.

The conceptual framework of research displays the identified influencing and compelling factors in the WMS sector in embracing the change adaptation. However, the findings bring the reality of polarisation in the DT approach by stakeholders. The literature indicates that dynamic fintechs firms are growing concerns for traditional firms as they invade customer markets. However, research outcomes explored that fintech is just one influencing element but shifting customer expectations, ageing of advisory and disruption in an advisory function.

These compelling factors tend to influence firms to evolve for business sustainability factors adapting to digital change. The critical question "whether organisations need to change?" arises from the literature review and secondary sources in the context of WMS organisations. The disruptions in the traditional service model compel the firms to adapt to meet the speed of normality of evolution. The research findings revealed that most of the board members(C-suites members, investors) lack adequate knowledge and technical awareness that impacts budget approvals or investment buy-in from management stakeholders

The above-discussed factors are crucial in defining the extent and expected impact of adopting the DT transition. The following factors are (a) unified approach and complete visibility of expected change across the organisations. (b) involvement of top management and core teams as co-creators of a new value proposition. (c) the flexibility of size and structural changes for communication flow. d) The clarity on vision and roles in the current and expected state of organizational transition will bring employees at all levels into an agreeable state of mindset for digital change.

Q 2: What are the constraints and challenges in embracing the DT in a traditional WMS environment?

There is inadequate evidence showing the relationships and factors impacting traditional WMS services digital transitioning journey. According to Behnam et al. (2019), reveals the investment of \$1.3 trillion was spent till 2018, and around \$900 billion was wasted in financial service transformation. The literature indicates the investment wastage linked with leaders ability to steer the projects and integrate all crucial elements with DT vision, but there is no reasons discussed or any evidence on investment wastages within the literature.

Literature shows the relationship between vision alignment, strategic leadership, and capability aspects (Liu et al.,2011; Mullen,2013; Matt et al.,2014; Hess et al.,2016; Morakanyane et al.,2017; Vial, 2019). According to literature, business scalability and value creation can be possible by leveraging technology (Kohli and Melville 2018; Lucas et al.. 2013). However, other researchers argue that only technology cannot create to value existing services (Matt, Hess & Benlian, 2015; Gerow et al.,2014; Renaud, Walsh & Kalika, 2016).

The relationship between the role of leader and capability in aligning the culture is most critical. Hence, the phenomenological research approach explored the human side of constraints and challenges that executives encountered in embracing the digital transformation change.

Research respondents indicated that digital maturity is vital for traditional organisations marching towards DT transition(Vial,2019; Lawton, 2015; Kaufman & Horton,2015). The research outcomes exhumed the granular view over the current issues of traditional firms in matching the speed of technology advancements.

Lack of talent and knowledge upskilling is another critical issue that emerged in data analysis, and the advisory executives (wealth managers and relationship managers) are retiring is faster than hiring young talents for this role. The research outcomes explored the polarised perspectives from senior executives over cannibalization of the existing business model by automating it completely. Few respondents from group B showed resistance towards Robo advisor's application to all customer segments, which will harm the value chain and touchpoints in customer management. Similarly, outcomes indicate the fear of the advisory role diminishing into more of executionary role. Hence there seems to be an inertia factor development in adapting the digital transitioning and acceptance of automation of business model, and thus inertia within organisations creates pressure on top management.

As per the Deloitte report (Industry 4.0 study. 2020), a survey reveals only 10% of financial services companies are matured with a comprehensive and strategic view. In this aspect, the majority of firms are ad -hoc decision-makers, according to a report. All respondents from four groups have linked the digital maturity approach with the organisational readiness to leadership quotient within firms. Digital readiness is culture and capability evolution by top management or leader by synching the mindset and culture towards fixing the issues with strategic planning. Although digital transformation has been agenda for leaders for a decade, the change process is conducted horizontally rather than vertically. The flow of information should be cascading to each key member of departments so strategic plans can be passed on to the functional team. However, in the current scenario, the firms are adopting a horizontal approach disseminating the communication in cohesive integration of business & functional level units.

In an analysis of research findings, the customer's participants questioned their perceptions of challenges experiences in their investment process. The outcomes of the analysis reveal the underlying reasons for the behaviour change.

1. Due to the push approach of wealth services firms, there is a gap in understanding the customer expectations and product suitability, which results in customers shifting to new investment firms.

2. In the current scenario, DT strategy should be linked with the customer they serve, as the expectation of each customer segment is different, younger customers are experimental with fintech digital apps while baby boomers and millennials still looking forward to having a human advisor for their investment planning.
3. The other reason for switching the traditional WMS firms is the transaction fees, higher in traditional WMS firms than fintech firms, which is the most attractive feature for first-time investors and young customers.
4. The data analysis indicates inadequate digital knowledge and upskilling among ageing wealth managers, which is a hurdle in the smooth transition from legacy to digital. Due to various factors unearthed in research findings, administrative processing delays the customer onboarding experiences, and excess information creates confusion in using digital platforms without much hand-holding from firms.

Q 3: What are the critical success factors (CSFs) for digital change transitions?

This research intended to explore the DT context and analysed data drawn together to zoom the CSFs in the research theme. The CSFs are the characteristics, elements, variables or factors, which enhances impact in creating successful impact if appropriately managed (Leidecker et al., 2018). The research outcomes were derived from semi-structured interviews with industry executives from various roles and the phenomenological objective to explore the relationship of themes from embracing to execution of DT changes practices.

The findings are pertinent to themes drawn from the literature, and each participant questioned their perspectives over the critical success factors in the scope of regulatory, leadership, and implementation strategy aspects in building the CSFs. The primary outline of framed questions entailed relevant sub-questions for the above question.

1. What is the outlook about CSFs from the organisation's journey starting from embracing to executing DT strategy?
2. What are external and internal factors in building the digital readiness of an organisation?
3. How can the digital readiness element be measured?

The research findings are significant to the current industry scenario as they provide inside-out perspectives. Digital maturity of organisation resulted as a vital factor in transformation concept.

1. Leadership is the main ingredient for preparing foreground for DT within the organisation, and this finding is aligned with the literature review. The leader's role in steering the change movement within the organisations (Kane, 2017; Oberer & Erkollar, 2018; Wade et al., 2017) is like the maestro of the digital transformation orchestra. Similarly, in the WMS sector, the role of a leader is crucial in sensing external factors and developing the culture by aligning the resources and capabilities.
2. As per Prahalad & Hamel(1994), organisations need to transform themselves before initiating the transformation for others. The research agrees with the statement, as top leaders of organisations require a transformative approach and knowledge before steering the change journey. The causation of failures is concluded towards issues apart from technology, and only technology cannot add value to the entire process. CSFs in context to digital transformation start with the firm's leader, with clarity on the purpose of adopting digital change followed by strategic planning on what requires change and how to implement the transformative change. The research outcome is in line with the approach of management researchers(Yokoi et al., 2009; Kagerman et al., 2013; Wade et al., 2017; Kane, 2017; Porfírio et al., 2021)
3. The other CSFs explored by data analysis are the size and structure of the organisation, which are essential factors in disseminating the communication horizontally and vertically, facilitating the control and implementation mechanisms to avoid any alignment of complex internal processes.
4. Developing an integrated approach by syncing the understanding of all employees by providing clarity on current and expected change and required transformation in job roles. This level of transparency will be helpful in the creation of the right mindset and culture-building towards the acceptance of the digital change.
5. The involvement of top management is critical in every stage of DT currently, research findings indicate the traditional service companies are using a push approach strategy instead of a pull strategy.

6. Currently, this research analysis reveals the legacy firms are using the same approach model for approaching young customers (gen Y,Z &Alpha), which is a mismatch in creating the touchpoints for customer loyalty.
7. The board-level management and private equity investors have inadequate technological expertise and knowledge but expect quicker ROI. The tighter regulatory frameworks and other challenges develop inflexibility at the execution committee like CEO, CTO & CDO.

Q 4: What are the strategic capabilities essential for the successful DT change?

The organisational capabilities are the backbone for the CSFs, for creating the value proposition. The answer to question four is integrated with above question three. The research outcomes resulted in exploring the critical CSFs, which answers the question focusing on determining the strategic capability quotient of the traditional WMS sector. The relevant definition of capability in the context of the DT is coined by David Teece (1997) “ as “the firm’s ability to integrate, build and reconfigure its external and internal competencies to address rapidly changing environment”(Teece et al.,1997, p. 516). With the context to nature of the WMS business model, the legacy advisory consultation for wealthy customers is highly sought to continue in similar present order with agile and efficient to reduce the administrative processing time. The confluence of legacy and agile methods is the digitally transformed way to create a value proposition. This finding agrees with Svahn(2017), who emphasised balancing existing and innovative capabilities by a clear path dependencies strategy.

Based on the discussion in the above paragraph about constraints and challenges as well as CSFs. Building the capability is interlinked with what customer segment of the firms is targetting. Each firm in the traditional Wealth Management sector caters to a specific set of customers based on their investment capability, risk-taking ability and expected returns and requirements. Hence the firms' DT scalability plans should be linked with the market base they provide or planning to extend their services.

The research findings show that UHNI (ultra-high network customers) are looking only at the human- advisory rather than the Robo advisor model, while the younger generation (Y, Z and Alpha) are keen to try Robo advisory. Every customer from various segments who participated in research has shown dissatisfaction in back-office and administration processing time and delays in providing visibility over their investment portfolio, which takes a very long time from the onboarding time.

The research finding reveals that traditional firms lack the swiftness to adapt to the wave of disruptive changes caused by technological innovation and the reasons explained above. This finding is relevant as industry reports by Peter Bendor-Samuel (2018) also indicate that 70% of firms disappearing from their listings due to the inability to match the speed of technology(Forbes,2018) as well as Weill and Woerner(2013: 2015) briefs the reason for failures in integration deficiencies in calibrating the capabilities and resources.

5.5: Significance of findings to the research participants

Holistically, the research findings have identified the factors that obstruct smooth transitioning and embracing the DT objectives. The research explores executives' perspectives from different hierarchies associated internally and externally with the traditional WMS sector. Following is the relationship between research findings with the role of participants presented in diagrammatic format.

1. Senior Management (CEO, CTO, Managing directors and Partners).

The research agrees with existing literature emphasising findings on the role of senior management in creating the right mindset and culture in adopting the digital transformation. The research has also explored the constraints and challenges at the top management and leaders level, which deters holistically from strategizing the digital plan to the execution level. The DT planning is a top-down approach, and research findings explored that the implementation strategy is cascaded horizontal rather than vertical on the practical side. However, this research argues that a strategic plan and implementation phases should be customised based on organisation size and structure depending on the complexity of the project undertaken in dynamic business settings. This approach cannot become rigid.

The outcomes are in line with the conceptual framework of research. The senior management should have key pillars for building digital culture on sensing, seizing and transforming (Teece et al.,1997). In particular, to research participants creating a unified understanding of DT aims, clear communication flow about the digital road map for firms. The identification of internal maturity and readiness towards digital scalability. Developing the clarity from top to bottom level about change transition with clear visibility on existing stage to expected state of transformation within the organisation. The breaking down transformation process-wise will bring conceptual clarity within people involved in the process about the pros and cons of DT.

2. Middle Management Level: Wealth/ Relationship Managers

As their role closely linked the customers, the middle management executives are known to be the organisation's ambassadors as they represent the firm, the vision and deliver the value chain by front-ending with customers. Hence they are the catalyst between the organisation and the customers, and they play a key role in creating value through service delivery, which is a critical part of wealth manager's roles.

The research findings have explored from research stakeholders about their perspectives and challenges encountered in embracing the digital transitioning as well as deliverables. The key factors associated with these roles are relationship management, trust factor, and value creation.

The various constraints and limitations at the middle are as follows: Inadequate clarity on DT phenomena, due to limited sharing by top management, chaos and the fear-like situation at this stakeholder level arises. The growing concern over disruptions at the advisory level might transform their role into only executing customer orders. The most critical challenge encountered by front end executives is customer acquisition in traditional WMS firms. Continuous education and upskilling of wealth/ relationship managers will create a smooth experience in transitioning the customers from the legacy process and value creation. Lack of preparedness to cater for the younger customers due to legacy processes and manual processes. The mixed opinion and perception over the fintech invasion in the traditional wealth service sector.

3. External DT experts: Technology Consultants.

The DT experts are external consultants to the WMS firms, and these experts support the firms in identifying, planning and implementing the transformation of legacy processes as DT objectives. In doing so, DT experts observed the following constraints and challenges: Lack of support and management buy-in approach, delaying the complete transformation of legacy processes. Inadequate technology awareness and technical knowledge at top management create issues in the organisation's implementation phases of digitalization, digitisation, and digital transformation. Due to the high cost of DT, many projects are shelved halfway through the process. Lastly, these DT experts believe that traditional WMS firms often hire them to extract information about their competitors rather than digital transformation aim.

The following research findings on capabilities are structured into a diagram format relevant to specific capabilities critical to each stakeholder's role discussed above.

Figure 13: The capability flow in focus to critical roles in the WMS firms (Author's illustration from the research findings)

5.6: The research contribution: The “ Capability Funnel Framework.”

The research study has explored the DT phenomena within traditional WMS firms in the London city region. Based on the results generated from research, relationships between the factors indicated by earlier literature are relevant. However, the relevance of research findings is significant, as they increase the clarity and scope of DT in an organisational ecosystem. This research has explored why traditional WMS firms derail from DT transitioning despite capabilities and resource availability, hence the extent and impact of the Digital transformation to now more clearly and connected. Thus, the research explored the critical success factors(CSFs), challenges, constraints and capabilities of traditional WMS firms.

Hence, based on the literature gap identified at the beginning of the research, the research outcomes have answered each question by concluding the research to recommend the framework for smooth transitioning of traditional firms by creating digital fluidity within the business ecosystem. The proposed framework, “ the capability funnel,” can be implemented within the business organisation in three stages. The significance of capability funnelling stages to develop the internal capability and competencies for adapting to execution is explained in brief below.

Holistically, according to the literature review of academia and industry sources, the current industries’ scenario depicts the change spillover of the industrial revolution wave. The WMS sector has fundamental traditional values, trust, and relationships as their core qualities in their existing business model, but the current disruptions are caused due to technology, an imperative factor in the services model disruptions. The suggested diagram of the “ Circular Transformation Cycle”(p. 66) provides the relevance of changes occurring in the i4.0 era (the fourth industrial revolution). The traditional WMS firm is inventing their business model, innovating their set legacy process for the sustainability of the business from fintech firms invasion, fintech concept is a product of this financial innovation concept. The diffusion is to identify the stakeholders in the process of adaption of DT and creation refers to classify the critical aspects in the change process and customize according to customer expectations and behaviour aspects close the circular transformation cycle.

Figure 14: The proposed “The Capability Funnel Framework”.

1. Stage One: In continuation to the above discussion, according to the recommended framework, it starts from the circular transformation cycle, the journey from the current state to the expected state of the transformed organisation. Stage one starts with the identification of external, internal influencing and compelling factors. As discussed briefly in an earlier paragraph, the sensing capability is the most critical aspect of change transformations (Teece et al.,1997). The organisation's leaders play a significant role in steering the change practices by explicitly analysing external and internal critical elements.

Influencing factors

The decision of adopting Digital Transformation is primarily involved top management and leaders in the WMS sectors. The analysed data presents the elements like rising competition, technology, regulatory changes inducing the changes in transaction fees are key influencing factors in WMS organisation.

Compelling factors

Many factors interlinked in creating the impact on traditional firms to adapt the DT, but the following identified crucial factors, which compels to change the existing business model by embracing the technology as an imperative factor. The business sustainability, growth of fintechs, shifting behaviour of customers enforce the change initiatives.

Wealth services firms are traditional in nature because of their business model. Leadership has a significant role in bringing up the vertical approach in integrating employees' mindset towards gearing the digital culture within companies, which will help create the fluidity culture to meet customer stakeholders' expectations. For impactful change implementation, the organisation's structure and size significantly link with digital transformation success. Author Chan et al.,(2006) emphasized that success factors for any transformational change are domain knowledge and prior success.

The alignment mechanism within organisations will be different in every business. The factors, lean structure and size are flexible and less hierarchical, wherein the Circular Transformation Cycle can be implemented (Figure no. 4).

Considering a behavioural change of customers, discussed briefly in chapter five, there were conflicting sub-themes, but after evaluating through the narratives repeatedly, indicated the digital acceptance level differs in different age groups of customers. The traditional firms have a competitive edge compare to fintech companies on the existing database to evaluate in-depth through big data, to understand the patterns and trends of customers expectations. Hence, companies can leverage technology to create customized services lines and digital upskilling of frontline managers to navigate digital platters of transformed services.

2. Stage two: This stage answers the research questions by identifying the capabilities regarding digital change transitioning. The research study explored the critical success factors for successful transformation in the traditional WMS sector. Stage two, critically linked with the gap identified in chapter two, the literature review. The capability framework (Fig.24, p.198) discussed the significant capabilities of developing the organisation's unified digital mindset approach.

The *GINC* framework(Fig 17,p.124) represents the pertinent gaps, issues, needs and capabilities in digital culture in traditional wealth services companies. In contrast, few outcomes indicated the delay in digital adaption in fear of the business model's cannibalisation. Thus, top-management roles are crucial in assessing present gaps, developing a clear digital strategy for impactful change towards digital transformation, and analysing the existing capability calibrations of internal and external resources. The integration of people, products and processes, is a foundational requirement for the DT. The themes observed from the *GINC* framework's analysis play the crucial role of organisational maturity linked with the digital transformation's success. Traditional companies link the success factors with knowledge of top management are success in past (Chan et al. 2006). The research revealed the constraints at top management levels in addressing the change successfully.

3. Stage Three: Assessing core capabilities identified through the *GINC* framework, not necessarily every firm or business will require the same capability component. Based on Teece (1997), the three main components, sensing, seizing and transforming, are generalized to all industries, but micro-foundations of dynamic capability framework require tailored to specific industry gaps.

Hence, regarding the impact of exogenous and endogenous factors over the WMS firms, the identified exogenous factors like competition, disruptive services and fintech competition, and endogenous factors are management approach, varied perceptions of DT, culture and business model.

Thus, critical contributions in the shape of capabilities to resolve these issues to embrace DT are multi capabilities like developing the unified approach by top management to clarify the future business model and value. Secondly, the advisory is the heart of the wealth services business. It needs to approach the hybrid model to reduce the interoffice operational time-consuming process into agile services. It is implementable through internal technology upskilling or synergising with fintech expertise for niche services. Thirdly, after evaluating the talent search challenges, talent harvesting is ideal for traditional companies with clarity on the long transparency on the strategic planning of organizational vision. The hybrid approach's adaption will be able to attract new talents to the wealth services segment.

Last and foremost, to avoid the massive investment wastage in digital transformation due to varied reasons can be avoided by introducing digital twin technique by creating the replica of the physical process with the help of disruptive technologies like AI and IoT will be a benefit in dual ways to reduce the operational costs and erosion of organisational value. The disruptions of services impact every function within the organisation. Most of the traditional firms are sailing in similar tides of digital change in financial services. Thus, developing a competitive advantage will be a sustainable tool for traditional organisations.

5.7: Summary

To summarise chapter five, this research investigated the gaps identified in the literature review. The review indicated two perspectives underlying within available literature. Firstly, organisations align their capabilities and resources to adopt the right technology, overlooking the organisation readiness. The second perspective identified is by developing the capabilities and maturity level of the organisation to adapt to the technological disruptions, as there was inadequate clarity on the relevance of factors to the WMS sector. Thus, findings from data analysis connected with the literature review and practical implications from the business point of view.

The chapter discusses the outcomes of the findings and validates if the findings justify by filling the gaps identified in the literature review chapter. The six major research themes explain the extent and underlying relationship and reasons impacting traditional organisations embracing the DT. The chapter highlights the significance of identified capabilities in relevance to critical positions within the sector. Hence research brings clarity about constraints and limitations at each strategic hierarchy level which is inadequate in literature.

The findings highlighted in this chapter reveal the critical underlying issues which crop up as impediments in the digital journey of organisations. Again these critical factors are specific to the WMS sector's ecosystem and culture. These outcomes have recommended the framework, "Capability Funnel Framework", stage-wise to create the fluidity towards creating a digital mindset and approach.

Chapter six revisits the research aim and objectives relevant to the recommended framework and discusses the theoretical and practical contribution of research.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSIONS

6. Introduction

The previous chapter provided the outcomes and discussion on findings, briefly connecting back to the literature review chapter. Chapter five presented the findings from each group, its relationship, and justifications. These outcomes resulted in comprehending the critical capabilities essential at specific levels with the traditional WMS firms and recommendations of the research framework.

Chapter six is the concluding chapter of the research, which will be revisiting the research aim and objectives as verifying the connectivity of research outcomes with literature. This research section will discuss the theoretical, practical contributions and implications to the chosen WMS sector reflect on the research limitations, learnings, and the scope of future research.

Chapter six structure is as follows: Section 6.1, 6.2 provides the summary of the introduction to the chapter and research overview so far, outlining the connection of the research outcomes with literature. Section 6.3 and 6.4 explains the theoretical research contributions and practice implications in respective to the chosen case sector of the Wealth Management sector, discussing the numerous contributions and their alignment to research gaps. Section 6.6 revisits the research aim and objectives, this section validates the research outcomes in relationship with research questions, and lastly, 6.7 and 6.8 presents reflections of the DBA journey and concluding comments of the research.

6.1: Research Overview

For the decade now, technology has been an imperative factor in the sustainability of any business across all industries. Similarly, in context with the research case study, the WMS sector is always on the cusp of digital transformation as technological advancements are much faster than the speed of adapting to it. The undermining issue of failures to adapt the digital change is linked with various factors specific to the nature of businesses. Hence this research aimed to explore the extent and impact of DT in the traditional WMS sector.

The intellectual justification for research locates its contribution within the broader field of strategic management, as this thesis explored the multifaceted role of the DT phenomenon on traditional wealth services firms. The research assessed the challenges, constraints and critical success factors which explored the division of the existing mindset approach, which derails the attempt towards the transformation. As per Sebastian et al. (2017), the divide and conquer mindset is not well suited to digital transformation. These approaches were significant strategic in the calibration of internal process mechanisms for the successful implementation of digital transformation.

The exploration to comprehend the DT phenomena resulted in diverse approaches to digital transformation. Hence explored the perspectives to define this digital phenomenon from researchers with transdisciplinary backgrounds (Agarwal et al.,2010; Valdez-de-Leon,2016; Hess et al., 2016; Colli et al.,2018; Herrmann et al.,2018; Kossowski et al.,2020) established the outlook in generally that digital transformation phenomena cannot be generalised as its supporting parameters linked to nature of business transforming. The review of the current scenario within the WMS sector indicated the tremendous external pressure compelling these traditional firms to adapt to the newer business model forcefully.

The WMS firms are known for their traditional business model, the combined form services inclusive of three departments, creating a value proposition. The back-office team manages customer onboarding processing and administration related activities, and the middle office manages risk, compliance and technology-related task, while the last is the front-office team, managing the customer acquisitions, relationship management and advisory.

The Integration of these three teams is crucial in providing efficient and effective services to customers/ clients in their investment profile. However, the review of literature from practitioners reveals the lack of unified understanding among these teams, which is related to the role of the leadership management team in disseminating knowledge and training across all levels in the organisation(Rogers,1962; Fitzgerald et al.,2014; Bharadwaj et al.,2013). The research strongly agrees with earlier researchers about the significance of leadership in digital change transitions. However, research clarifies the constraints at top-management and leaders in developing the right approach with the organisation as there was inadequate clarity over the constraints and role of leaders specific to the WMS business.

The research study identified the significance of an innovative approach in the traditional business model. Fintech is currently successfully providing efficient and agile services to their clients, thus creating pressure over the traditional firms to innovate their service level to customers. Technology being imperative and the primary influencer in changing the behavioural patterns of customers. Hence, research contributed to developing the Circular Transformation Cycle (p.66), which is most relevant for the sustainability of the traditional business model.

The literature reviews outcomes establish the gap; firstly, the case sector is under-researched in academia. Hence there is a lack of concrete evidence of factors and elements impacting the DT derailment of efforts by the organisation. Moreover, the existing literature is split into two approaches. The first approach emphasised imperativeness of technology be held higher in integrating the capabilities and resources around it (Fichman et al.,2014; Hess et al.,2016; Vial,2019; Collin et al.,2015) and following researchers, Liu et al. (2011); Morakanyane et al., (2017); Aldrich & Ruef(2006) and Vial(2019) argues of importance dynamic capability development prior choosing the technology for successful digital transitioning.

The conceptual framework of research is presented in chapter two and discussed briefly (p.90). The framework is a confluence of a critical set of components from the TAM model (Davis,1989) and Teece et al.,(2007) Dynamic capability framework. The conceptual framework is relevant to gaps identified in the literature review for further investigation of research.

In connection to the conceptual framework, the qualitative research methodology is adopted to explore the perceptions phenomenologically from stakeholders of the WMS firms associated internal and external. Chapter three explains and justifies choosing the qualitative methodology with interpretive paradigm and inductive methods for data collection. The research study interviewed 23 participants, including executives from the top management leadership team, wealth managers, external DT consultants, and customers/clients of the WMS firms.

Chapter four provided the findings from thematic analysis of data collected, and the outcomes presented the relevant and critical sub-themes and themes group-wise. Hence, significant themes from each group are drawn into main research themes to avoid repetition. Hence, the analysis yielded six major research themes, briefly explained and verified if they answered the raised research questions in chapter five.

The discussion chapter discusses the outcomes of the research. It maps the findings to the research gaps identified and questions raised. The main findings of the research resulted in developing the critical capabilities at key participants functional roles and the significance of integrating the mapped capabilities towards developing the recommended framework of research, “ Capability funnel framework.” It is interesting to find out that cause of failure within an organisation is not technology but very general key factors that traditional organisations have propensities to ignore to focus and align these factors. The findings of the research are found consistent with the literature review.

6.2: Theoretical contribution

The research outcomes align with the literature contributed in comprehending the extent of factors involved in the DT adaption precisely focused on the WMS sector. The research has the following contributions to existing literature and knowledge body.

1. The research has contributed to the growing body of knowledge by conducting the research study in the traditional WMS business sector, which remained under-researched in an academic field. This exploratory research presents the individuals' perspectives on the extent and impact of the DT in chosen case study sector.

2. Each research contributes to understanding the DT phenomena and its driving factors, but this research attempted to exhume the facts and elements impediments to the process of digital transitioning specific to the WMS sectors. Hence this is a novel contribution to the body of knowledge.
3. The literature review identified two imperative factors: technology and capability, critical in the change transformation process (Appx 5,p.252). The central gap revealed is the fragmented understanding of the DT phenomena. The process of planning, extent, scalability and impact over the existing function, roles and business model is unclear among the executives involved in digital change planning.
4. The significant contribution of the research is the outcomes resulting from the findings, which presents the granular view of constraints and limitations at involved stakeholder levels and challenges. Existing literature provides the visibility and role of leadership, culture, investment approach, value proposition, and significance. Nevertheless, this research yielded concrete reasons and relationships among these factors and how constraints at each level impact on digital transformation objectives of traditional firms.
5. In alignment with the literature review in chapter two, the outcomes of research findings have provided answers to research questions. In specific to question three, the research findings have identified the elements that crop up as impediments in the path of embracing the DT. In connection to the literature review, the elements yielded from the findings have brought much more profound relationships and their impacts on digital change transitions.
6. The research outcomes resulted in detecting the core issues at the top-management level and followed limitations and challenges, which reduces the scope of DT. Similarly, at middle management, external DT consultants and detected the customer perspectives of issues underlying. These outcomes are presented in a diagram showing the relationship and impacts level. (Fig 23,p.196).

6.3: Practice and policy implications

The motivation for this research is linked with the researcher's personal experience of being a stakeholder in the digital transformation process in the financial services firm. Hence, experienced the misperception and lack of clarity about the digital phenomenon fails DT adaption despite the capabilities and resources. Thus research adopted a phenomenological approach to exploring the perspectives about the extent and impacts of the DT through the key stakeholders. Thus, the outcomes of the research findings are significant in bringing the clarity and relationship impact of contributing elements in embracing the digital transformation adaption.

The research confirms the constant evolution of technology impacting the traditional business and service models (Alvensson et al.,2008; Herrmann et al., 2018; Hess, 2016) as the speed of technology is much faster than the speed of adaption by traditional WMS firms (Burnes,2004; Oliver Wyman report,2020; Kotter,2012). The research contributed by identifying the elements for policymakers and practitioners for a clearer understanding of inertia and synergistic factors in integrating resources.

Considering the nature of the business model of the WMS sector, firms are constantly attempting to adapt the technology to fuel the trust and loyalty factor in their customers(Hallmann & Rosenbloom, 2009; Cocca, 2016). However, the research outcomes offer a set of elements that disrupt the trust and loyalty factor; hence these research outcomes will provide directives and visibility to practitioners and leaders to review their plans in the direction of DT transitions.

The conceptual framework focused on user adoption theories, and it was formed by the union of two models, the TAM model (Davis,1989) and the Dynamic capability framework(Teece et al.,2007). It provides the relationship between the elements essential in assessing digital embracing, firstly assessing the influencing and compelling elements and secondly, exploring the perspectives in the process to develop the solutions. The developed conceptual framework provides a reference point to understand the perspectives of involved stakeholders and integrating them into a unified perspective towards achieving the digital goal.

The leaders of the wealth service firms and policymakers must pay attention to these research outcomes, as literature reveals that around 70% of firms in the financial sector have not achieved their set DT goals due to lack of clarity(HBR, 2019; Valdez-de-leon et al.,2016; Hess et al., 2016; Hughes, 2016). The term DT is overused in industry practices reducing the fine lines of differentiation between digitisation, digitalization and digital transformation(Christensen et al., 2016; Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2016; Bloomberg, 2018). The research precisely explains the significance of each phase of DT change about the internal culture and process of the WMS firms.

The recommended research framework, “ the capability funnel,” presents the adaption process to the DT in traditional settings. The research presented the intricacies and complexities underlying the adaption of digital change. Hence, the business leaders and policymakers should address these complexities gaps discussed above before planning to adopt technology to meet customers' expectations. Thus, the proposed framework supports achieving the Circular Transformation Cycle for the traditional firms assembling the three stages of the framework in building the fluid ecosystem with filtration process to customize with greater flexibility of chosen required capability and resources project-wise.

During the interview with all four groups of research participants, the important observations indicated the positive acceptance level on technology adaption but the constrained with various limitations and constraints, which is not discussed in any literature adequately. The main outcome indicates the underlying distress about the risk of losing the revenue-generating advisory model in case of transforming complete business model at top management level, while middle management levels have anxiety regarding their functional roles in advisory and consulting might transform into mere execution role if the organisation transform their business model. Hence these apprehensions at each level within traditional settings procrastinate the transformation process.

The research findings recommended adopting a digital twin model to avoid losing business revenue or customer loss due to frequent changes and delays in back-office processing in the onboarding process. The above section presents the outcomes of the findings as some outcomes and implications towards practice implications.

There are many elements interlinked with each other discussed briefly in chapter five. The policymakers and leaders of firms will benefit from an inside-out view over the constraints and limitations as well as perceptions underlying the DT transformational process. Hence the research states that the digital transformation journey can be successful only if an organisation can link the reflective assessment and prospective expected goals using the *GINC* perspective.

6.4: Research limitations

The limitations are crucial for any research as they cannot escape the limitations and disparities during the entire journey. As these variations occurred during the study will be the scope for further research to be conducted.

The research findings were purely perspective-focused, followed the phenomenological approach in exploring the participants' experiences. The other identified factors, such as regulatory elements, trading cost/fees, technicalities of technology and other factors in the supply chain, do not focus on this research.

The research earlier planned for ethnography methodology in empirical data collection but encountered the constraints due to the financial industry protocol of no access to any outsider or student. Hence phenomenological perspective was employed for semi-structured interviews, but again the outbreak of the Covid pandemic disrupted all access for direct interviews. Due to the lockdown situation, the remaining interviews were conducted virtually through MS-Teams, Zoom and Skype.

Due to the uncertainty and anxiety in Covid's environment during the first lockdown, many participants dropped out of interviews, expressing their overwhelmingness due to the new culture of working from home and work-related stress. Few senior participants dropped out of scheduled interviews as they were unsure about sharing any information or voicing their experiences during online interviews. Some declined to be part of any research during a pandemic and expressed to be contacted after the pandemic.

The research identified many factors and overviews during the research journey like organisational size and structure, cannibalization of business model and Robo advisory as the focus of research is to explore the perspectives towards digital transformation. Hence, there is enormous scope to research further on these aspects specific to the WMS sector.

This qualitative research shortlisted the case study sector specifically to the WMS firms only within the London region due to time and pandemic as constraints and limitations on movement. Hence there is considerable scope to conduct a comparative study among different regions to analyse the digital maturity and embrace the process.

Although the research outcomes are specific to the wealth management sector, holistically, the directives and outcomes apply to other industries as the proposed framework favours the customized filtering of capabilities and resource integration based on project requirements.

The empirical data collection process was conducted in mid of pandemic situations; hence many things were undergoing the change, accelerating digital induction into routine business conduct; hence it could be a novel contribution to revisit the same research theme post-Covid environment.

6.5: Revisit to research aim and objectives.

As explained in the initial chapter, this research adopted the problematization approach about the underlying problem issues within the WMS and gaps identified. The four research questions were designed to address the aim of research to explore the extent of the digital transformation in the WMS sector. In order to meet the research aim, the following four objectives were set and explained in chapter one (p.30). The below table presents the summarised format of explanation on how the research objective was accomplished in order to meet the aim of this research.

Table 14: Mapping of research objectives (Table format adopted from Mahmood.M,(2019)

<i>Research objectives</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Chapter</i>	<i>Summary of objectives accomplished</i>
<i>Examining the current and relevant literature in relation to explore the Digital Transformational phenomenon and its impact on the chosen WMS sector.</i>	<i>Met</i>	<i>Chapter 1 & 2</i>	<i>Chapter 1 presented a brief discussion of the background and current scenario of the WMS industry. The significance of DT outlines the relevance of digital change to the legacy business model. The literature review presents two approaches within the existing literature as well as the overview of influence and compelling factors in the adaption process.</i>
<i>Investigating the relationship and significance of critical success factors for the successful embracing of Digital Transformation.</i>	<i>Met</i>	<i>Chapter 2, 3,4</i>	<i>Chapter 2, 3 and 4 have present the detailed analysis and discussions consecutively the factors relevant in context to the WMS. The findings are in line with literature on outcomes of thematic analysis, presenting holistically the explanations of reasons for gaps identified. The perspectives and relationships between each factor and its impact.</i>
<i>Defining the perspectives on challenges and constraints in relation to chosen WMS sector's digital transitioning.</i>	<i>Met</i>	<i>Chapter 2, 5</i>	<i>The literature review provided a view on few critical sets of factors in relevance to the DT. Due to the lack of adequate literature in the context of chosen WMS sector, the qualitative method was adopted to explore the perspectives directly from stakeholders of the industry. The findings of the research provided a brief granular view on underlying the challenges and constraints discussed in relevance to participated executives associated at different levels with the traditional firms.</i>
<i>Discussing and sharing the key findings outlining the theoretical and practical implications of the research and offering directives for future research.</i>	<i>Met</i>	<i>Chapter 4,5,6</i>	<i>All research findings are presented and mapped into the recommended framework " Capability funnel" discussed and explained briefly in chapter 5 and mapped to raised research questions in the current chapter. Based on the research outcomes, the researchers have recommended the framework for business practices, and this brings more</i>

			<i>clarity on various impediments in the path of digital transitioning in the WMS industry. The leaders and practitioners will be benefitted from this research contribution.</i>
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6.6: Personal reflection of DBA journey

It is always quite challenging to pen down the self-reflection, but putting it down on paper can further improve my next challenge. It's been a long journey of 3 years into learning, unlearning and learning back again. Being a practitioner for 12 years with opportunities to work with some of the best organizations at various roles, I never dreamed of changing or plunging into the academic sector from there, especially the doctoral degree. After completing my Master's degree (MBA), I had a long break from the academic ecosystem and, as a practitioner, needed to explore, research and learn academic writing again, and the journey was not easy for me.

Following has been my key learnings during the DBA journey; the doctoral study is systematic learning and a very interconnected journey, the researcher needs to follow the systematic process in conducting the research and writing it down. Requires constant practice of writing and endurance to keep shifting between back and forth in the process of connecting each chapter. The most critical in DBA is time, as completion and submission of the thesis are time-bound; hence, researchers must work on timely approvals and access grants for smooth research and data collection process.

My journey has been like a roller-coaster ride from the 2nd year of DBA; apart from personal commitments and responsibilities, the Covid pandemic brought sets of obstacles in the smooth conduct of research. The pandemic situation blocked access to research participants, impeding the process of the empirical data collection method. It was emotionally draining and challenging as many participants declined to be part of research interviews, which extended the data collection process.

Despite being a practitioner for 12 years, I believe the research journey has changed my outlook towards business conduct. This research process has elevated the research skills and the significance of connecting the theoretical literature research to business practices and policymakers.

Despite all challenges encountered during the research journey, I was able to navigate successfully under the guidance of an academic supervisor, encouraging all situations and challenging times.

6.7: Closing comment

The research investigated and explored the extent and impact of digital transformation in the Wealth Management Services sector. This qualitative research has contributed by exploring the inside-out view of complexities from stakeholder perspectives about the digital transformation journey of traditional WMS firms. The research has unpacked the complex constraints, limitations and challenges in a granular level will be beneficial for top management, leaders and policymakers, to have a clear perception for developing the digital strategy, hence research is a significant contribution to the knowledge body and practitioners.

The research contributed by recommending the framework “ Capability funnel,” which is beneficial for leaders and policymakers to develop the unified strategy considering the perception-based research outcomes about underlying impediments for the DT transitioning. According to the best of the researcher’s knowledge, this research is the first to present the inside-out complexities and panoramic view of the DT adaption. The research outcomes are potentially significant in creating the visibility and synchronisation of stakeholders’ understanding about DT, as traditional WMS sectors are constantly attempting to be digital champions by overlooking critical aspects required for transformation.

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